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A quest for standardisation: Fully Convolutional Neural Networks and marine morphology mapping

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A rekindled interest in offshore mapping driven by the need for evidence-supported strategies for marine spatial planning is forcing a re-shaping of marine geomorphology mapping techniques. High-resolution MBES datasets allow for the creation of detailed maps of marine regions, but computer algorithms are indispensable to effectively facilitate the task.

Deep Learning, and in particular Fully Convolutional Neural Networks (FCNNs) can be applied to a marine bathymetric dataset to derive morphological classes over an entire continental shelf. FCNNs are a set of algorithms that produce pixel-wise classifications in order to create semantically segmented maps. We employed the Irish high-resolution shallow seabed bathymetric dataset to create a set of normalised derivatives commonly utilised in seabed morphology and habitat mapping. The class domains cover ten semantically distinct surface textures and submarine landforms present on the shelf, with our definitions aiming for simplicity, prevalence and distinctiveness. Sets of 50 or 100 labelled samples for each class were used to train several U-Net architectures with ResNet-50 and VGG-13 encoders. Our results show a maximum model precision of 0.84 and recall of 0.85, with some classes reaching as high as 0.99 in both. A simple majority (modal) voting combining the ten best models produced an excellent map with overall F1 score of 0.96 and class precisions and recalls superior to 0.87. For target classes exhibiting high recall (proportion of positives identified), models also show high precision (proportion of correct identifications) in predictions which confirms that the underlying class boundary has been learnt.

Derivative choice plays an important part in the performance of the networks, with hillshades combined with bathymetry providing the best results and aspect functions and VRM leading to an overall deterioration of prediction accuracies. To date, trials involving the application of pre-trained networks (i.e. FCNNs trained on Irish data) on novel but geomorphologically analogous bathymetric data (Baltic Sea and Inner Hebrides Sea) fail to reproduce the previous result, suggesting potential fundamental limitations of morphological labelling and inadequacy of derivative normalisation procedures.

High-Resolution Map of the Seafloor Grain Size Distribution along the Eastern Mediterranean Israeli Continental Shelf Using Multibeam Backscatter Data

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The grain size distribution along the continental shelf is a critical factor with profound implications for benthic habitats and human activities such as environmental management and infrastructure planning. This study, funded by the Ministry of Energy, presents the first stage of a comprehensive analysis of the spatial variability in grain size distribution along the Eastern Mediterranean shelf of Israel, utilizing multibeam backscatter data collected during annual surveys aboard the R/V Bat-Galim from 2017 to 2023. A mathematical correction was applied to the multibeam backscatter data using observed angular responses. Normalized backscatter responses obtained at sampled locations were cross-checked for reliable representation of seafloor sediments—spanning from silt to gravel and submerged rock surfaces—using in-situ samples. Where limited coverage exists, sparsely distributed backscatter data underwent spatial interpolation, filling gaps in the dataset to provide a more comprehensive spatial distribution of grain size across non-surveyed areas.

The result of the first stage is a high-resolution map of grain size distribution across the Israeli continental shelf, with a resolution of 250m per grid cell and coverage from 10m to 100m water depths. The preliminary findings highlight a dynamic spatial distribution across the study area, where the governing factor for grain size is not depth but rather the distance from shore. This distribution features a sandy seafloor strip, a region characterized by coarse and medium silt, and a transition into a muddy strip of clay extending westward to the shelf's edge. Additionally, gravelly areas were pinpointed as Aeolianite outcrops along the coast, occurring at water depths of 10-15m and 35-40m.

Seafloor sediment classification using locally normalized multibeam backscatter data proves to be a practical and cost-effective method. The creation of a detailed map illustrating the grain size distribution on the Israeli continental shelf provides valuable insights into sedimentary characteristics, offering essential information for habitat mapping, environmental monitoring, and coastal zone management. In the second stage, we will focus on collecting data in areas where it is sparse, as well as those less sedimentary homogeneous. To achieve this, we plan dedicated sediment sampling in these locations, coupled with validation and examination using remotely operated vehicles (ROVs). This approach aims to enhance the accuracy of our findings in these dynamic seafloor environments.

Multi-spectral acoustic mapping of buried shellfish beds in the North Sea

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The conservation of high-diversity seafloor habitats, such as shellfish aggregations, is of great significance to achieving a sustainable ocean environment. These habitats, however, can be threatened by bottom disturbance during human activities such as fisheries and sand extraction. From 2008, sand extraction from the North Sea has been prohibited within a distance of 100 m near the shellfish beds. To achieve this, it is particularly important to accurately map and regularly monitor the seafloor shellfish aggregations. In recent years, acoustic methods, especially multibeam echosounders (MBES), have been extensively used for seafloor characterization due to their ability of simultaneously collecting bathymetry and backscatter data in a large scale. Compared to the traditional bottom sampling, MBES can be a cost-effective and efficient alternative. In this study, we aim to map the shellfish beds using MBES. We also try to improve current MBES mapping abilities through the multi-spectral backscatter technique.

From 2021 to 2023, we measured three areas near the Wadden Sea in the North Sea using a multi-spectral MBES system R2Sonic 2026, which provides frequencies from 90 to 450 kHz. Sediment types of these areas ranged from fine to coarse sand. With respect to marine benthos, we found abundant sand mason worms (*Lanice conchilega*) in two areas, while the other one was entirely located on a shellfish bed (*Spisula*). Regarding the relation with median grain size and sand mason worm densities, no large difference was found between the backscatter data of different frequencies. As for the shellfish bed, however, unsupervised backscatter classification results of 90 and 450 kHz showed distinct patterns, which might be related to the existence of living shells inside the sediment body and on the seabed surface, respectively. We also attempted to directly link the multi-spectral backscatter to the marine benthos abundance through regression using machine learning methods, which might further bring the potential of using acoustic backscatter data to enhance species modelling.

Educating the Backscatter Workforce - Getting Better at Collecting Better Backscatter

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Multibeam acoustic backscatter is becoming more and more important as a remote sensing tool to help understand the nature of the seafloor. New applications are continually emerging from many sectors of the seabed mapping market ranging from offshore renewables to coastal zone management. These applications are supported by a growing research and development community to ensure that the acoustic backscatter products are fit for purpose. This community encompasses hardware and software vendors, seabed mappers, and of course the analysts and end-users of the data. Looking more completely, the community even includes the decision makers who are relying on the information being correct, credible, and reliable.

All of these efforts are hampered by the prevalence of substandard data, resulting either from poor mission planning or poor decision-making during acquisition. Many people are collecting backscatter data for many reasons. Most do it “ok”. Very few do it very well and many do it quite poorly. This problem is exacerbated by the fact that there is only so much that can be fixed in post-processing.

To help improve the overall quality and utility of backscatter mapping products, efforts have been made to raise awareness of best practices in a 2015 document from the Backscatter Working Group, titled "Backscatter measurements by seafloor-mapping sonars. Guidelines and Recommendations". An entire chapter, numbering 25 pages, is devoted to best practices to follow during planning and acquisition. These best practices, however, can prove difficult to turn into action without expert guidance, knowledge, or experience.

In this paper, we aim to bridge the gap between “book smarts” and “field smarts”. We will provide a high-level synthesis of recommended BSWG practices with an eye towards converting the guidelines into actionable procedures and practices. Additionally, some "Do and Don't" practices will be discussed for a selection of multibeam sonars to help the community get better at collecting better data.

MAREANO – multi-purpose ecosystem-based seabed mapping at 57-81°N

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There is growing demand for knowledge on marine environments, for multiple purposes. The information needs from both users and stewards of the sea are diverse. They may be simple or complex, clear or poorly defined, or anything in between. One increasingly common trait is that the information is needed very soon, immediately, or even yesterday. As urgency increases so does the risk of incomplete, perhaps less fit-for-purpose data and maps being used in an attempt to plug the information gaps. One way to prevent this and provide quality information to management and industry is to have dedicated national mapping programmes that follow standardised approaches and build a comprehensive and intercomparable regional knowledge framework.

The Norwegian offshore seabed mapping programme MAREANO started in 2005 with an annual budget of 5 million NOK (nearly 440 000 Euro) in popular fishing grounds off northern Norway. It has since developed into a large programme with a budget of 162 million NOK (around 14.2 million Euro) in 2024, operating across three seas, six degrees of latitude and a depth span of a few metres to nearly 6000 metres. So far, MAREANO, through a collaborative effort across the three partner institutions, has conducted multi-disciplinary, multi-purpose ecosystem-based seabed mapping of 300 000 km² in Norwegian waters. As well as providing an overview of the mapping progress here we highlight thematic maps of particular relevance to the GeoHab community from the Arctic, the deep part of the Norwegian sea and the North Sea. We present strategies for data acquisition, sampling, and planning and prioritisation of mapping areas and discuss how these have evolved to match both advances in scientific methods, survey practicalities, and management demands.

Evaluation of Chlorophyll-a retrieval algorithms in an Optically Complex Aquatic Environment

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Inland and coastal waters have great biological, economic, and social importance. Environmental changes and anthropogenic activities have been impacting these aquatic environments, which has been leading to the deterioration of water quality. Changes in water quality can be monitored by mapping biogeochemical parameters. One of the most commonly used biogeochemical parameter is Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a), which is the major photosynthetic pigment in aquatic phytoplankton and hence it provides a proxy about the abundance of the aquatic biomass. Chl-a can be retrieved from radiometric data acquired by optical sensors onboard satellites. Estimating Chl-a from remotely sensed data is challenging in inland and coastal waters due to the presence of various type and amount of optically complex substances.

Lately, machine learning methods have been introduced for Chl-a estimation in these optically complex aquatic environments. In order to successfully apply these methods and ensure their robustness a representative dataset is required. This is difficult to obtain due the large variations in these waters.

Therefore, the aim of this work is to analyze a study site showing various degree of optical complexity, to collect data and evaluate machine learning techniques for estimating Chl-a content. The study site is Lake Balaton, which is the largest shallow lake in Central Europe, situated in Hungary (46°50' N, 17°40' E). The lake shows large spatial and temporal variability, which provides an excellent opportunity to study and evaluate Chl-a retrieval algorithms. We collected in-situ radiometric data and corresponding water samples in the year of 2018 and 2021- 2023. The in-situ radiometric hyper-spectral measurements were obtained by a Trios RAMSES and WISP-3 (Water Insight Spectro Radiometer) sensors and Chl-a content was retrieved from water samples. This data was complemented with simulated data by using Hydrolight. Data collection was coordinated with the overpasses of the Sentinel-3 A and B satellites onboard the Ocean and Land Color Instruments (OLCI).

We used the in-situ data to train and evaluate various machine learning methods including Neural Network (NN) based methods, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) and the Gaussian Process Regression (GPR). The trained models were applied to remotely sensed data acquired by OLCI. Our study indicates that the NN and GPR models are suitable methods to estimate Chl-a content from remotely sensed data in various degree of optically complex aquatic environment. This might allow to transfer the methodology to other inland and coastal waters.

The Utility of Uncalibrated Bathymetry-Mode Backscatter from a Phase-measuring Sidescan Sonar

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Phase-measuring sidescan sonars are becoming more prevalent as the need for shallow water mapping increases. These instruments simultaneously collect co-located sidescan imagery and swath bathymetry, in addition, an uncalibrated backscatter data set, referred to here as bathymetry-mode backscatter (BMB), is also captured. The latter dataset has been minimally addressed in the literature. Here we present several recent and ongoing applications for the use of these data. They include the mapping of kelp beds and other submerged aquatic vegetation, characterization of bottom type, and the detection, localization and classification of targets and clutter associated with unexploded ordnance (UXO). Statistical regression models for several variables including bathymetry-mode backscatter amplitude, sounding distance from nadir, per-ping vessel roll, orientation offset between per-ping vessel heading and object orientation, and all combinations of these variables will be discussed for targets associated with UXO.

Two decades of mapping the deep-ocean seafloor and its minerals on the Norwegian continental shelf; technology, data, analyses and results

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Parts of the seabed of the Norwegian Continental Shelf (NOC) host deep-sea mineral resources in the form of deposits of polymetallic sulphides and ferro-manganese crusts. These areas are seaward of the shallow, continental crust-based shelf area that holds the oil and gas resources. The sulphide and crust deposits are based on oceanic crust and are exposed at the seabed or overlain by minor amounts of unconsolidated marine clays.

The Norwegian Petroleum Directorate (NPD) was established in 1972 as the Government expert body on geology and geophysics in the exploration for and management of the NOC petroleum resources and be the offshore national database. Since, the Directorate has been tasked also with exploring offshore geological resources in general, including deep-sea minerals, traps for CO₂, and sites for offshore wind installations; and changed name to the Norwegian Offshore Directorate.

The Directorate's current deep-sea minerals exploration and resource estimation is very much a spin-off from the University of Bergen's more than two decades of geological and biological deep-sea research. During the same period, the Directorate has acquired and released about 150 000 km² shipborne MBES within the deep-sea part of the NOC, which have been extensively used by Academia and industry. Since 2011, the Directorate has been acquiring geological, geophysical and environmental data on annual joint marine research cruises with the University of Bergen; and from 2019 also with the University of Tromsø. In addition, the Directorate has carried out its own annual marine data acquisition campaigns from 2018. During these recent year's activities, the Directorate has acquired almost 10 000 line km of high-resolution multibeam data, geophysical and electromagnetic data, and water-column data using deep-water AUVs, together with drill cores, and extensive rock sampling and video recording by ROV. The high-resolution data, video data, and rock samples that have been acquired until 2022 (including about 7000 line km AUV data) have been released to the public and are the basis for the resource assessment report published by the Directorate last year. The MBES data and video data are now in use for studies of habitats and biodiversity. In general, it seems that active hydrothermal vents at depths greater than 1000 meters are dominated by bacteria. The hard ground habitats are populated by sponges, whether it be on extinct hydrothermal deposits, manganese crust, or rock surfaces. More details on this will be presented.

An Enhanced Angular Range Analysis (eARA) workflow with backscatter and magnetometry data for wider industrial impact and uptake of INFOMAR data, Ireland

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With >100 offshore renewable energy (ORE) projects in development, Ireland's seabed is subject to intense geotechnical and geophysical investigation. In support of this, the INFOMAR programme aims to complete the mapping of the full extent of the Irish by 2026. Despite the advanced stage of data acquisition and volume of data, ORE developers require advanced analyses of these data such as angular range analysis (ARA). Given the volume of data acquired through the INFOMAR programme, analyses are often carried out in isolation. Furthermore, while ARA provides a useful estimation of sediment type, it often results in a reduced spatial accuracy with an overall 'blocky' appearance. Here, we offer a framework that combines ARA, object-based image analysis (OBIA) and other datasets (e.g. magnetometer) to create an enhanced Angular Range Analysis workflow (eARA) that can support the needs of the growing ORE industry in Ireland. eARA proposes to combine the high spatial resolution offered through the OBIA of multibeam echosounder backscatter and bathymetric data with the rich seabed contextual information provided by ARA and magnetometer data. This workflow will be applied to six broad areas of INFOMAR data in the North Celtic Sea, Ireland. The first three were chosen to appraise eARA's effectiveness at different depths, and the second three were chosen due to their potential for ORE developments. Moreover, this workflow will be scaled up and applied to the entire INFOMAR dataset with sediment samples available for calibration and accuracy assessment. Consequently, this research provides an objective sediment classification methodology and a magnetometry processing workflow that will aim to improve the industrial uptake of governmental data. Additionally, this work aims to i) provide valuable information regarding Ireland's seabed sediment composition and ii) provide novel approaches for the use of publicly available data which can accelerate both ORE decision-making and the development of ORE projects in Ireland.

Detailed, fast and scalable seafloor imaging data to accelerate seagrass-based blue carbon projects

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Despite the immense carbon sequestration potential of the seafloor, a serious lack of data has been hindering the growth of the blue carbon market. To cover this gap of knowledge, PlanBlue has been developed a scalable method to assess the carbon sequestration capacity of seagrass efficiently lifts this barrier. Our technology combines advanced imaging, underwater navigation, and machine learning to full automation. The result is highly detailed geo-referenced seafloor maps, which provide concurrent data on biomass, carbon sequestration potential, biodiversity, health, pollution, and human-made materials. Moreover, the analysis derives detailed insights on the health state of the seafloor (e.g., spectral recognitions of pigments to assess the state of photosystems of seagrass), biodiversity (e.g., habitat assessments, pollution, invasive species) and materials (e.g., (plastic) waste). Planblue technology can also offer a reliable solution to ground-truthing satellite datasets already available (e.g. Emodnet) to better assess ecosystem services of vegetation-based marine ecosystems, improving consequently marine policies and the impact for a more sustainable climate-friendly society.

Mapping benthic ecosystems for sustainable ocean stewardship in a shifting ocean climate

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In the Northwest Atlantic (NWA), marine ecosystems have been identified as particularly vulnerable to pressure from rapid changes in ocean parameters driven by climate shifts due to the region's important effect on the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) and to its significant role in ocean uptake of anthropogenic CO₂. Climate-induced change on the range and distribution patterns of benthic fauna are expected, but precise prediction on how these changes will occur, or the underlying abiotic and biotic drivers of change, are mostly unknown. When faced with warming temperatures, studies have shown that many species are likely to exhibit poleward range shifts. However, the role that availability of suitable benthic habitat plays in this process is largely unknown due to a scarcity of available seafloor mapping data. This is a critical gap in almost every study to date examining climate impacts on benthic faunal distributions. To address this knowledge gap, a major, multi-year research program commenced in 2020, funded through the Ocean Frontier Institute (OFI): The BEcoME project – Benthic Ecosystem Mapping and Engagement.

Here we present an update on the progress of the OFI BEcoME project, and include a case study example of mapping vulnerable ecosystems using multispectral multibeam backscatter data, examining sponge habitat on the Scotian Bank, off the east coast of Canada. The Sambro Bank Sponge Conservation Area (SBSCA) protects a globally unique aggregation of the glass sponge (*Vazella pourtalesii*), and we present the first comprehensive, high-resolution mapping study of this site. Multispectral multibeam echosounder (MBES) mapping at three operating frequencies and benthic drop camera surveys were conducted at the SBSCA in 2022. Video data were analysed to quantify the abundance and location of *V. pourtalesii* and all associated benthic fauna and sediment characteristics. Using the MBES data as predictor variables, the study created a generalized linear mixed model of *V. pourtalesii* presence in the SBSCA, with 90.1% accuracy. Four seafloor benthoscape classes were identified from the video imagery, with statistically distinct benthic macrofaunal communities associated with each class. The study creates a baseline assessment of the current community composition and habitat characteristics of the site, which can be used for future ecological monitoring and management within the shifting ocean climate of the NWA.

Using integrated distribution models to map deep-sea habitats

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In recent years, Predictive Habitat Models (PHMs) have become essential tools for the mapping of deep-sea habitats. One challenge in the use of PHMs to predict the distribution of VMEs and other habitats in the deep sea is that the information on the presence and abundance of indicator taxa originates from multiple sources. These include standardised surveys with different detectability and spatial scales (e.g. underwater video or bottom trawl surveys), and unstructured data from fisheries by-catch, and on-line databases (e.g. OBIS, GBIF). Common approaches to deal with this heterogeneity in data is to degrade it to the lowest common denominator (e.g. presence-only data) or to restrict the data used to fit the model. An alternative approach, rarely used in mapping deep-sea habitats, is the use of integrated species distribution models (IDMs). IDMs explicitly incorporate separate observation models for datasets of different origin, accommodating the structure and potential biases in each data source while maximising the information about the species's distribution. Here we demonstrate the use of IDMs, namely a state-space Bayesian point process model, to predict the distribution of taxa indicators off Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem (VME) off Iceland. Three heterogeneous data sources are used: direct observations from underwater video surveys (abundance data), by-catch from an bottom trawl survey (presence-absence data), and records from the BIOICE project (presence-only data). Model prediction are compared with the output of models fitted after pooling all sources as presence-only data and assuming a single observation model.

Do the Alf Reefs reveal a distinct ‘wave-field’ morphotype of cold-water coral structure, developed through autochthonous biogeogenic feedback?

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Calcareous framework-forming cold-water coral form topographic features with biogeogenic growth controlled through a balance between coral-growth rates, bioerosion and sediment trapping. These reefs and carbonate mounds are typically imaged as isolated mounded features which may elongate parallel to current flow and range from small patch reefs (metres tall) to giant carbonate mounds (100s of metres tall). On a finer scale, purely biogenic, undulatory reef-surface morphologies have been imaged, controlled by colony shadowing and self-organisation processes. High resolution surveying of deep cold-water coral reefs is time-consuming, requiring underwater robotics. To reveal fine-scale dynamics in the mid-slope section of the Belgica Mound Province (900m water depth, SW of Ireland), an area of over 18 km² was mapped using a multibeam echosounder mounted on the Holland I ROV at a constant 150 m altitude.

The hence discovered Alf Reefs represent a distinct and rarely imaged reef-morphology type consisting of a series of ridges and troughs running parallel to current flow. Coral absences in the troughs of the Alf Reefs indicate their formation through interactive biogeological processes with reef overshadowing making a significant contribution. Coral stature, biomass and biodiversity on ridges appears to increase with ridge size suggesting biogeogenic feedback developmental processes. Increased ridge height likely enhances ridge-top coral food flux, coral growth rates and sediment trapping conditions whereas troughs receive less food, with little or no coral and hence reduced sedimentation rates.

This wave-field cold-water coral reef growth form is less obvious than mound-types on low resolution deep-water seabed imagery and may be poorly imaged or mistaken for sediment wave fields. As such, the Alf Reefs may represent an alternative cold-water coral reef morphology or a missing step in the transition from coral garden to giant coral carbonate mounds.

Updates on the South African offshore mapping programme

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The South African offshore area is larger than the onshore region, and may be more than doubled if the extended shelf claim is ratified by the United Nations. The Council for Geoscience (CGS)' marine geoscience programme aims to create a complete map of South Africa, which seamlessly spans from the onshore area to the outermost edge of the offshore territory. This programme applies hydroacoustic and geophysical methods including multibeam bathymetry, magnetics and shallow- to medium-penetration sub-bottom profiling.

South Africa's rich and productive coastal waters contribute 35% to the national Gross Domestic Product. Our key objectives are to enhance economic growth through research on the coast and continental shelf.

The CGS team is undertaking mapping on the continental shelf mapping from 10 to 120 m water depths. For each map sheet, eight layers are produced which include (1) seafloor, or onshore-offshore, geology maps; (2) Hill-shaded Digital Elevation Models (DEM); (3) Colour-shaded DEMs; (4) Side-scan sonar mosaic of acoustic textures; (5) Marine benthic habitat maps; (6) Seismic reflection profiles; (7) Competent rock structural features and (8) Magnetic anomalies.

We are currently using these high-resolution marine geophysical data to conduct earthquake and tsunami hazard assessments, define areas current turbines (offshore renewables, e.g. from the Agulhas Current), create a shipwreck catalogue, provide baseline datasets for monitoring global change and future projections (sea-level change, coastal erosion), locate offshore strategic minerals resources and commodities, update nautical charts, and characterise and model benthic habitats and ecosystems to contribute to the South African Regional Environmental Management Plan.

This poster presentation provides an update on the South African seafloor mapping programme.

Geological Data Of The Mid-Atlantic Bight Continental Shelf For The Purpose Of Offshore Wind Turbine Foundation Recommendations

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The offshore wind energy sector is growing, and with that comes the expansion of larger projects that move into areas further off the coast. There is limited information on some locations in these areas. Specifically, there is limited subsurface geological data on the Mid-Atlantic Bight, which can, in turn, impact wind turbines' foundations in upcoming projects. The Bureau of Ocean Energy Management (BOEM) and offshore wind companies have assumed that the limited surficial data and core logs fully represent the Central Atlantic Call Area A and B. Through analyzing previous geological studies, the presented conclusion is that the sediments are too variable to make that assumption. A data compilation of the area's bathymetry, surficial sediments, subsurface sediments, paleochannels, and hazards will be helpful in addressing the knowledge gap. This information and the sediment requirements of each foundation type show that a detailed geological examination is necessary to conserve costs and improve knowledge of the area used for offshore wind energy.

Identifying the gaps: Geospatial analysis of modern and legacy hydrographic data in Whakaraupō/Lyttelton Harbour, Aotearoa New Zealand

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Seafloor mapping is crucial in better understanding and managing the coastal marine environment. Whakaraupō/Lyttelton Harbour and the wider Banks Peninsula in the South Island of Aotearoa New Zealand are ecologically important sites and parties interested in learning more about the area are proposing obtaining more multibeam echosounder (MBES) data in the area. Several organisations have collected sonar and other sounding data in the area for a variety of reasons, but these have not been combined into one dataset. This is necessary to understand where the ‘gaps’ are, and how to optimise future mapping efforts.

This undergraduate project collated data from Toitū Te Whenua Land Information New Zealand (LINZ), Lyttelton Port Company, Taihoro Nukurangi NIWA, and the University of Otago. These data sources were categorised as multibeam (MBES) for charting, MBES for port operations, MBES for scientific purposes, and digitised singlebeam (SBES) - courtesy of Seabed 2030. The results indicated areas with no sounding information, and areas with dated or lower accuracy data. Whakaraupō/Lyttelton Harbour significantly lacks MBES coverage, but this is primarily in areas of <2m water depth. Other nearby areas along the northern and eastern Banks Peninsula are also lacking MBES coverage. However, these outer areas are characterised by steep cliffs and rocky outcrops and appear to be hazardous to navigation, likely explaining why they haven’t yet been mapped.

Challenges faced when collating the data included the varying coordinate systems, vertical datums, spatial resolutions and metadata associated with the different datasets. We also identified errors resulting from time-dependent transformations that excluded deformation (which is very important in Aotearoa New Zealand!), and different legacy dataset file types.

Calculations were undertaken to determine the effort required to ‘fill the gap’ and it is suggested that a combination of MBES, LiDAR, and hyperspectral imagery are all viable options depending on overall survey objectives. This project investigated only a sliver of the marine geospatial data available in New Zealand and adds to useful conversations regarding data integration and data uses beyond the its initial purpose.

Impacts of repeated hurricane disturbance on shallow coastal sediment habitats and infaunal communities

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Shallow coastal sediments are important habitats for diverse communities of burrowing invertebrates (infauna), which contribute to global nutrient cycling and carbon storage. These sediments are susceptible to large-scale disturbances including hypoxia, coastal defense projects, fishing, and tropical cyclones. Tropical cyclones and other extreme storms can dramatically restructure shallow sediments and kill infauna through resuspension, advection, and deposition, causing abrasion, exposure to predators, and smothering. However, little is known about how storm-induced physical changes to sedimentary habitats affect post-storm infaunal community development. We collected sediment cores to assess the relationship between short (10 days) and long-term (6 weeks to 8 months) changes to surficial sediment properties (grain size distribution, porosity, organic content) and infaunal community structure in shallow (5, 12, and 20 m depths) coastal Alabama (USA) sediments before and after two consecutive tropical cyclone impacts in fall, 2020. Hurricane Sally was a near-Category 3 tropical cyclone and the storm's inner core passed directly over the study sites, generating winds up to 48.9 ms⁻¹ and significant wave heights reaching 8.2 m. Six weeks later, Hurricane Zeta (Category 3) made landfall ~250 km away but still produced winds >24 ms⁻¹ and >6 m waves. Post-Sally sedimentary changes varied spatially, likely due to interactions of storm-induced currents, bathymetry, and pre-Sally sediment type. Post-Sally sedimentary changes were mostly preserved despite physical forcing during Zeta, winter/spring winds, and riverine inputs.

We hypothesized that infaunal communities at sites exhibiting drastic and long-term post-storm sedimentary changes (e.g., sand deposition over mud) would be more impacted than those at less physically restructured sites. We analyzed differences in infaunal community structure, diversity, total abundance, and abundance of numerically dominant taxa before and after the storms. However, there were few direct storm impacts on infaunal community structure consistent with the magnitude of sedimentary change, likely due to a combination of pre-Sally disturbances, seasonal infaunal recruitment, and opportunistic taxa adapted to dynamic river-influenced sediments. The lack of storm-induced sediment restructuring impacts to the infaunal community furthers our understanding concerning the relative roles of disturbance history and seasonal dynamics of benthic communities for accurately relating physical habitat mapping to benthic community structure, particularly in dynamic coastal environments such as shallow and/or estuarine sediments. Additionally, the longer-term (>8 months) impacts of post-storm sedimentary changes on infaunal communities remain untested but are necessary for accurate prediction of extreme storm impacts to coastal benthic ecosystems, especially as enhanced storm intensity is predicted with climate change.

What a load of cobble! Unveiling biological insights from imagery particle size analysis using Segment Anything AI.

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To create habitat maps and to assess biological assemblages, ground truth data is required in the form of grabs and cores to determine sediment types along with imagery. Sediment can only be collected to a certain size depending on the gear, with gravel and cobbles often causing failures in the collection process. Therefore, larger gravel and cobbles sizes are often absent from particle size analysis (PSA) with estimates gained from user interpretation of imagery on the sorting, shape and percentage of each component. Recent advancements in machine learning have made new tools available such as the Segment Every Grain (SEG) package that uses the Segment Anything Model (SAM) developed by Meta (Facebook) for high-quality masks which characteristics of the sediment can be extracted. SAM often has overlapping mask and non-grain objects, to avoid this, SEG relies on a Unet-style, patch-based convolution neural network to the segmentation approach. This new tool has allowed the analysis of coarse sediment that is not suitable for grabs and bridge the gap between grabbable sediment and rock. We utilised images from the West of Wight-Barfleur Marine Protected Area, located 50km off the Dorset coast in the UK, designated for the protection of subtidal coarse sediment and subtidal mixed sediments. The SEG methodology, unveiled new insights into the biological assemblages, that that were previously inaccessible, in a novel and efficient way.

CMECS mapping for offshore wind development in the Humboldt Bay region of northern California

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Survey data collected in the Humboldt Bay region of northern California were used to create Coastal and Marine Ecological Classification Standard (CMECS, Federal Geographic Data Committee) surficial geology and benthic habitat maps as part of the USGS California Seafloor Mapping Program. Maps were produced for Cape Mendocino and the area off Humboldt Bay, four of the 83 map areas of the California Seafloor Mapping Program (CSMP). The maps are intended to provide regional bathymetric and habitat information in California State waters for offshore resource and ecosystem management including, offshore wind energy lease sites offshore of Humboldt Bay. The geospatial data includes substrate, geomorphic, and geologic attributed polygons and a three-class CMECS induration modifier raster. The induration rasters are derived from multibeam echosounder (MBES) data and derivatives of that data using video-supervised classification. The polygons are derived by combining the induration raster, a classified BPI raster, and a classified bathymetry raster that are subsequently converted to multi-attribute polygons. The attribute values conform to the CMECS standard to be useful for national ecosystems management. The area offshore of Cape Mendocino has abundant rocky habitat across the shelf, whereas the adjacent area off Humboldt Bay has none. This is the result of tectonic uplift associated with the Mendocino Triple Junction. To the north, offshore of Humboldt Bay, thickness of sediment above the transgressive discontinuity varies in thickness from 2 to 30 meters.

The maps are part of USGS Data Series 781, which can be found at <https://doi.org/10.3133/ds781>. The CSMP is a collaboration with California State University Monterey Bay (CSUMB) and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). Funding was provided in part by the California Ocean Protection Council.

Measuring Seagrass Dynamics with Multibeam Sonar

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Seagrass habitats provide ecologically essential functions. It is necessary to understand how human influences to seagrass will impact the corresponding community. A disparity exists between the scale of community and the methods commonly used to assess seagrass distribution. While satellite and airborne imagery are valuable for understanding large-scale, often whole estuary changes, they face limitations in accurately assessing patchy or transitioning habitats, as well as areas either too turbid or deep. Multibeam echosounder (MBES) sonar, especially when equipped with multiple spectral frequencies, has emerged as a powerful tool for examining high resolution seafloor features. The development of multispectral MBES systems, capable of measuring signals from various spectral bands especially the 200-700 nm wavelength range, offers more detailed information about habitat. The literature points to a need to further develop use of these tools, in order to understand how small variations in seagrass meadow structure, which have profound community effects, reflect sound under controlled and natural conditions.

The patterns discerned from acoustic reflections can provide essential insights to true seagrass dynamics and have been proven capable of presence/absence surveying at small scales. It is also possible to measure root structure, biomass, productivity, and even species variations due to changes in leaf geometry and spacing which reflects sound differently. Our research is advancing the understanding of the acoustic footprint of one species of seagrass through innovative tank studies, leveraging the EM 2040 MBES system ability to change the swath configuration between multibeam pings. These controlled tank experiments will observe different growth stages and cycles of *Vallisneria americana* (eelgrass). By quantifying acoustic signatures in controlled conditions, and influencing variables which will cause this highly phenotypically plastic species to change its structures over time, we aim to establish a foundational understanding of slight changes in acoustic response. This knowledge serves as the cornerstone for more comprehensive transect surveys in natural seagrass environments.

Simultaneously, we are developing an in-house Autonomous Surface Vessel (ASV) equipped with a mounted multibeam multispectral sonar device, specifically designed for shallow water habitat mapping. This ASV will serve as a valuable tool for testing the insights gained from our tank studies in controlled and real-world environments. Although seagrass ecosystems are typically found at relatively shallow depths, which limits the swath width achievable with MBES, even a swath width of 1-3 meters can provide high-resolution data and valuable insights. By conducting narrow transects extending beyond known seagrass areas into uncharted territory, we can gather crucial information about seagrass footprint boundaries and uncertainties. This ancillary yet crucial information can be used to ultimately improve the development of seagrass community models, which are growing as a decision making tool, but can only resolve meaningful predictions at the level of input data. This research initiative addresses an existing gap in the field but also has the potential to revolutionize seagrass mapping, offering a deeper insight into the acoustic complexity of these vital coastal ecosystems and their future dynamics.

Identifying resilient sites for seagrass restoration by integrating suitability modelling and climate forecasting.

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Seagrass restoration can reverse trajectories of decline and foster the return of previously lost ecosystem services. Unfortunately, poor site selection hinders restoration success. To guide site selection, suitability modelling is often used to identify contemporary restoration sites. However, suitability can change over time because of environmental perturbations, potentially rendering sites unsuitable under different scenarios. As such, there is a need for restoration practitioners to not only identify contemporary sites for restoration but also shortlist those that are resilient to environmental change, increasing the likely persistence of restored populations. Here we develop suitability models to identify contemporary intertidal and subtidal restoration sites to inform seagrass restoration planning in a large embayment in Victoria, Australia. Once potential restoration sites were identified, resilience was assessed using a series of environmental scenarios representing degradations to local light environments and climate change. Models initially identified 161 km² of areas potentially suitable for seagrass restoration. Of these, only 71% (115 km²) remained suitable for seagrass restoration under 2030 projections, whilst 62% (100 km²) remained suitable under 2090 projections. Moreover, where a contemporary restoration site remained above thresholds to be considered suitable under modelled scenarios, suitability was reduced, suggesting that climate change may both reduce the number of resilient sites for restoration and reduce the quality of remaining sites. Our results demonstrate the need to quantify the suitability of candidate restoration sites under future environmental perturbations to ensure that restoration resources are committed where the greatest opportunity for successful establishment is present, now and into the future.

Locating and Characterizing Submerged Springs on the West Florida Shelf Using Seafloor Mapping Technologies

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The rise of sea level over the past 20,000 years has led to the submersion of nearly half of Florida's original land mass, causing springs hypothesized to have been a gathering spot for prehistoric people to become submerged. As the water rose, humans lost touch with their ancestors' ways of life and migratory patterns. Interests in the potential significant cultural, archeological, and paleontological resources at submerged spring sites on the West Florida Shelf have spiked among geo-archeologists, historical experts, biologists, and geologists. The goal of the WF2305 research cruise aboard the R/V Western Flyer was to perform geophysical mapping of previously unidentified submerged springs dating from 10,000 cal BP at a maximum of 100 feet depth, with an aspiration to locate precontact archaeological sites and fill knowledge gaps about human history. Here we present preliminary results from new acoustic data collected in July 2023 from three survey areas in the Big Bend region of Florida. WF2305 utilized side-scan sonar (SSS) and sub-bottom profiling (SBP) to successfully map the three target areas and identify a submerged spring in one survey area. The results of the research cruise provided important insight into the current and past environment of the Big Bend area of the West Florida Shelf, including multiple SSS signatures demonstrating the heterogeneity of the area. The results emphasize the importance and advantages of mapping oceanic shelves to learn more about ancient environments and prehistoric populations. This research strengthens the public's knowledge of our history and our home, opens doors to future collaboration with Florida's Indigenous people, and allows scientists to further develop multidisciplinary characterization of the seafloor. Follow-up work on these survey areas is already being performed, specifically from follow-up cruise WF2306, through sediment cores, water samples, scuba, and remotely operated vehicle (ROV) video and image characterization to characterize the modern environmental setting of the survey areas and learn more about their geological history.

Iongairo, a collaborative approach to coastal habitat mapping in Aotearoa New Zealand

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Iongairo is a collaboration between local and central government agencies, indigenous communities and the University of Otago. The project leverages multibeam data collected by a national mapping initiative and aims to produce a platform and products that aid ecosystem and fisheries decision-making across a range of legislative frameworks. The focal region of the Iongairo project includes commercial fishing zones, marine reserves, aquaculture and customary protection areas (coastal ecosystems managed by indigenous committees). In a region that is significantly impacted by land derived sediment inputs we endeavour, for the first time, to develop a land change model that links seamlessly with bathymetric and marine habitat datasets to better understand the connectivity between systems that have historically been managed as separate entities. This talk focuses on the pathway to establishing the project priorities with multiple partners, the fieldwork approach and the data products required to implement policy.

Innovative Approaches in Environmental Impact Assessment for Deep-Sea Mining: A Case Study from the TRIDENT Project

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The TRIDENT project (Technology-based Impact Assessment Tool for Sustainable, Transparent Deep Sea Mining Exploration and Exploitation) aims to pioneer advanced solutions for monitoring environmental impacts resulting from deep-sea exploration and exploitation activities. A critical aspect of this endeavour is the establishment of a standardized framework, including a common language or vocabulary, to describe ecological management units. In shallow waters, hierarchical classification systems are conventionally employed to map biological communities and associated habitats into spatial management units known as biotopes. These biotopes play a pivotal role in identifying and quantifying changes from baseline conditions, as well as facilitating ecological risk prediction and modelling without an in-depth taxonomic understanding.

This presentation focuses on a case study that introduces a biotope classification scheme developed for a deep-sea site—specifically, the Tropic Seamount. Situated in the Northeast Atlantic Ocean off the coast of Northwest Africa, this flat-topped seamount with a depth of 1000 meters serves as the TRIDENT technology demonstration site. The derivation of biotopes involves the analysis of video footage and archived acoustic data. Our findings emphasize the effectiveness and simplicity of biotope classification for deep-sea impact assessment, showcasing a hybrid approach that integrates relatively low-resolution acoustic data with high-resolution video data. This study illustrates the feasibility of applying such methodologies in deep-sea environments, providing valuable insights for future standardized assessments in the context of environmental impact evaluations for deep-sea mining activities.

Assessing Temporal Changes in Restored Coral Reefs using Multiple Mapping Technologies

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In the Anthropocene, coastal ecosystems have experienced greater transformations than any other marine region, primarily due to their proximity to land-based sources of disturbance. Coral reefs are rapidly declining. Yet, they offer several ecosystem services, boasting biodiversity comparable to the Amazon Rainforest, providing a habitat to one-quarter of all marine life and are of cultural and economic significance. Regrettably, various stressors, including polluted river runoff from agricultural centers, sedimentation, overfishing, ocean acidification, and increasing ocean temperatures, pose challenges for corals to perform the function of reef building, potentially resulting in habitat loss for other organisms. Because of their economic and ecological importance, multiple agencies around the globe are focused on restoring coral reefs using various mechanisms, including coral outplanting. However, monitoring the long-term success of coral outplants is a time-intensive task as divers measure each coral individually. This method also complicates the evaluation of the relative health of a reef at spatial-temporal scales that are relevant for management purposes.

Consequently, it is becoming increasingly important to evaluate multiple mapping technologies for effective, cost-efficient monitoring across a range of spatial and temporal scales. Since 2021, we have acquired annual datasets of nine coral reefs in the Florida Keys, USA using uncrewed aircraft systems (UAS), multibeam echosounders (MBES), and diver collected underwater imagery processed in Structure-from-Motion (SfM) photogrammetry software. The datasets collected from the different platforms are enabling multiple comparisons between both different years and different combinations of data sets. We discuss how we use the datasets and derive seafloor terrain variables to detect and quantify changes in the restored reefs. Analysis of the data is providing insight into the changes occurring at the nine reefs included in this study, as well as informing recommendations for how to efficiently and cost-effectively monitor coral reef restoration sites across a range of spatial and temporal scales using various mapping technologies.

Influence of construction material and habitat characteristics on size-specific fish assemblages on a southern California artificial reef using Stereo-ROV

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Artificial reefs (ARs) and human-made infrastructure (e.g., offshore oil platforms, offshore wind, harbor breakwalls) can create fishing and economic opportunities by changing the distribution of local marine habitats and species. To aid in policy makers' evaluation of ARs in southern California, fish survey transects were conducted with an ROV fitted with a stereo-video system (Stereo-ROV) of the Bolsa Chica Artificial Reef (BCAR) complex. The BCAR complex is at a depth of 26-30 m in federal waters offshore of southern California. Construction of the first reef modules began in 1986, modules of varying size, complexity, and construction materials (e.g., concrete pier pilings, rubble, chimneys) were added until 1999. Stereo-ROV transects were conducted using a stratified sampling method to proportional survey the various construction materials. To define the extent of the AR modules (habitat classification) and calculate habitat characteristic metrics (e.g., vertical relief, BPI, rugosity, slope, heterogeneity) for each module, sonar data (bathymetry and acoustic backscatter) were collected by the Vantuna Research Group at Occidental College and analyzed in ArcGIS Pro and R by the Claisse Lab at Cal Poly Pomona. The Stereo-ROV video footage was analyzed using EventMeasure software and multivariate analyses will be used to determine how size-specific fish assemblages vary across AR construction materials and habitat complexity metrics.

Nature in Norway (NiN) – describing and classifying properties of nature: Relevance for seabed habitat mapping

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Nature in Norway (NiN) is a comprehensive system for describing and classifying nature, across terrestrial, freshwater, and marine environments in Norway. It is an application of the EcoSyst theory conceived by the same authors. At the heart of NiN is the Properties of Nature tree which we bring into focus here. This all-encompassing tree is split into biotic and abiotic components where certain key properties are further categorized into nature types, while others remain as environmental variables.

NiN v.3.0, was launched in November 2023, including several improvements to the marine components and an overhaul of the structure and code system. The system now offers a more solid framework for classification and description of seabed habitats, which is increasingly based on data analysis to supplement more general expert knowledge. We present some highlights of this development work including hypothesis testing using MAREANO data, revision and reorganization of NiN landforms, and development of documentation and guidelines for marine nature types. We also show some examples of NiN implementation in seabed mapping initiatives including MAREANO and the Marine Base Maps for the Coastal Zone pilot. Further, we discuss some remaining challenges for practical use of the system and some potential future developments.

We hope this work will promote community discussion on the relevance of NiN (EcoSyst) for seabed habitat mapping, as well as providing a platform for exploring synergies with habitat classification and related systems around the world.

Mapping Canada's West Coast Cold Seeps: new data for informed assessment

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Potential cold seeps have been previously mapped and published along the Canadian west coast using acoustic data from research and other vessels of opportunity. As further multibeam bathymetry data are collected along the shelf, the number of observed flares is increasing along with repeat observations within the footprint of the sonar. Cold seeps are assessed as Ecologically and Biologically Significant Areas (EBSAs) in Canada's commitment to protecting at least 30% of its seabed by 2030, consequently mapping and understanding these features is becoming increasingly important. These features also contribute to the carbon cycle and if gas flares reach the surface, they have potential to interact with the atmosphere and greenhouse gas cycle, implicating climate targets.

A 2022 expedition by the Research Vessel Sonne mapped water column observations of gas flares at Swiftsure Bank, Winona Basin and Hesquiat Slope with some flares exceeding 1000 m into the water column from the seabed. Co-located distinct morphology was also observed with high resolution seabed mapping at some of these sites. Three of the sites at Winona Basin and Hesquiat Slope were later visited in May 2023 by the Canadian Coast Guard Ship (CCGS) J. P. Tully Northeast Pacific Deep-sea Exploration Project (NEPDEP) expedition with remotely operated vehicle ROPOS and revealed visual bubbles in the water column, carbonate outcrops, gas hydrates, and chemosynthetic seep biota such as bacterial mats, clams, and tubeworms. Though these features were found at each site, the site geoscientific characteristics varied. Some areas had sheets of carbonate of varying thicknesses, some had large mounds of gas hydrate, and some had boulders. One particularly remarkable seep area created the perfect conditions for a deep-sea octopus nursery ground—a new discovery and one of the only few such nursery grounds known to science.

A summer 2023 expedition on the CCGS Vector collected water column data along with bathymetry data at Swiftsure Bank. The water column data are assessed for the first time here and tied in with the previous Swiftsure Bank observations. This presentation looks at the cold seep geological observations made on these expeditions along the Canadian Pacific margin, interpretations from the data collected, and it brings together the new findings with the previous mapping done to investigate repeat observations. The results will be used in future assessments of these EBSAs.

Optimal terrain attribute sampling methods for habitat suitability modeling in the fine-scale

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Habitat suitability modeling (HSM) has been increasing in popularity within the field of restoration ecology, due to the potential to identify and build favorable habitats for endangered species, as well as better understand species' environmental needs. These inquiries are no better displayed than in coral restoration, where HSMs have helped to explore the future of coral survival as ocean temperatures rise. One of the most common corals targeted for restoration and outplantation is *Acropora cervicornis* (staghorn coral), an endangered stony coral which builds essential reef structure throughout the Florida Keys. However, outplantation has resulted in mixed and unexplained success, at the scale of meters, within the reefscape. This has necessitated the development of site-specific HSMs using finer-resolution data (centimeters to meters), yet data sampling methods at such fine-scale resolutions are vulnerable to artifacts and amplifying noise. Here we determine which fine-scale terrain attributes and computational approaches most effectively account for the variability in healthy staghorn coral coverage. Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), constructed from Structure-from-Motion photogrammetry and multibeam echosounders, were developed for 8 sites within the lower Florida Keys. The resulting DEMs, as fine as 1cm and 50cm, respectively, were resampled to seven spatial resolutions ranging from 1cm to 1m. We then extracted over ten terrain attributes, at four different cell window sizes (extent of surrounding cells). Multiple iteration of curvature and rugosity were additionally used to evaluate if different computational versions of these terrain attributes explain variation at different resolutions. Partial Least Squares Regression predicted that some terrain attributes are more important at finer scale resolutions than at coarser resolutions, but are also more sensitive to cell window sizes. These results emphasize that in order to comprehensively model coral success within a reefscape we must delineate variance by analyzing fine-scale influences on coral health.

A combination of acoustic and optical remote sensing for habitat mapping offshore Tenerife (0-100 m water depth)

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Marine communities in coastal habitats play critical roles in nursery and biomass production, shelter and feeding, but these habitats are increasingly threatened by climate change, agriculture, industry and urban expansion. The overall objective of the OCEAN CITIZEN project is to develop a sustainable protocol for coastal restoration and conservation of marine biodiversity that is tailored to, but also replicable in, different ecozones, from the coastline to deeper waters. Habitat mapping of the different coastal communities is part of this protocol, both for maritime spatial planning of conservation and restoration measures, and for monitoring purposes. Therefore, we combine satellite imagery, airborne drone surveys, and shipborne acoustic remote sensing to contribute to the generation of habitat maps from the coastline to about 100 m depth in the main study area off Tenerife, Spain. Target habitats include the abiotic seafloor composition, coral reefs, black corals, rhodolites and macrophytes. Areas of overlap between the interpretation of commercial satellite imagery (EOMAP data available down to about 15 m depth) and the acoustic surveys carried out in the project (NORBIT iwbms data available down to about 10 m depth) allow a comparison of the sensitivity of the methods to the different habitats identified. Initial analysis shows good agreement between satellite derived bathymetry at 2 m resolution and multibeam echosounder derived bathymetry processed to 1 m resolution. The increased noise and lower resolution made interpretation of smaller features more difficult for the satellite derived bathymetry. In contrast, the boundaries of identified seafloor facies show significant differences between satellite imagery and multibeam echo sounder backscatter in the zone where the data overlap. These discrepancies need to be taken into account when producing a seamless habitat map from the coast towards deeper waters, but also highlight the opportunity to integrate different remote sensing technologies for effective coastal and marine habitat conservation.

Enhancing Marine Data Accessibility and Usability through FAIR Principles: The Case of Seamap Australia, Tasmania's Marine Atlas, GlobalArchive, and the IMOS Understanding Marine Imagery Sub facility

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Marine data is essential for scientific research, policy making, and sustainable management of the ocean. However, the quality and accessibility of marine data is often fragmented and challenging, hindering its full potential. The FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles provide a framework to make data more accessible, usable and trustworthy.

In this conference presentation, we will showcase the recent initiatives of Seamap Australia (<https://seamapaustralia.org/>), Tasmania's Marine Atlas (<https://tasmarineatlas.org/>), GlobalArchive (<https://globalarchive.org/>), and the IMOS Understanding Marine Imagery Sub facility (<https://squidle.org/>) in applying the FAIR principles to marine data. We will demonstrate how these platforms are working together to generate immersive and dynamic content, leveraging the strengths of each to provide user-focused information for various stakeholders. Our examples will include dynamic links between platforms to avoid duplicating efforts and state-of-knowledge reporting.

This presentation will provide insights and challenges into the current state of marine data management and highlight the progress made in making marine data FAIR. The findings will contribute to the ongoing efforts to improve the accessibility, quality, and impact of marine data for scientific research, policy-making, and sustainable management.

Habitat mapping for deep reef restoration and conservation in the LIFE DREAM project (Deep REef restoration And litter removal in the Mediterranean sea)

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The EU's biodiversity strategy for 2030 promotes the recovery of the biodiversity of European natural ecosystems through extending conservation networks, preventing and reducing anthropic impacts, and restoring the degraded natural heritage. Marine Deep Reefs (DR) are ecologically relevant benthic habitats acting as CO₂ sinks and attracting a highly diverse associated fauna. The multiple pressures DR are currently facing (e.g., climate change, fishery and littering) make the need to protect and restore these habitats more urgent. Marine Litter (ML) can affect the health status of DR, leading to the loss of associated ecological functions. Through an innovative, sustainable approach, the LIFE DREAM Project aims at mitigating the anthropic pressure on deep sensitive habitats (DR) and promoting their protection, recovery and preservation. LIFE DREAM will comprise active intervention to aid the regeneration of DR and will provide supporting information to extend the Natura 2000 network (N2K) to the deep sea by integrating biological data on DR and ecosystems services they supply with spatial data on human activities. Active restoration (deployment of artificial structure as substrate for DR the forming-species growth) will be integrated with passive restoration activities (ML removal in correspondence of DR).

Within the LIFE DREAM Project, maps of the distribution of DR and of multiple human uses were produced to provide a more comprehensive picture of the Project areas, to precisely identifying the locations for the deployment of artificial structures, and for ML removal. By integrating spatial information on DR distribution and human activities using a multi criteria analysis, the project provided an assessment of the human activities on DR and identified the areas for the new N2K sites, aimed at preserving the DR status after restoration activities.

Following the principles of the circular economy, among the ambitions of the Project is pairing the recovery with recycling of materials at the end of their lifecycle, converting the recovered ML in 2nd generation fuel that will reduce the CO₂ emissions.

We show the first results of the LIFE DREAM representing the baseline to extend the Natura 2000 network to the deep Mediterranean Sea and to restore deep sensitive habitats by providing best practices for DR restoration and the related costs and benefits.

Challenges for Marine Spatial Planning in Brazil: analysing the compatibility of multiple uses for the Espirito Santo State

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Brazil has a 7,491 km long coastline and an EEZ covering 3.6 million km², potentially reaching up to 5.1 million km², considering the bid presented before the Commission on the Limits of the Continental Shelf (UNCLOS). Despite the drawback of not yet having a nationally implemented marine spatial planning, several efforts are being made in this direction, with the advantage of having several other countries existing programs offering inspiration to achieve both economic and environmental objectives.

To support the initial process of Brazilian MSP, a project has been featured on SeaSketch platform by government representatives and consultants. Here, we analyze the information available using the Espirito Santo State as a case study. Our analysis is performed through a compatibility matrix, classifying each intersection among the distinct activities/uses as: Compatible Sea Uses Necessary, Sea Uses Compatible Under Certain Conditions and Conflicting Sea Uses.

A number of 28 uses and activities has been identified among land infrastructures (ports), recreational (nautical sports, scuba diving, free diving and artificial reefs), marine transportation, oil and gas (exploration platforms, blocks under concession and production fields), mining (process and potential areas), wind energy (licensing power lines, tower and farms), fishery (artisanal and industrial – pole and line, pots and traps, set longlines, drifting longlines, purse seiners and trawlers), coastal and marine protected areas, and priority areas for conservation (marine habitat, sea birds, marine mammals, invertebrates, sea turtles and fishes).

Possible conflicts were recognized among human activities (e.g., fishing and recreation) and between human activities and priority areas for conservation (mostly mining and oil production). Looking at the results' spatial distribution, we were able to identify which uses can occupy the same space (compatible uses) and which sea uses need appropriate spatial measures (compatible under certain conditions) or even are mutually exclusive (conflicting uses). To apply a spatial tool like SEANERGY would be useful to increase synergies and minimize conflicts. Moreover, a high degree of seabed habitat mapping can facilitate more detailed management to enable multiple uses, especially in areas where incompatible uses overlap. The results presented here is a conceptual proposal exercise since stakeholder's engagement on this phase is crucial to understand the underlying sectoral priorities and interests, to identify conflicts and problems, as well as, to develop solutions to the problems identified. Although aware that this is only a proto stage, the expectation is that a larger and adaptable project might benefit from the contributions provided here.

Squidle+: a large and growing repository of high-quality image annotations fostering data reuse, collaboration, synthesis and automated image analysis

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Squidle+ (squidle.org) is a marine image data management, discovery and annotation platform underpinning Australia's National Understanding Marine Imagery facility. It provides access to millions of images and annotations and is, to the best of our knowledge, the world's largest repository of openly accessible, easily discoverable, georeferenced seafloor images with associated annotations.

Squidle+ provides a centralised platform for managing, discovering, & annotating marine image data, offering advanced workflows for collaboratively analysing marine imagery & expediting data delivery. It adheres to FAIR principles, supporting granular discovery, access, sharing & fostering scientific research, collaboration, communication & educational outcomes. It integrates with existing cloud storage repositories, reducing the need for redundant image storage, and streamlines the importing, discoverability and accessibility of new survey data for many well-established marine image data collection programs.

Squidle+ features a user group framework, facilitating sharing and collaboration between users and also with external algorithms. Algorithms are set up as "users" of the system that interact through the comprehensive API backend. This architecture enables a variety of automated processing pipelines, connecting independent machine learning (ML) researchers to real-world ML problems with high-quality, validated training data. Conversely, it provides the marine science community access to algorithms that can help reduce annotation time and improve data quality. Traditionally, annotation tools that offer automation are wedded to a particular internal ML pipeline. This architecture offers unprecedented flexibility for ML integration.

SQUIDLE+ supports multiple standardised or user-defined vocabularies for annotation and also provides tools to translate between vocabularies. This gives users the flexibility to construct data sets that target specific scientific questions and facilitates data reuse, cross-project syntheses, large-scale machine learning training, and broad summaries like National State of Environment Reporting.

In this presentation we will showcase how the tools and features built into the Squidle+ platform facilitate advanced collaborative annotation workflows, enabling third-party integrations, big-picture reporting and automated annotation of marine imagery with transparency, quality control and unprecedented flexibility to accommodate multiple end user needs.

Habitat Geological Mapping Supports Artificial Fish Reef Construction in offshore of China

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The rapid economic development has significantly improved people's living standards and happiness, but it has also brought about numerous environmental issues, such as ecosystem imbalance due to overfishing, red tide occurrences caused by coastal eutrophication, and the loss of habitats due to land reclamation projects. China is no exception. According to statistics, in over 50 years, China has experienced a 53% loss in salt marsh wetlands, a 73% loss in mangrove areas, and an 80% loss in coral reef areas. Additionally, almost all seagrass beds have been lost, and the influx of nutrients from the Yangtze River has led to annual red tide events in the East China Sea, severely impacting marine ecological balance. Fortunately, everything is changing, as China has been committed to marine environmental protection and sustainable development. The country has established national marine nature reserves and ecosystem protection and restoration areas. Since 2015, extensive efforts, deployed numerous Artificial Fish Reefs (AFR), have been made to restore benthic biomass near coasts and islands and improve marine ecological environments. Approximately 220 marine ranches have been set up nationwide, with over 60 million cubic meters of AFR being deployed.

The China Geological Survey is currently conducting coastal and nearshore mapping projects aimed at supporting the development of coastal and nearshore resources and environmental protection. By analyzing marine survey data on hydrological environments, geological conditions, hydrodynamic conditions etc, these measures support the proper selection of placement for AFR and ensure the effective functionality of AFR. It is crucial for the success of marine conservation and ecosystem restoration efforts.

HSM predictions reveal the potential role of submarine canyons as reservoirs of deep-sea shrimp *Aristaeopsis edwardsiana* (Johnson, J. Y., 1868) stocks, in the Brazilian Meridional Margin

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Aristeid shrimps are valuable deep-sea resources in the Brazilian Meridional Margin (BMM). For seven years (2002 – 2009) three species were heavily exploited by slope trawlers in a narrow depth zone of the slope (700 - 800 m), resulting in important stock reductions and further ecosystem impacts. Limited scientific records indicated, however, that these species occurred in much deeper zones (up to 2000 m) mostly unavailable to the trawl fisheries. We modelled the spatial distribution and projected the probability of suitable habitats of *Aristaeopsis edwardsiana*, in the northern sector of the BMM. The region encompassed slope areas of Campos and Espírito Santo basins, which is characterized by numerous cross-slope blind canyons. The analysis was based on the species occurrence in 3,431 trawls conducted between 2004 and 2007. Explanatory environmental variables were extracted from a Digital Bathymetric Model produced by Petrobras in the context of oil and gas production licensing process, and from the high-resolution circulation model INALT20. An ensemble habitat suitability model (HSM) was built considering the results produced by three applied HSMs: GLM, Maxent and Random Forest. Water mass structure variables (bottom temperature and salinity), current speed and seafloor aspect (easterness) tended to exhibit a high explanatory role in all models. In general, suitable habitats included water masses mixture zones with reduced bottom flow dynamics. These habitats were most likely to occur between 200 and 800 m depths throughout the entire study area, and particularly within canyon systems where suitable habitats likely extend to over 1800 m depths. These are unreported distribution areas that could represent (a) important reservoirs inaccessible to the trawl fisheries and/or (b) pathways to mid-slope fishing areas. Because nearly all catches were formed by mature individuals, these canyons may provide important connections between spawning and pre-reproductive areas in the northern BMM.

Morphologic evidence for fluid seepage in the Western Baltic Sea

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Seafloor fluid seepage in coastal regions can result from gas venting, freshwater flow, or compaction induced sediment dewatering. When fluids expel into the water, they often bring the surrounding sediment into suspension. This usually results in characteristic seafloor depressions, that are often referred to as pockmarks. Here we summarize, for the first time, known shallow-water fluid seepage structures in the German section of the Baltic Sea and quantitatively invest their morphologies. To capture fluid seepage across the challenging first 10 m of water depth, where standard research ships do not sail, we combine shallow-water hydroacoustic data from portable multibeam systems with orthophotos and digital elevation models from repeated Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) surveys. Investigating seep morphologies along the entire German coastline, from the Flensburg Fjord to the Bay of Greifswald, we test whether different morphologic appearances can be related to specific driving processes and if seep distribution varies in space with respect to marine sediment thickness and distribution or hinterland geology. Our work further provides a baseline study for future investigations on possible temporal and spatial variations in seep activity.

Shallow water Processes and Transition to the Baltic Sea (STB)

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Coastal seas consist of distinct but closely linked ecosystems such as estuaries, shallow water habitats, tidal wetlands and the continental shelf. The coastal zone can be defined as the area where waves and currents remobilize sediments into the upper light flooded waters (approximately 0-10 m water depth in the Baltic Sea). Despite their essential role in the sequestration of material from land and shaping unique habitats, the shallow coastal waters are not integrated in our understanding of marine processes or in physical-biogeochemical modelling, although they are strongly affected by climate change and human activities. One of the reasons for this, is the lack of custom tailored scientific tools for thorough studies of the coastal zone, as well as the multitude of shallow water processes, that can only be disentangled in a truly interdisciplinary approach. To address these challenges, a new research area is implemented at the Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research Warnemuende (IOW), that combines:

- Shallow-water time series stations with specifically designed instruments at representative coastal sites.
- In-situ devices and vehicles including AUVs, flying drones, swimming catamarans and research ships, all equipped with multiple sensor packages, to study coastal zone processes.
- Field experiments in shallow coastal environments that investigate eddy covariance, methane, pH, as well as optical and acoustical remote sensing across scales.
- Multi-scale coupled physical-biogeochemical numerical models that exploit the field and laboratory data in order to quantify coastal zone processes and their feedback to the marginal sea.
- Management and planning tools for science-policy transfer, integrating existing tools and suitable new approaches in order to meet the increasing demand for information by authorities.

The key focus site of the new research area is the Baltic Sea. The IOW is open to collaborations on both, coastal zone research in the Baltic Sea region and the transfer of methods and gained knowledge to other coastal seas worldwide.

Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Sonar for centimeter scale mapping and imaging of seafloor hydrothermal deposits and lava flows, Galapagos Rift, Pacific Ocean.

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With the potential advent of deep-sea mining, development of high-resolution seafloor mapping and imaging for mineral exploration and environmental assessment and monitoring is needed. Interferometric synthetic aperture sonar (InSAS) is a relatively new technology that provides high-resolution imagery (3 cm/pixel) and bathymetry (25 cm/pixel) of the seafloor, with a total survey swath width of 300 m at 15 m altitude. InSAS has primarily been applied for military or commercial purposes (e.g., mine detection, pipeline surveys), and its application for seafloor characterization by the scientific community remains limited. The low survey altitude above the seafloor, the side-looking geometry of the system, and the requirements for a highly stable platform using InSAS presents a challenge when operating in rough terrain, such as mid-ocean ridges, where faults and volcanic edifices are often 100s of meters in size, both vertically and horizontally. In this presentation we will describe applications and challenges of using InSAS to characterize the seafloor. We will compare InSAS to conventional technologies (multi-beam echo sounders, side-scan sonars) and propose strategies for InSAS surveys over chaotic terrain using data from recent surveys along the volcanic and hydrothermally active Galapagos mid-ocean ridge.

The Galapagos ridge was surveyed during a 2023 cruise on board the Schmidt Ocean Institute *Falkor (Too)* research vessel, using a Kraken Robotics *MINSAS 120* system mounted on the ROV *SuBastian*. We collected 3.2 TB of InSAS imagery and bathymetry over 18h hours of ROV dives, covering 4.5 km² of seafloor. The InSAS data were ground-truthed by ROV video imagery and 1 m resolution bathymetry collected using a Kongsberg *M3* sonar system, also mounted on the ROV. The data allow us to resolve active, black smoking hydrothermal vents and diffuse venting areas, faults, fissures, and a range of lava morphologies, including sheet flows, lobate and pillow flows, collapse pits, columnar basalt talus, whorls, and lineations on the flow surfaces. The results also highlight the challenges resolving vertical or near-vertical surfaces on the seafloor. Overall, the study shows that, with careful survey design, InSAS is an effective tool for high-resolution characterization of geological features on the seafloor and has potential applications for environmental monitoring.

Making maps together: Collaborative seafloor mapping for sustainable marine conservation in Arctic Canada

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Canada has committed to conserve 30% of its coastal waters by 2030 and the majority of these habitats lie within the Arctic, where Inuit communities rely heavily on these marine environments for subsistence, economic, and cultural activities. Equitable placement of new protected areas need to respect the longstanding co-dependence of Inuit with these habitats and accommodate local priorities. Habitat maps can serve as a crucial tool to delineate and communicate these community-driven goals. The Imappivut Nunatsiavut Marine Plan focuses on co-managing a coastal marine area of interest (AOI) of 48,690 km² in the Labrador Sea. Ramah Bay, adjacent to the National Historic Site of Ramah in the Torngat Mountains National Park, was selected by Nunatsiavummiut as a culturally and historically significant- yet unmapped area in the AOI. Our research addresses this gap by creating a benthic habitat map of Ramah Bay, contributing scientific ecological knowledge needed for effective marine protected area (MPA) planning. The hamlet of Pangnirtung Fjord (Pang), Baffin Island, Nunavut serves as a contrasting case where mapping is focused on commercial benthos like scallops and urchins, driven by the community's active engagement in hunting and fishing.

Collaborating with Inuit boat operators, we employed non-invasive drop cameras at 28 sites in Pang, and 30 sites in Ramah. Continuous bathymetry and backscatter layers were collected on earlier research cruises using a Kongsberg EM 2040 and an R2 Sonic 2024 MBES. Species distribution modeling and supervised machine learning methods were employed on species matrices and ground-truthed seafloor sediment class layers to create predictive habitat maps. Pang contained 137 different morphospecies, with significant scallop and urchin presence. Ramah had 74 morphospecies, but was mostly populated by brittle stars and shrimp. These maps will be presented to decision makers at both the federal and local levels, as well as to community members to provide empowered research information access. Emphasizing the integration of local knowledge, our approach fosters an open dialogue that ensures the community's values and needs are incorporated. By examining the benthic ecology of these Arctic marine environments and actively involving local perspectives, our research contributes to a comprehensive framework for sustainable marine management. The result is marine planning which supports international targets as well as local communities.

Mapping an Urban Sea for Tidal Power – The Salish Urban Sea Exemplar

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Urban Sea Systems are interactive networks of all activities, natural and human-generated, operating within entire watersheds flowing into proximal coastal waters harboring one, or more, major port cities. The Salish Sea is one such system and connects Canada with the US. These urban seas also present opportunities to produce clean, renewable, and secure energy for both communities (high voltage) and sensing/monitoring networks (low voltage) to the system. We present a seafloor mapping technique using multibeam echosounder and backscatter data to target sites within the San Juan Archipelago (central Salish Urban Sea) that may be promising for locating multipurpose (low and high energy) tidal harvesting devices. Seafloor geomorphology can provide critical evidence of strong tidally driven bottom currents, useful for a first approximation of a current regime benefitting a tidal harvesting installation. Such a mapping effort, along with the characterization of marine benthic habitat types, not only benefits siting decisions but can set-the-stage for fast-tracking permitting processes. The constructed maps will assist in the engineering of eco-friendly devices by highlighting sensitive critical habitats and ambient biology that could be affected by a tidal harvesting mechanism design. Geological foundation information such as substrate type, seafloor stability, and sediment movement within a site can also be presented in map form, information critical to minimizing the footprint and assuring stability of any seafloor emplaced or anchored structure. We present a case study based on geological and biological habitat mapping efforts that apply to the increasing interest of industry, power utilities, government, environmental organizations, and other stakeholders in the generation of electrical power for the Salish Urban Sea System that is dependable, predictable, clean, and secure.

Example of seafloor tidal current scour (blue) and banner banks indicative of promising tidal harvesting sites that will be assessed for potential use offshore Orcas Island, central Salish Sea.

Marine Ecological Characteristics and Habitat Mapping in China

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Ocean is a three-dimensional ecosystem with a wide range of temporal and spatial scales, making it extremely challenging to visualize the characteristics of marine ecology. It is an important issue for marine managers and decision-makers to know what marine ecological types exist in a region, where they are distributed, what their current status is, and what their trends are. Based on the analysis of the relationship between organisms and the environment, this study constructs spatial data products of different marine elements, levels, and scales under a general framework of five multi-level groups: ecoregion group, water body group, landform group, sediment group and organism group, according to the “Guide to Marine Ecological Classification”. By combining the data products of each element, a list of marine habitat types and a distribution map of habitat types are constructed within different ecoregion. A marine ecological map database and web application are built to quickly query marine habitat types and ecological characteristics, providing a reference for the management based on the marine ecosystem.

Evaluating drone imaging and AI for mapping seagrass distribution and ecosystem services

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Coastal zone vegetation such as seagrass and rockweeds are important to human well-being, as nursery grounds for fish, and to marine carbon storage and sequestration. Seagrass is sensitive to ocean warming and eutrophication, in addition to natural pressures. Monitoring and mapping of these natural resources and assessing their contribution to ecosystem services using current technologies are both time consuming and expensive, yet important to ensure healthy marine ecosystems and quantify their role for marine carbon turnover and climate regulation. The SeaBee research infrastructure project (www.seabee.no) is developing novel methods to improve mapping and monitoring of coastal habitats. Using flying and surface drones, combined with RGB and multispectral imaging (MSI), and artificial intelligence (AI) analysis has demonstrated the benefits of using efficient tools for both mapping and monitoring of shallow water coastal habitats. Here we explore the possibilities to extend drone mapping towards ecosystems status assessments. The talk will present data on repetitive surveys of seagrass meadows and evaluate how well drone remote sensing can be used to assess seagrass distribution dynamics, changes in biomass, health status and carbon content on seasonal time scales. Drone data products are generated from orthomosaics and then converted into habitat classification maps using convolutional neural networks (CNN). By stacking and comparing temporally resolved data supported by ground truth data collected using traditional methods relevant species and habitat classes and their dynamics are quantified. Conclusively, we propose that flying and surface drones provide a unique and cost-efficient methodology for collection of high spatial and temporal resolution data, at demand, and as such can provide a much-needed tool for digitalized and reproducible ecosystem research and monitoring.

Biological associations with classified shoal features on the northwest Atlantic shallow marine shelf

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Sand is a finite resource facing growing demand around the world. Sand shoals may be targeted for dredging to support beach nourishment projects, and simultaneously support diverse biological communities. While the relationship between geomorphology and the associated ecosystems has been investigated on a site-by-site basis, a more systematic and regional approach has lagged. Recent research has improved the understanding of shoal habitat associations along the shallow shelf in a more consistent and quantifiable way.

A common definition of shoals was needed to better characterize factors that influence the distribution of marine organisms. Using publicly available bathymetry data for the northwest Atlantic, shoals were modelled based on depth, standard deviation of depth, slope, bathymetric position index, and distance to shoreline. Following unsupervised classification, modelled shoals were validated with 65-93% agreement. Shoal descriptions were subsequently adopted by a U.S. federal classification system, enabling a common standard among resource managers. With a reliable map of modelled shoals on the Atlantic and Gulf of Mexico shallow shelf, the significance of relationships between these features and benthic infauna and fishes were investigated in multiple regions. Predictor variables representing a variety of ecosystem scales, including bottom type, oceanographic conditions, and wetland/estuary proximity, were tested for influence on marine animal distribution at different trophic levels. Oceanographic variables tended to have the greatest influence on fish distribution, though shoal presence occasionally emerged as a small but significant variable. Quantifying the influence of physical, chemical, and biological features on marine animal presence allows resource managers to better characterize important habitats and therefore make more informed decisions.

Plastic pollution and benthic habitats – what is yet to come

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Around 460 MT of plastic was produced globally in 2019 and around 82 million tonnes/year escapes into the environment, so-called “mis-managed plastic waste” (MPW) ([data from UNEP](#)). An estimated 5.8 Mt/yr of MPW enters the world’s rivers but only some of this (between 0.13 to 2.46 million tons) reaches the ocean; 90% is thought to be retained in migrating point bars, lakes, levee banks and within man-made reservoirs. However, these plastic storage sites are ephemeral over different time scales and rivers will therefore continue to export plastic into the marine environment even if all MPW were stopped immediately. It is estimated that about 2% of MPW reaches the ocean; thus between 75 to 199 million tonnes of plastic has accumulated in the ocean (as of 2015) in two main places: a) between 46.7 and 126.4 Mt is stored along coasts; and b) between 50 and 90 Mt is stored suspended in the ocean mixed layer. Only around 3 Mt is stored in deep sea sediments. Plastic in coastal habitats is constantly reworked by waves and tides but is eventually sequestered in marine sediments. Plastic suspended in the water column is exported via faecal pellets and flocculation and will also eventually be sequestered in (deep sea) sediments. It follows that nearly all plastic that has escaped into the environment currently resides in temporary storage sites (in rivers, along coasts and suspended in the ocean) while gradually making its way, over decadal to millennial timescales, to its final resting place in the world’s marine sedimentary environments (i.e. benthic habitats). Therefore the flux of many millions of tonnes of plastic pollution into marine sedimentary environments will continue over the next century, regardless of any actions taken to curb the escape of plastic into the environment. Common rates of sedimentation and sediment mixing are small in comparison to the rate of plastic input meaning that the apparent concentration of plastic in surface sediments will continue to increase, in many cases surpassing safe limits for benthic biota.

A study of the effect of fine-scale terrain resolution on habitat suitability models on deep-sea (~3km) outcrops

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Terrain variables play an important role in habitat mapping and our ability to predict benthic biodiversity. High-resolution hydrographic surveys in the deep sea generate fine-resolution data of seafloor terrain, and understanding the impact of small changes in fine-scale resolution on habitat suitability models for deep-sea outcrops is of paramount importance as our mapping capabilities improve. In the deep-sea, on small outcrops, the loss of terrain details extracted from ‘lower’ (i.e. 10m vs 1m) resolution bathymetric grids will presumably result in overestimation of suitable habitat in distribution models. To understand the influence that fine-scale resolution has on suitability model predictions, we compared suitability models using terrain variables across a range of horizontal resolutions from one to 10m for two families: Schizopathidae (Black Coral) and Euplectellidae (Glass Sponge) on two outcrops in the Monterey Bay National Marine Sanctuary, USA. Our results indicate that the amount of suitable habitat varied with resolution. For both families, the 10m-resolution model identified more suitable habitat compared to the higher resolution models. We also found that the most informative variables for suitable habitat were consistent among all resolutions. Our findings are consistent with the generalizing effect seen in shallower depths and larger-scale resolutions (100s-1000s of meters). The implication of our findings is that, although minor from a full ocean depth perspective, the jump from one to 10m resolution has an impact on deep-sea suitable- habitat predictions. Although, in projects where overestimation of suitable habitats is negligible, such as those aimed at protection of an area, rather than protection of specific targets, opting for surveys at the lower end of the fine-scale resolution can offer time and cost advantages. For instance, if a model’s requirements are met by lower resolution data, conducting surveys from a higher altitude, and thus a wider swath, will reduce the time needed to cover the survey area. Faster surveys allow for the possibility of conducting additional surveys or saving on valuable ship time.

Implementing Sognefjorden MPA: Mapping the distribution of vulnerable deep-sea habitats to evaluate borders and protection level

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As part of the Norwegian national marine protection plan written in 2004, 36 representative coastal areas are being selected for protection. The implementation of the MPA in Sognefjord is now in its startup phase. In this startup phase, information on the distribution of deep-sea foundation species and the characteristics of the habitats they construct is imperative for management to decide borders and tailor protection levels within the MPA, including implement heavier protection in areas that are particularly vulnerable to today's and future human activities.

Sognefjord is the longest (205 km) and deepest (1308 m) fjord in Norway, creating a unique system that supports characteristic deep-sea communities in a coastal environment. It has however become apparent in the last years that knowledge of the distribution of vulnerable species in fjords is very limited, even in highly accessible regions.

We collated available data from previous underwater video and image surveys and conducted 57 new ROV surveys at various depths to increase the knowledgebase of the distribution of benthic foundation species in Sognefjord. The combined underwater video and image transects were used to map the distribution of 129 deep-sea foundation species and associated taxa, with a focus on those listed as threatened and declining by either OSPAR, ICES or the Norwegian Red List, and to describe the structure of the habitats they construct. The predicted distributions of the most common foundation species and associated communities were then modelled.

The results of this work will be presented, highlighting: (1) areas for MPA border adjustment, (2) areas that are candidates for extra protection measures, such as new identified areas of gorgonian and bamboo corals, (3) a preliminary assessment of human impact sites, and (4) prospects for stakeholder engagement to ensure local community support of the MPA management efforts. This work highlights the value of gathering spatial ecological data to enable informed knowledge-based management decisions.

NNEMO Cam – Neural Network Enhanced Marine Observation Camera

Harnessing AI to Classify Epifauna and Substrates

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We have long sought ways of streamlining and improving our processes for acquiring robust, quantifiable data on epibenthic assemblages from seabed imagery. The issues have tended to centre on limited quality control of counts and measurements of coverage – alongside inter-analyst biases associated with taxonomic identification. Furthermore, the costs associated with analyses of large seabed imagery datasets are significant. AI enabled seabed camera systems could help address each of these issues.

To this end, we have started development of a prototype AI-enabled seabed imagery system, using off-the-shelf components and in collaboration with the Alan Turing Institute. NNEMO Cam (Neural Network Enhanced Marine Observation Camera) is a self-contained remote or tethered camera system with the capability to perform real-time spatial AI and object classification tasks. In essence, this system can provide more robust estimations (using stereo derived image depth calculations) on organism volumes (and by extension, the possibility of estimations on biomass) - alongside the ability to identify and count individuals from key indicator taxa (such as sea pens). Work with the same components by others (not in a marine context) has shown the ability for real-time SLAM (Simultaneous Localisation and Mapping – i.e. point cloud photogrammetry) to be undertaken.

We are proposing to present here the results of the first and second sea trials of the prototype, focussing on the platform, housing and electronics in both a stand-alone and a tethered “live view” option, alongside successful deployment of real-time classification and tracking algorithms and subsequent enumeration of seapens at a site in the Celtic Sea.

Point Clouds & AI – A new approach for automatic hydro-acoustic habitat mapping using multibeam echosounders

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Multibeam echosounders (MBES) have become a standard instrument for bathymetric mapping. Modern systems transmit over 1000 beams at a ping rate of several hertz in shallow waters and can therefore record high-resolution point clouds (PCL) of echo returns from the seafloor as well as from objects in the water column. These high-resolution data provide valuable information not only about water depth, but also about benthic habitats. Usually, multibeam data are interpolated into regular grids, for performance and easy visualization reasons, before further analysis. This can result in significant loss of information. We suggest staying in the point cloud domain can be beneficial for certain habitats, especially when mapping vegetated seabeds. The increase of computer power over the last decades enables the calculation of derivatives from dense PCLs in a reasonable time, eliminating the need for prior rasterization.

Here we present our recent results on this novel approach for analyzing MBES data. Our approach comprises two main steps: First, the computation of characteristic features for each point in the PCL, by analyzing all points in a cylindrical neighbourhood. These features describe the arrangement and distribution of the points in relation to each other and include, among others, the so-called Eigen-features. In the second step, each point of the PCL is classified based on the features using a trained random forest. The random forest has to be trained beforehand in an area with sufficient ground truthing data. The classified PCL can afterwards be splitted into real seafloor returns, for more precise bathymetry, and echo returns of e.g. vegetation, enabling biomass estimation. We have implemented our approach using only open-source software and developed fast C++ programs.

We tested the approach on seagrass and stone habitats in the German part of the Western Baltic Sea. Therefore, we collected MBES data with a broadband NORBIT iWBMSc and a NORBIT iWBMS STX with a range resolution of 9 mm. The necessary ground-truthing data for training of the random forest were collect by in situ video. We achieved promising test performances for echo discrimination between bare seafloor, seagrass between 80 and 90 %. The results show that PCL analyses on high resolution shallow water multibeam surveying data performs very well. MBES surveying can therewith complement satellite optical seagrass mapping campaigns towards the goal of a seamless seagrass map in the coastal zone.

Development of a biologically-validated, global-scale, benthic habitat map for use in basin-scale marine spatial planning and area based management

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The global ocean is critical to life on our planet and is increasingly the subject of human use. Society depends on services provided by ocean ecosystems in which ocean life plays an intrinsic part. Predicting how ocean life will respond to pressures, because of both increasing human use and impacts of climate change, is the central basis for science informed decision-making and sustainable use. At its heart this requires a comprehensive spatial understanding of the distribution of species and habitats, i.e. maps. While there have been notable efforts to develop habitat maps for the world ocean, few have been developed specifically to represent variation in biological diversity. The aim of this study is to develop and validate a global benthic biological habitat map for use in spatial management of the ocean. Environmental data layers (or proxies thereof) for the five most well reported drivers of marine species distributions (biogeography, water mass structure, substrate, primary production), are used in a multi-step classification process to develop two new global scale seafloor biological habitat maps. These new maps, together with existing published global and Atlantic scale habitat classifications are validated using a benthic ‘clean’ version of the OBIS database in a replicated permanova analysis at the genus level. Results suggest both new models explain almost 50% of the variance in benthic biological community composition at a global scale at genus level and are statistically significantly better (explain more variance) than previously published models. We suggest these maps may provide a useful decision-support tool for area-based management of the global ocean and particularly areas beyond national jurisdiction within the context of the new The High Seas Treaty.

Identification of Potential Atlantic Sturgeon Spawning Habitat in the Delaware River through Side Scan Sonar: Post Army Corps of Engineers Main Channel Deepening Project

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The Atlantic Sturgeon has been listed as a federally endangered species since 2012. Only 125-250 adults return to the Delaware River to spawn, favoring regions of larger-grained sediments in fast-flowing reaches. Data on habitat requirements and locations have been listed as a priority item for Atlantic Sturgeon conservation efforts. Despite the broad application of side scan sonar in marine settings, there has been limited research applying side scan sonar in riverine environments, due to shallower depths and turbidity levels. This research uses side scan sonar to locate and quantify areas of Atlantic sturgeon (*A. oxyrinchus oxyrinchus*) spawning habitat in the recently dredged Delaware River, which has limited data available due to its high turbidity and heavy vessel traffic. The United States Army Corps of Engineers (USACE) Delaware River Main Channel Deepening Project (2010-2016, with ongoing maintenance) aimed to deepen the Federal Navigation Channel from 40 to 45 feet ($\approx 12-14$ m) through dredging and dynamite blasts from Philadelphia, Pennsylvania to the mouth of the Delaware Bay. According to the most recent Atlantic Sturgeon Status Report, dredging is one of the largest threats to the Delaware River subpopulation. Side scan surveys and accompanying sediment samples were collected from Bellevue Range, Delaware, to Tinicum Range, Pennsylvania in 2020. The resulting sediment classification maps document that although the blasting and dredging did create areas of coarse gravels and expose regions of bedrock which could serve as sources for potential Atlantic Sturgeon spawning habitat, the majority of this habitat is located within the navigation channel, which puts sturgeon at risk for vessel strikes. This study fills a gap in understanding long-term impacts of anthropogenic activities, such as channel deepening efforts, on the reproductive success of Atlantic Sturgeon, and can be applied to recovery efforts in other river systems.

Methane and carbon dioxide emissions as result of decomposition of organic matter in modern bottom sediments of the Gulf of Finland

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In the Russian part of the Gulf of Finland, there are extensive fields of stable accumulation of Holocene silts with a high (over 5%) organic matter (OM) content. The total area of Holocene silts deposits on the surface of the seabed in the Gulf of Finland is 4663 km².

In the context of modern climate change, the emission of greenhouse gases is of greatest interest. In particular, the emission of carbon dioxide from the decomposition of organic matter requires an assessment of its annual release into the atmosphere. For this purpose it is necessary to take into account: the rate of decomposition of organic matter in the bottom sediments and the mechanism of decomposition of organic matter with the determination of the volume of gas emitted. To determine the organic matter decomposition rate, the results of organic carbon (TOC) content determination in the intervals of 8 core columns were used. In this case, the sedimentation rate is 0.51 cm/year.

The decomposition mechanism of OM can be described by Buswell equation. Using this reaction equation we can calculate the theoretical specific volumes of methane and carbon dioxide per 1 m³ of sediment at STP. The volumes of carbon dioxide vary between 1.17 and 163.99 m³/m³ of sediment with carbon contents of 0.09 - 12.58 %, at the same time methane volumes vary between 1.97 and 274.78 m³/m³ of sediment.

At the same time, the methane produced in marine and freshwater sediments is partially oxidised under anaerobic conditions in the presence of nitrite and sulphate. Thus, anaerobic oxidation of methane (AOM) produces an equal volume of carbon dioxide, regardless of the sulfo- or nitro- group involved in the process. It is estimated that about 80% of methane produced from marine sediments is oxidised anaerobically.

Taking into account AOM, the obtained data of total carbon dioxide volumes, taking into account the sedimentation rate, allow to calculate the average value of carbon dioxide emission to the atmosphere, which is 0.18 m³/m³ of sediment per year (STP). At the same time, given the area of Holocene silt distribution in the Gulf of Finland, the annual carbon dioxide emission to the atmosphere would be 11 million m³/year (298 K, 0.1 MPa).

Managing bottom-disturbing fisheries and their impact on gravel beds in the Belgian part of the North Sea

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Gravel beds in the Belgian part of the North Sea (BPNS), are important ecological habitats that provide structural complexity in otherwise more two-dimensional, soft-sediment habitats, and in turn promote biomass and diversity. The century-long history of bottom-contacting fishing practices has degraded these once rich and diverse habitats significantly. The most recent environmental status assessment revealed that under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), a “Good Environmental Status” (GES) has not been reached and the habitat 1170 “Reefs” is in an unfavourable status according to the Habitats Directive (HD). In line with European environmental goals, a Natura 2000 site was established to protect ecologically important species and habitats and ultimately allow for recovery. This however is not possible as long as the historic bottom-contacting fishing practices continue to exert massive pressure on the environment.

To reach the goals set out in the European Union’s environmental directives, three regions inside of the BPNS have been proposed in 2021 where fishery restrictions are deemed necessary and are expected to be the most effective. The delineation of the proposed areas is based on biological valuation maps, sensitivity analyses of the benthic habitats, the impact of fishing métiers, and socio-economic analyses. In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the planned fishery restrictions, a monitoring protocol including a thorough baseline study was setup. The protocol is in line with the MSFD, as well as the HD and relies on non-destructive sampling methods. A combination of multi-beam echosounder and imagery data, collected via a towed videoframe, is gathered, providing insights into the biodiversity, community structure, and ecological status.

At this point, all samples for the baseline study have been collected and are being analysed. The final results and report are expected to be published late 2024.

Currently, semi-automated to automated image analysis pipelines are being developed to increase time efficiency. Future plans include expanding upon the current sampling methods with innovative methodologies such as photogrammetry.

Acoustic multibeam and topo bathymetric LiDAR analyses of Germany's complex underwater landscape around Heligoland

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Located in the southern North Sea, Heligoland is Germany's only offshore island and provides divers of underwater habitats for hundreds of species. Salt doming formed the island and extended bedrock outcrops over several km². The region is known for its growth of macroalgae and is characterized by strong tides, currents, and anthropogenic influences. Until now, only single-beam bathymetry with a maximum grid resolution of 10 m had been available. Not only from a nautical safety perspective but also to better constrain habitats associated with different rock formations, a higher-resolution bathymetry of the Heligoland rock shelf is crucial. We focused on generating an integrated map covering the island, the land-to-ocean transition zone, and the bathymetry down to 55 m with a 0.5 to 1 m horizontal resolution and a few centimeters vertical accuracy. Therefore, we employed advanced hydroacoustic techniques in combination with topo bathymetric LiDAR. Given distinct morphological changes on a few-meter scale, we foresee strong improvements in habitat mapping and modelling.

Large parts of the area have been surveyed during 6 cruises with a NORBIT iWBMS and a KONGSBERG EM2040 multibeam echosounder since 2021 in cooperation between the Kiel University and the German Hydrographic Agency (BSH). The island itself and the very shallow coastal zone were surveyed by a topo bathymetric LiDAR survey (LKN.SH). The shallow water depth, the complex hydrographic and geological setting, the strong tidal influence, and the underwater vegetation made the data recording and processing challenging. As a result, we were able to image even small structures, becoming visible on a 1 x 1 m grid. The new map discloses hitherto unknown domains such as Mesozoic outcrops, tectonic faults, mobile sands, seafloor pits, and anthropogenic influences. The geological units Bunter Sandstone, Chalk, and Shell Limestone were mapped out. Hard substrate's existence is key for predicting the habitable areas for macroalgae.

Analyses of the RIEGL VQ820 green LiDAR data revealed a maximum penetration depth of 3.5 meters below the water surface. It was found that the seafloor substrate type and colour are paramount to the overall depth penetration performance. A detectable bottom echo was only obtained from bright, sandy sedimentary environments. In turn, the dense populations of macroalgae and their canopies (*Laminaria hyperborea*) on the outcropping bedrock prohibited any seafloor signal returns. Therefore, we foresee mainly acoustic surveying in Heligoland's vegetated zone to close the gap between the coastline and the shallow bathymetry towards a seamless map.

Seabed habitat mapping supporting the development of offshore wind energy and marine planning in Australia

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There is a rapidly developing offshore renewables industry in Australia's continental shelf and slope waters, which will involve planning, installation, operation, and eventual decommissioning of significant offshore wind infrastructure. This includes five offshore wind declaration areas under consideration throughout south-eastern Australia, with a combined area of around 33,600 km². There is an immediate need to ensure that assessment and regulatory processes can access relevant information on seabed geomorphology, habitats and biodiversity to ensure that planning decisions are evidence based, gaps in understanding are identified, and are available to inform future research and monitoring by government and industry.

Seabed mapping data is being collated and analysed across the declaration areas to inform the assessment process. The national marine data portals of Ausseabed (ausseabed.gov.au/), Seamap Australia (seamapaustralia.org/) and the Australian Marine Spatial Information System (AM SIS) (ga.gov.au/scientific-topics/marine/jurisdiction/amsis) are proving fundamental to the assessment, management and delivery of seabed data to research-users. This is essential as a number of government agencies and regulators are responsible for administering licensing and regulatory processes for offshore wind. There will also be an increasing need for industry to access the available seabed data to understand aspects of sediment composition, acoustic noise, biodiversity values and regional environmental risk.

The current offshore wind areas across south-eastern Australia vary considerably in their extent, structure and composition of seabed habitats, which reflect the regional patterns of geology, geological history, coastal inputs and sediment transport. The broad distribution of rocky reefs reflects the patterns of bedrock geology, which varies in its geomorphic, textural and weathering attributes. Information is available at a range of resolutions depending on the availability of multibeam data, sediment surveys and data compilation and analysis. For example, high-resolution 5 m bathymetric grids are available for several areas, with more detailed geomorphic features defined from 1 m gridded multibeam data. In contrast, other areas have limited multibeam data, and seabed features are coarsely described from historical single-beam data – highlighting the importance of enhancing surveying efforts.

The development of continental shelf and slope areas for offshore wind across southern Australia is occurring in parallel with the advancement of a national Sustainable Ocean Plan. Details will be provided on the current state of knowledge of seabed mapping across the current offshore wind declaration areas within the context of existing and proposed marine spatial planning.

How do marine heat waves affect cold-water corals in the deep-sea?

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Ocean temperature plays an important role in governing the biophysical environment and in turn the realized ecological niche of benthic organisms and the distribution of marine habitats in the global ocean. As a result of anthropogenic-induced climate change Marine Heat Waves (MHWs) have resulted in widespread coral bleaching and mass mortality of tropical corals. Comparatively little is known about the impact of sub-surface MHWs on cold-water coral communities in the deep-sea, which lack the dependence on symbiotic zooxanthellae of their tropical cousins in surface waters. This study aims to address this deep-ocean knowledge gap utilising numerical modelling.

Previous studies have shown that prolonged and intense sub-surface MHWs and their cumulative intensity results in increasing thermal stress encountered by benthic organisms in depths down to 2000m. This study utilises hydrodynamic modelling outputs of reanalyses data to study impacts of sub-surface MHWs on cold-water corals. With intensification and duration of sub-surface MHWs predicted to rapidly increase in this century, it will increase the thermal stress experienced by cold-water corals and associated communities in the deep-sea.

It is hypothesized that through increased stratification and increased mixed layer depth due to increased storminess and deepening of the thermocline, cold-water coral distribution will be impacted physically, however their mortality is more likely to be dependent on food availability and oxygen supply. Preliminary results support this hypothesis in the North Atlantic, indicating that although the cold-water corals may be resilient to thermal stress physiologically, the resulting physically dynamic environment will lead to secondary impacts at the local scale in the benthic boundary layer. Furthermore, oxygen saturation has been found to decrease with increasing temperature and is likely to have a secondary impact on cold-water coral health. This study demonstrates how numerical modelling can provide quantitative spatial and temporal information of biophysical interactions to inform marine habitat mapping studies and species distribution models of habitat suitability.

Revisited mapping reveals short-term morphological changes by ongoing transport mechanisms along the shelf edge of the Eastern Mediterranean

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As part of the Israeli National Monitoring Program of the marine environment, we mapped the shelf-edge during 2022-2023, revisiting several sites that were mapped in previous surveys for scouring comet structures study. These rocky knolls, up to tens of meters wide, are located along the edge of the continental shelf of the Eastern Mediterranean offshore Israel, at water depths 90-150m, and they are hard bottom insular habitats, proven to host diverse ecological niches and unique faunal communities. Wherever they are found in Israeli waters, they are defined as unique habitats. Here, we present differential analyses among revisited surveys between 2017-2023.

Multibeam differential maps reveal elevation variations up to ~3m in the interaction zones between the rocky bottom and its surrounding soft sediment. We present results from 6 sites spread over ~150 km along the entire Israeli shelf edge, where both erosion and deposition of meters of sediment occurred around Comet structures over 1-6 years. Noticeable changes occur over shelf-edge parallel transects, implying dominant prevailing sediment driving forces. Additionally, a transect across a submarine canyon head in northern Israel shows an erosional zone of up to -1.5m sediment removal, suggesting active incision and development of the canyon.

In search of the driving forces, we conclude there has been active sediment transport by shelf parallel currents and possible CCW gyres along the shelf edge of the Eastern Mediterranean for the past thousands of years. Sediment removal in the canyon head implies active canyon incision and transport downslope towards the deep basin in a shelf perpendicular direction. The shelf edge plays an active role in sediment transport, both along-shelf and across into the deep basin. These conclusions suggest rapidly changing environments in these shelf-edge habitats, e.g. constant transport of sediment and erosion/deposition which reveals-and-cover, and varies the area of the rocky bottom surfaces and the zones of contact with the neighboring soft sediment. These conditions should be considered when investigating the properties of the faunal communities in these habitats and their interaction or connectivity aspects with their surroundings.

Habitat mapping of macroalgal vegetation by photogrammetry: A case of the artificial boulders reef in Genkai Sea, Japan.

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Macroalgal beds play important roles for coastal ecosystems by supplying food and habitat for various species of fish and invertebrates. Macroalgal beds have also attracted attention as a source of CO₂ absorption. In recent years, macroalgal beds have been significantly declining in a wide range of coastal areas in Japan. Therefore, attempts have been made to restore macroalgal beds by installing new substrates on the seafloor. However, detailed environmental conditions suitable for the establishment of macroalgal beds have not been elucidated. Therefore, in this study, we created a seafloor vegetation map of artificial macroalgal beds by underwater photogrammetry, and investigated habitat suitable conditions for each species of seaweeds.

The study site was the southern part of Himeshima, Genkai Sea, Japan. There is a flat sandy bottom at a depth of 4 to 10 meters surrounded by several cobble ridges. In this site, the areas of 80 m×20 m artificial macroalgal reefs were created by installing the boulders in the fiscal year 2016. A photogrammetry survey was conducted by SCUBA diving on March 7, 2023. Using a multi-camera system with three GoPro Hero8s, 9,751 photographs of the boulders reef were taken in 57 minutes. A 0.07 m resolution 3D model of the boulders reef was constructed using Agisoft Metashape from the photographs, and a macroalgal vegetation map was visualized on the 3D model.

On boulders placed on the sandy bottom, the appearance frequencies of *Sargassum* spp., *Undaria pinnatifida*, and geniculate coralline red algae were high. However, on boulders placed on the natural cobble ridges, seaweeds except for a short-lived species *Colpomenia sinuosa* few appeared, and most of the boulders were *C. sinuosa* community or bare rocks. On boulders placed on the sandy bottom but adjacent to the cobble ridges, the macroalgal vegetation was *C. sinuosa* community or bare rocks. Rich macroalgal vegetation established on the boulders surrounded by the sandy bottom, which is attributed to low density of purple sea urchin *Heliocidaris crassispina*, a main herbivorous animal in temperate waters of Japan.

According to the results of this study, in temperate waters of Japan, when creating artificial macroalgal beds, installation of boulders on the sandy bottom would be preferable, avoiding areas on or adjacent to the natural cobble reefs. Visualization of the seafloor vegetation serves as a tool to elucidate the efficient method for creation of artificial macroalgal beds.

A novel acoustic approach for effective biomass mapping of kelp biomass

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Kelp forests are among the largest and most productive vegetated ecosystems in the world. Ecological and economical importance has also received increasing attention within the last decade, due to their potentially large but not well understood role in carbon sequestration. Despite the growing interest in blue forests they remain largely unmapped, or they rely on limited data for coarse distribution models. based on data from satellite and drone technologies, underwater cameras and physical sampling.

We propose a novel acoustic method for efficiently assessing kelp biomass using a hull mounted echo sounder, similar to the types commonly found on most vessels. Echograms are manually inspected and interpreted using a standard interpretation procedure for acoustic abundance estimation using an open-source software for marine acoustics data.

For two consecutive years we surveyed an area of kelp forest (*Laminaria hyperborea*) in the Nordland County of Norway, recently opened for kelp harvesting, using acoustics - and video data for validation. The dataset includes transects both inside and outside of harvest zones with varying seabed substrate and kelp coverage. Implementing this method will significantly enhance the extent of spatial mapping, biomass estimation of kelp forests as well as environmental monitoring.

Marine geological data products from the European Seas and beyond – EMODnet Geology

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The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) is a network of organizations supported by the EU's integrated maritime policy. Traditionally, marine data collection, storage and access in Europe has been carried out in a fragmented manner. Most data collection has focused on a single purpose by a range of private and public organizations, often separately from each other. The EMODnet aims to assemble this fragmented and partly inaccessible marine data into coherent, interoperable, and freely available data products covering entire marine basins. As the resulting data products are open for use, the program is supporting any European maritime activity in promotion of sustainable use and management of the European seas. Through its Central Portal, EMODnet provides access to European marine data across seven discipline-based themes: Bathymetry, Biology, Chemistry, Geology, Human activities, Physics and Seabed Habitats. Data collection is mainly performed by these thematic projects, but a separate Data Ingestion project is collecting additional third-party data.

EMODnet Geology is delivering integrated and harmonized marine geological data products that contain seabed substrate, sediment accumulation rates and seabed erosion index database, seafloor geology including lithology and stratigraphy, Quaternary geology and geomorphology, coastal behaviour, geological events such as submarine landslides and earthquakes, marine mineral resources, as well as submerged landscapes of the European continental shelf at various timeframes. The products are presented at a scale of 1:100,000 or finer but also at coarser scales to ensure the maximum areal coverage. The current EMODnet Geology project phase is executed by a consortium of 40 partners and subcontractors, which core is made up by members of EuroGeoSurveys backed up by other partner organizations with valuable expertise and data.

Currently, EMODnet is expanding beyond the European Seas. In this context, one of the priorities of the ongoing project phase of EMODnet Geology is to ensure the integration of Caribbean Sea data into geology data products. In addition, the methods have been shared with the EMODnet PARTnership for China and Europe (EMOD-PACE) project (2019-2022).

The EMODnet Geology project is funded by The European Climate, Environment, and Infrastructure Executive Agency (CINEA) through contract EASME/EMFF/2020/3.1.11 - Lot 2/SI2.853812_EMODnet – Geology. Discover Europe's seabed geology at: <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/geology>

Biogeochemical features of gas saturated zones in the Gulf of Finland (Baltic Sea)

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Our study focuses on gas saturated zones in the Gulf of Finland (Baltic Sea). The fact of gas-saturation of the studied sediments (except for the reference station) was made based on the high resolution seismic which indicate the spatially pronounced acoustic anomalies in the surface sediments commonly referred to the presence of the free (bubbled) gas. As follows from our measurements the corresponding gas saturation is caused by methane formation or migration.

The sediments of the gas saturated zones contain methane as major compound of gas mixtures with concentrations 4-8 mmol below the zone of methane oxidation. Methane concentration in gas saturated sediments about 4 orders higher than in the sediments sampled from the gas-free zone. Molecular composition of hydrocarbon gases is evident of the ultimately microbial origin of methane. The diffusive fluxes of methane in sediments were varied from $1,71E-05$ to 1.04 mmol/m²day which corresponds to the published data for Baltic sea. The shallow sulfate-methane transition zone within the subbottom depth range 20-35 cm coinciding with drastic methane decrease suggests the intensive sulphate reduction coupled to anaerobic methane oxidation (AOM). The downward diffusive fluxes of sulfate are higher than those of methane at most of the stations. The downcore increase of pore water ammonia and phosphate demonstrates the progressive organic matter (OM) decomposition in early diagenesis, finally leading to generation of substrates for methanogenesis (acetate, H₂, CO₂). The drop in dissolved phosphate below 50 cmbsf, while ammonia continues to almost linearly grow downcore, may point at limitation the microbial community in phosphorous, but not in nitrogen. The observed trends in vertical distribution of carbon cycle bulk parameters suggest the progressive enrichment of pore water DIC as result of AOM and OM mineralization. Distribution of fluorescent DOM compounds indicates the sedimentary pore water enrichment in humic compounds with subbottom depth, probably responsible for downcore increase in pore water DOC content.

Relationships among remotely-sensed habitat features and fish assemblage structure on artificial reefs in southern California

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U.S. Federal and California State resource management agencies need informed best practices for the design and evaluation of future projects that add artificial reef (AR) habitat along the California coast for compensatory mitigation or habitat restoration, or for other infrastructure projects (e.g., offshore energy development, harbor breakwaters, structures to protect coastlines from sea level rise). In southern California it remains unclear to what extent existing artificial structures contribute to local and regional-scale ecological dynamics. Determining how the physical habitat characteristics of these ARs interact with regional drivers will improve forecasts about consequences of decisions related to marine infrastructure and support environmental review. We have quantified the physical attributes of five existing AR complexes (~66 AR modules) that were built decades ago to increase recreational fishing opportunities in southern California by analyzing geophysical sonar data (acoustic backscatter and bathymetry) collected by the Vantuna Research Group at Occidental College with a Multi-Phase Echo Sounder. These data were analyzed in ArcGIS Pro and in R with functions from the MultiscaleDTM package. Extent of AR modules were determined through classification of a multiband raster composed of acoustic backscatter and bathymetric derivatives (terrain ruggedness and slope) with object-based image analysis in ArcGIS Pro and then exported as a polygon shapefile. Reef habitat metrics were then quantified for each module using functions from the MultiscaleDTM package. For each AR module we have quantified size and location metrics (e.g., location, depth, reef extent), and relief and complexity metrics (e.g., slope, rugosity, terrain roughness, bathymetric position index, heterogeneity). Multivariate analyses were then used to examine which habitat features best explain patterns in the corresponding fish assemblage structure, particularly for ecologically and economically important species.

Documenting seagrass recovery following human disturbance using a low-cost sidescan sonar system

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Globally seagrasses are threatened and disappearing due to a variety of human activities. One of the most productive seagrass beds in Trinidad and Tobago disappeared from Williams Bay in 2014 with the construction of a boardwalk and other infrastructure along its shore. After construction concluded, the seagrasses started to slowly recover naturally. We are documenting this regrowth using a Lowrance HDS mapping system mounted to a kayak that also tows a kickboard with a downward-facing action camera underneath. The camera provides groundtruthing imagery and we can also compare the acoustic mosaics to satellite imagery and other *in situ* surveys for verification and accuracy assessments. The Lowrance HDS collects sidescan sonar imagery, single beam sonar data converted into depths, hardness and roughness, as well as GPS coordinates. Using this system, we mapped the shallow areas of Williams Bay in 2017, 2018 and 2023. Parallel tracks 10 m apart were run using a 50 m swath width and at a frequency of 455 kHz. The data were processed using ReefMaster software, which is another low-cost tool. The resulting map products were sidescan mosaics, bathymetry, hardness and roughness maps. Manual interpretations of these map layers were then performed to delineate the boundaries between seagrass and bare sand or rocks. A subset of the groundtruth data was used to enhance the interpretations, and the rest of the points used later to perform an accuracy assessment. Across the years, the extent, density, height and composition of the seagrasses changed, especially between 2018 and 2023 when shoal grass expanded, grew taller and more dense and turtle grass patches increased in area and height. Extracting these patterns using the sidescan mosaics and other map layers has been difficult and requires further efforts to better model the distribution and extract the relevant variables of interest, such as species, height and density. Artificial Intelligence may be a suitable means for improving the interpretation of the acoustic data and decreasing the time required to perform delineations. If the processing can be streamlined and standardized, these inexpensive tools can be more effectively used to monitor seagrass beds across the globe and help us document impacts to them and develop more effective restoration.

Evaluating the impact of boating pressure on common seagrass (*Zostera marina*) habitats

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Marine protected areas (MPA) with high recreational values are important tourist attractions. It's widely known that tourism has positive effect on e.g. local economy and awareness raising but tourism may also impact negatively on the ecological values within the protected area. For effective management of MPAs we need to find ways to evaluate and assess the impact of recreational use and safeguard the ecological integrity if necessary. In this study, we present our methodological approach and preliminary results on evaluating the impact of anchoring disturbance of recreational boaters on common seagrass habitat, in an Archipelago National Park island that attracts a lot of visitors and holds nationally significant common seagrass population. Our hypotheses is that intensive anchoring has degraded the seagrass population in the area.

We targeted detailed survey based on the amount and location of anchored boats that were detected with Sentinel-2 satellite imagery from 2016-2023. Based on this information we sampled selected area of intensive anchoring and control areas for estimating the impact of anchoring to common eelgrass habitats. We tested several methods to map eelgrass coverage and condition including drone survey, simultaneous underwater imaging and downscan with Autonomous Surface Vehicle (ASV) and scuba diving. Based on the experiences, we will discuss the success of the methodological approach in evaluating the eelgrass coverage and condition and discuss feasible ways to monitor the impact of recreational tourism to valuable shallow water habitats. We will present our findings in the conference.

Climate and oceanographic control on seabed change in the marginal seas – the Baltic Sea case

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A marked sedimentological change in subsurface sediments from the entire Baltic Proper, the Baltic Sea, has been previously observed. We have studied this seabed change using acoustic profiling, hydrographic instrumental monitoring (AD 1950-2021) data (near-bottom-water parameters: oxygen, salinity and temperature) and sediment core data like artificial radionuclide (¹³⁷Cs, ²⁴¹Am), the total carbon (TC) and total inorganic carbon (TIC) contents, XRF scanning data (e.g., Mn, Ca), and benthic foraminifer counting.

The results of our studies of sediment cores from basin-wide transects indicate (Moros et al. 2024) that this sedimentological change was caused by large hydrographic and environmental changes that started at the end of the Little Ice Age (LIA) (~ AD 1850) and were accelerated by a rapid change in water column stratification resulting from the giant saline water inflow from the North Sea into the Baltic Sea basin in AD 1951. On a longer timescale, winter-time deep-water convection gradually weakened due to the warming of the atmosphere and ocean after the end of the LIA, but still contributed to complete ventilation of bottom water of the entire Baltic Proper, while currents prevented accumulation and even eroded seabed sediments above a water depths of ca. 150-160 m until the early 1950's. The hydrographic conditions changed markedly with the giant saline water inflow AD 1951. The accompanied increase in stratification caused a collapse of the already weakened vertical convection, leading to hypoxia in the bottom waters, which in turn forced a sudden phosphate release from the sediments (i.e., internal loading) and increased primary production in the late 1950s. The sharp sedimentological boundary reflects this sudden environmental change, with the convection collapse the delivery of fine-grained re-worked material to the subbasins stopped, the base (depth) of sediment re-suspension shifted upwards and much calmer conditions prevailed also in shallower water depths until today. This enabled from the late 1950s onwards the accumulation of organic carbon-rich sediments also at water depths between 150 and ca. 60–70 m. The recent limit of sediment resuspension at a water depth of ca. 60–70 m marks the modern winter-time mixing depth.

The speed (<10 years) of the seabed change triggered by external forcing (temperature and stratification) and accelerated by internal processes is remarkable. The combined effect of stratification and temperature changes seems to have played a stronger role than previously thought.

Moros et al., 2024. Giant saltwater inflow in AD 1951 triggered Baltic Sea hypoxia. *Boreas*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bor.12643>.

SeaMoreEco - Seamless monitoring, restoration and conservation in the northern Gulf of Bothnia

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The shallow bottoms of the northern Gulf of Bothnia are important areas for the whole marine environment, for example due to their high biodiversity. At the same time the species and habitats of the shallow areas are under increasing threat from human activities and climate change effects. If actions are not taken as soon as possible, they are under risk of considerable decline. A challenge for management today is the lack of knowledge of occurring species and habitats and practical solutions on how to improve their environmental status. Several marine macrophyte species are unique to the northern Gulf of Bothnia and populations are spread across the border existing on both Swedish and Finnish territory, making cross-border collaboration necessary for the success of management. The SeaMoreEco project joins expertise from marine biological and geological management in Finland and Sweden with the overall objective to test, develop and demonstrate methods for efficient monitoring, conservation and restoration of biodiversity on shallow bottoms, with a focus on threatened species and habitats and invasive alien species.

The monitoring activities involve a) testing remote sensing methods to map and monitor underwater vegetation, using acoustic remote sensing, flying drones, floating drones and satellites and b) develop monitoring techniques for invasive and threatened species. The restoration and conservation activities involve a) test restoration methods such as removal of invasive species and translocation of endangered species b) establish a cross border restoration network.

Early results from the first field include e.g:

- a) The acoustic-seismic soundings and seabed sampling suggest that in the shallow water study areas of the eastern coast of GoB (Finland), large areas “suffer” seabed erosion (e.g., by ice and wave action). More sheltered river estuaries are hot spots for sediment accumulation, and in some places with very dense and high (soft bottom) vegetation.
- b) Commercial drones can be used as a tool identifying different vegetation habitats as well as invasive species (e.g. water weed - *Elodea*) in shallow coastal bays in the northern Gulf of Bothnia. This information, in combination with the knowledge of endangered species distribution, is important when identifying where restoration efforts should be considered.

SeaMoreEco (Seamless monitoring, restoration and conservation in the northern Gulf of Bothnia) is an Interreg Aurora project co-funded by Lapin Liitto and Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management.

Effect of submarine groundwater discharge on benthic coastal communities of Prince Edward Island, Canada

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The subsurface flow of freshwater into the ocean provides direct input of freshened water to coastal and offshore benthic ecosystems. This submarine groundwater discharge (SGD) occurs on continental margins, where terrestrial groundwater flows along subsurface aquifers and seeps out from beneath the ocean sediment. Offshore freshwater seepages are a direct link between the terrestrial and marine environment, bringing nutrients (P, N, SiO₂), pollutants, gases (CH₄, CO₂) and metals (Fe, Ni, Zn) to the seabed.

The different make-up of this water may influence primary production, geochemistry, temperature, and mixing along the seafloor. Freshwater seepages have the potential to create estuarine conditions around areas of discharge, which can alter benthic community structure and function. While the impact of SGD on benthic communities has been studied, results are conflicting and vary depending on seafloor processes or composition.

During fall 2021, an Ocean Frontier Institute (OFI) led project (SOURCE) found evidence, in gravity cores, of freshened groundwater seepage off the northern coast of Prince Edward Island (PEI), Canada, in the southern Gulf of St. Lawrence region. Approximately 100km² of Kongsberg EM710 bathymetric data were obtained at 30-80m water depth from the identified groundwater seepage areas. The water column data were analyzed to pinpoint zones where flares were visible, which may be indicative of freshwater discharge, to narrow down seepage sites. The possible implication for the ecosystem services provided by the local benthic communities will be explored in summer 2024 with drop camera, benthic grab sampling and CTD work. Available geomorphic data combined with groundtruthing and biological sampling will be used to create a benthic habitat map to showcase the potential effects of SGD on the benthic environment of PEI, with aims of understanding how benthic communities differ around areas of active freshwater seepage. Knowing if and how SGD influences northern PEI benthic community dynamics is important for understanding future implications for local fisheries and ecosystem management considerations.

Drone and ground-truth data collection, image annotation and machine learning for coastal habitat mapping and classification

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Aerial drone imaging is an efficient tool for mapping and monitoring of coastal habitats at high spatial and temporal resolution. Specifically, drone imaging allows for time- and cost-efficient mapping covering larger areas than traditional mapping and monitoring techniques, while also providing more detailed information than those from airplanes and satellites, enabling for example to differentiate various types of coastal vegetation based on individual spectral reflectance and structural patterns. Here, we will present a systematic and standardized method to 1) collect drone images and create orthomosaics; 2) collect ground-truth data in the field to guide the image annotation and to validate the final map product; 3) annotate drone images into hierarchical habitat classes; and 4) train machine learning algorithms for habitat classification. The method is based on experiences accumulated through numerous drone mission campaigns and subsequent data analysis work collected during > 5 years, as part of the SeaBee research infrastructure for drone-based research, mapping, and monitoring. Although focused on the coastal zone, the same approach can largely be applied for freshwater, and even terrestrial field data collection. As a case study, we present the results from a field campaign conducted in 2022 that employed these methods to map a coastal site dominated by seagrass, seaweed and kelp, in addition to sandy sediments, gravel, and boulders. Such detailed and comprehensive mapping and classification can serve as a vital tool to understand and preserve ecologically valuable marine ecosystems and is essential to secure sustainable management actions.

Seafloor mapping as a key component of decision-support for marine industries: applications for aquaculture in Tasmania, Australia

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Seafloor mapping is a key source of information guiding the operations and management of marine primary industries, e.g., fisheries, offshore oil and gas, and marine energy. Data products and interpretation from high-resolution seafloor mapping can support decision-making on the exploitation, planning, siting, and monitoring of marine industries, augmenting the value of these data against other uses, such as biodiversity and habitat mapping, and conservation planning. Here, we focus on how seafloor mapping supports sustainable aquaculture management by summarizing research from Tasmania, Australia, where aquaculture is a core primary industry. We highlight empirical and modelling approaches to decision-support for government and industry – and lessons learned – from two applications in marine spatial planning and environmental monitoring: 1) mapping ‘rocky reefs’ (consolidated hard substrate) as key socio-ecological features for aquaculture siting to reduce environmental impacts and conflict with other uses, and 2) using sediment composition from high-resolution mapping as further context for hydrodynamics and biogeochemical modelling in a high-energy coastal embayment. We found that when embedded in cross-disciplinary research and engaging with stakeholders seafloor mapping can provide direct benefits to decision-makers, industry, and researchers. These benefits are particularly promising in the context of marine spatial planning meant to ensure the sustainable management of marine resources.

Spatial and temporal evolution of tidal channels benthic habitats in the Northern Venice Lagoon using multibeam echosounder data and ground-truth techniques

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Coastal tidal zones are among the environments arousing major global interest in both socioeconomic and cultural–natural terms. The evolution of these environments is complex, influenced by natural and anthropogenic factors. These systems evolve in response to complex hydrodynamic interactions, including tidal asymmetry, sedimentation, and channel morphodynamics. Tidal channels are a common feature in tidal environments. Yet their spatial and temporal evolution remain largely unexplored, especially regarding the morphological and sedimentological characteristics of the seafloor and their changes over time. Information on their evolution is particularly relevant in highly populated areas where natural processes are strongly intertwined with anthropogenic pressures. This is the case of the Venice Lagoon, where tidal channels are responsible for the water, nutrients and biota transport and exchange.

Using high-resolution MultiBeam Echo-Sounder (MBES) and ground-truth data, we investigated the tidal channels' seafloor and their spatiotemporal evolution in the northern part of the Venice Lagoon. Bathymetry and backscatter data were acquired in 2013 and 2021 in the same area. Sediment samples and video footage of the seabed were collected to describe the substrate and validate the maps produced with the MBES acoustic data. Morphological features were characterized in GIS environment from the bathymetric data. We identified both erosional and depositional features, with the latter comprising the majority of the study area. Seafloor sediment map was created by classifying backscatter data using the unsupervised Jenks Natural Breaks classification. To assess changes over an eight-year period, we compared data obtained in 2013 with information gathered in 2021. Our findings suggest that deposition processes predominantly influence the study area with an overall net sediment accumulation of $542.7 \cdot 10^3 \text{ m}^3$, which was strongly influenced by anthropogenic activity, related to the recent start of functioning of the mobile barriers at the lagoon inlet and the anthropogenic restoration of salt marshes in the area.

The integration of MBES surveys and ground truth data using a GIS methodology has proven to be a successful approach for monitoring an exceptionally dynamic area. This work establishes a consistent, repeatable, site-specific workflow applicable to other seabed mapping studies and future monitoring datasets. In the context of mean sea level rise and the consequent adaptation measures, this work can contribute not only to broadening the knowledge of highly valuable and vulnerable transitional environments, but they can help to assess the impact of such anthropogenic adaptation measures over time.

A large-scale deep learning approach for visual ecological assessment of cold-water coral reefs based on ROV video data

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Exploration, mapping and monitoring of cold-water coral reef habitats is supported by various technologies. Great technical achievements have been continuously reported for fine-scale visual mapping and 2D-, 2.5D- and 3D-reconstruction of single reefs. However, the standard approach to collect coral data is to explore a wider area utilizing cameras attached to a ROV. Due to various environmental conditions e.g. particles and organism in the water, various current regimes and height of the reefs, the quality of the videos normally varies in visibility and with distance to objects of interest. Further, these types of surveys, covering hundreds of m², generates large video volumes. Currently, these videos are evaluated and interpreted by human operators. This process can be tiresome, expensive, and error-prone. We have developed a computer vision approach to automatically classify and segment four different classes relevant to the ecological status of cold-water coral reefs: *Desmophyllum pertusum*, *Paragorgia arborea*, other gorgonians and sponges. The segformer algorithm, based on the transformer architecture, is used for semantic segmentation of corals and sponges. To create training data, an expert annotated one frame for 171 out of a total of 255 videos, annotating all instances of the aforementioned classes. The system was applied to 255 videos collected during 5 dedicated coral surveys in the Haltenbanken area (Norwegian Sea) area. One frame per second was extracted and segmented. Based on the computed data, we estimated the reef status and compared the results with assessments from human observers who visually inspected the videos following a defined protocol. The study demonstrates that the results of the computational approach are comparable to the “traditional” manual approach performed by human users, but offers the added benefits of reproducibility, transparency (due to single frame segmentations) and a more fine-grained resolution of results. Additionally, a new visualization front-end has been developed to facilitate quick exploration of the computational results, following the visualization mantra of “overview first, zoom-in and filter, details on demand”.

The results offer a foundation for enhancing the quality and reproducibility of cold-water coral reef monitoring by efficiently evaluating more videos from a greater number of surveys, and by being more flexible in the sharing and interpretation of results.

What do we need to know to boost South Atlantic Ocean seafloor mapping?

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Mapping the seafloor is an essential target to meet the stipulated outcomes of the Ocean Decade and will only be achieved through a great deal of effort by various actors and factors. Today, only 24,9% of the seafloor is mapped at a sufficient resolution to perform environmental analysis; this diminishes when the South Atlantic comes into play. To understand the needs and challenges in the South Atlantic mapping scenario, we proposed a questionnaire addressed to marine data-related people to seek their perceived importance (from 1 = no contribution to 5 = maximum contribution) about the contribution of stakeholders to the proposed priority actions, and the contribution of these actions to the defined outcome/targets towards enhancing South Atlantic Ocean seabed mapping in a near future.

The quest captured a sample size of 120 complete responses from University Professors/Researchers (53 responses), Student–undergraduate and Graduate (34 responses), Government or Private Research Institutes (22 responses), and Business/Industry employees (12 responses). The answers show that the Ocean Science Community Policy Makers and State Institutions were perceived to be more important to most of the actions. A Sankey diagram analysis shows that the Ocean Science Community together with Civil Society and NGOs understand to be more important to Disseminate the Importance of Mapping, while the Business and Industry considered to be more important to Establish Multilateral Partnership, and the Policy Makers were perceived to be more important on Investment in Education and Technology. None of the stakeholders were supportive to be particularly important to Scientific Technology and Advances and Data Sharing, meanwhile, these actions were perceived to be more important to building Seabed Models and gathering a Digital Atlas of the Ocean, respectively. Investment in Education and Technology was understood to be more important to Assist the Decision-Making process as well as to stimulate Ocean Literacy. Establish Multilateral Partnerships, Human resources training, and Disseminate the importance of Mapping were not shown as more important in one goal than the other.

Understanding the perception of marine data-related people about the expected role of each stakeholder in diminishing the gap of mapping the South Atlantic, as well as knowing which actions will be more important to achieve the targets towards enhancing the seabed map would boost the science outreach and public engagement efforts towards seabed mapping in the South Atlantic Ocean.

On the way to the most mapped continental shelf in Brazil: a geomorphological habitat mapping initiative

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The Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021–2030) has set the goal of having the ocean floor fully measured and mapped by 2030 on a high-resolution scale. However, this achievement is particularly challenging for the South Atlantic Ocean. In an effort to increase the knowledge on the Espírito Santo State continental shelf (ESCS), we currently have an area of 2000 km² mapped with multispectral MBES and almost 600 videos from drop-cameras and dives. Now the challenge lies on how to integrate the products transforming them into productive information for scientists but also for managers and decision-makers leading the process of the ongoing construction of the Brazilian Marine Spatial Planning. So far, the mapped area ranges from 10 to 450m depth and comprises a complex geomorphology area.

The Rio Doce area is characterized by a muddy habitat concentrated up to 30 m deep and is then interspersed with sandy bars that have a linear direction to the coastline present up to 40 m deep. Further than that, there are the presence of rhodolith beds, associated with fleshy macroalgae and carbonate fragments, and consolidated bottom with bioencrustation forming mesophotic reefs in the most distal portion, potentially formed by aggregate of rhodoliths.

The Costa das Algas portion is an heterogeneous area encompassing bedforms that intercalates sand and mud, presence of laterite, in addition to rhodolith beds. Geomorphologically, the area features incised valleys up to its middle portion (<40m) where there is a predominance of rhodolith beds generally associated with other forms of coralline algae. On the edges of the channels as well as in the more distal offshore portions there is the presence of mesophotic reefs potentially composed by aggregation of rhodoliths.

Although rhodolith beds are present in both areas, they differ in terms of algae coverage on the surface and in the transition area there is a limit observed in the rhodolith bed patterns where the rhodoliths usually associated with other calcareous algae forms (Costa das Algas) transits to rhodoliths bed only with nodular form (Rio Doce).

The road ahead for seabed mapping, both in Brazil and for the South Atlantic, will require a lot of science, effort and partnerships, to reach a level of habitat mapping that would change paradigms, impact the use of knowledge in various sectors (academia, government, private companies) and drives us forward a future sustainable marine society.

An easy implementation of the Random Forest technique for predicting habitats

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The prediction of marine habitats and environments, relies on the technique of characterising an area where actual observational data, such as photographs or sediment samples, is available. These point data can then be combined with data that has areal coverage, such as bathymetry and its many derivatives, backscatter, and possibly other oceanographic variables including bottom temperature, salinity and current strength and direction. The Random Forest (RF) methodology has been available for several years but often considered as difficult to implement and use, and therefore only used, if at all, by more expert users, and considered as a high-end product. Having an easy implementation of the RF technique should allow more time for further development of data analysis beyond random forest output.

Showcased and made available here are plugins for QGIS. New tools, with a user-friendly Graphical User Interfaces within the geographic information system, allow users to manipulate their data easily and use the RF functionality of R without having to change software systems. The RF software uses software within the statistical package R but this is not seen by the user. The linkage with R software libraries from QGIS can be inspected and may help other software developers. The software is all open-source and thus can be copied and edited to make new tools.

In addition to Random Forest predictions are other useful interpretational techniques in QGIS include Benthic Terrain Modeler (BTM), bathymetry morphometry, segmentation and Object Based Image Analysis (OBIA). Some useful marine survey tools are also provided, such as; a tracklines designer for surveys, prediction of swath coverage over low resolution data, and outlier and null data manipulation.

Examples will be shown of predicted habitats in the British Virgin Islands, using a variety of data sources that include bathymetry from a variety of sources, satellite imagery, and oceanographic model data for temperature and salinity. Groundtruth data was also collated from various sources but include over 200 mini-ROV dive video data.

Towards a GeoHab Backscatter Working Group Roadmap: Community Identification of Research Priorities

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Acoustic backscatter is an indispensable tool for marine habitat mapping. Almost a decade after the GeoHab Backscatter Working Group (BSWG) published its guidelines and recommendations report, new technologies, challenges, and questions have emerged. Given the range of potential backscatter research avenues, it can be difficult to align research programs with the priorities of the community of practice. Prioritization of backscatter research topics is thus necessary to establish a roadmap for BSWG research efforts.

We asked the international community working with acoustic backscatter to submit priority questions in backscatter research with a 5- to 10-year horizon. We analyzed and curated a total of 177 research questions from 73 contributors, and the resulting 104 questions were grouped into eight broad recurring themes: “Technologies”, “Calibration”, “Data acquisition and ground-truthing”, “Data processing”, “Post-processing, quality control, data handling, and curation”, “Data analysis”, “Data interpretation”, and “Applications and end uses”.

A follow-up survey based on the final list of questions was distributed to characterize the community working with backscatter and to identify key research priorities. More than 120 respondents from 23 countries participated, ranking priority backscatter research questions within each theme. Most were researchers (54%), while others were technicians (20%) or program managers (9%). Affiliations included academia (41%), governmental agencies (37%), and industry/private sector (19%).

After scaling the responses, the most commonly selected theme was “Post-processing, quality control, data handling, and curation”, followed by “Data analysis” and “Calibration”. Respondents consistently ranked several research questions as priorities. The two questions that were identified as priorities by over 25% of respondents were “How can we move towards absolute calibration of different systems to allow interregional comparisons?”, and “How can we quantify seafloor backscatter quality and develop standards similar to what exists with bathymetry?”. Additionally, over 22% of respondents indicated the importance of the question

“How can the data acquisition settings of multifrequency sonar systems be optimised to collect multifrequency backscatter data for habitat and seabed substrate mapping, while still performing at the highest standard for the collection of bathymetric data, for example for hydrographic surveys?”.

All eight themes are represented in the top 10 priority questions, underscoring the need for contributions to backscatter research from multiple perspectives to advance the field. The ranking of priority questions encourages collaboration within the community and will serve as a roadmap for backscatter research programs over the next decade.

A technology for extracting and compensating acoustic backscattering strength from multibeam data

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The Multibeam Echosounder System (MBES) serves as a crucial tool, providing not only seafloor water depth but also sound wave intensity reflected after absorption and scattering on the seafloor. This information holds paramount importance for underwater mapping and exploration. The intensity of backscattered sound pressure is influenced by both multibeam echosounder equipment characteristics and the marine environment where sound waves propagate. Backscatter data undergoes compensation processes, encompassing TVG (Time Varying Gain), Source Level, Beam Pattern, Transmission Loss, and Insonified Area. This study aims to extract raw sound pressure intensity by eliminating compensation values applied to the raw data using model estimates based on input marine environmental factors. Additionally, the study involves generating standardized sound intensity through a compensation process that considers on-site marine environmental factors. Therefore, various analyses suitable for local marine environments have become feasible by extracting backscatter data with removed corrections and applying compensation processes.

Realtime backscatter normalization with EM2042.

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Backscatter strength (BS) values produced by the EM multibeam are corrected for transmit and receiver directivity, insonified area, and other effects to produce high-quality BS by default. However, it may still be desirable to even out residual differences between systems, modes and/or sectors by performing backscatter normalization or calibration. For the EM2040 product group, KD offer a service where we create a BS correction file from a set of lines covering all modes, in addition to software that applies these corrections in post-processing.

For EM2042 an improved BS correction method is developed. The new method speeds up the data collection process and the corrections can be applied in real time. In this talk we describe the new method in detail, explain how it works, how to use it, and show examples from the field.

A key component is a new backscatter calibration mode that utilize MultiFrequency mode to gather reference data for all modes on a single line. A sufficient dataset can therefore be collected in as little as two lines, although more may be desired for robustness. The method also includes a new file format for the backscatter corrections. Both the file and applied corrections are included in the kmall file. The new method will also be supported by the EM2040 product group.

Drone-based high-resolution hyperspectral mapping and monitoring of the seafloor – a study across tides

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Hyperspectral imaging, or imaging spectroscopy, has been thoroughly investigated for ocean color remote sensing. The technique measures a spectrum of radiance per pixel, and the signal has a well-understood dependency on the water column composition, the water depth, and the bottom types within the pixel (if the water is shallow). Most hyperspectral mapping has been carried out from manned aircrafts with footprints typically ranging from meters to tens of meters. With the development of unoccupied aerial systems and payloads, new opportunities arise in terms of hyperspectral mapping and monitoring. Drone-based hyperspectral imaging enables imagery with resolution at the deci-centimeter scale, more frequent revisitation, and simpler correction for atmospheric effects due to the low altitude. However, higher spatial resolution brings new challenges, such as stricter requirements for georeferencing of image data and ground truth data.

In the first part of the presentation, we address the challenge when the drone's direct georeferencing accuracy for push broom hyperspectral images is inadequate for the desired resolution. In the presence of high accuracy reference points, this motivates a flexible co-registration method tailored to scanline imagery. In our proposed method we generate thousands of reference points by automatically matching the directly georeferenced hyperspectral images against an accurately georeferenced orthomosaic, made from Red-Green-Blue (RGB) images. We attribute the georeferencing errors to slowly varying position/orientation errors in the drone's navigation system. Co-registration of the data is done by estimating the navigation error time series that minimize georeferencing error. In our case the RGB orthomosaic was considered perfectly georeferenced and was used in conjunction with on-ground observations to annotate the bottom types. In the second part of the presentation, we show the results of a seafloor mapping of a coastal zone at Remøy, Norway. We demonstrate 10 cm resolution hyperspectral mapping of the seafloor using semi-analytical inversion to retrieve water depths, bottom types, and water column constituents on a per-pixel basis. The same area was mapped at low, mid, and high tide, and the co-registration allowing us to effectively compare retrieved bathymetry and bottom types across tide. As such, the study represents a demonstration of a hyperspectral, high-spatial resolution monitoring concept in the shallow-water domain. Derived bathymetry is validated against airborne bathymetric LIDAR while bottom types are validated against on-ground observations.

Enhancing habitat mapping in polar environments through Hyperspectral Imaging: Studying the interconnected dynamics of seaice and seafloor habitats.

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Understanding the biophysical dynamics of polar environments, including under ice and seafloor habitats in Antarctica, poses significant challenges due to both physical access and habitat complexity. This presentation explores hyperspectral imaging as a means of adapting a technology for precise habitat mapping to understand these unique habitats.

In the context of sea ice research, traditional sampling methods struggle to capture the high spatio-temporal variability of small-scale processes, hindering our ability to model and predict sea ice primary productivity and ecological functions. Hyperspectral imaging, with its high spatial and spectral resolution, revolutionizes the monitoring of biophysical processes in sea ice. This method acquires data both ex-situ and in-situ, providing detailed insights into sea ice productivity, ice algal ecological interactions, and biogeochemical model parametrizations. Computational algorithms permit the quantification of these processes, offering a fundamental improvement in understanding sea ice dynamics. This work outlines potential applications and research prospects for imaging spectroscopy in the context of sea ice biophysical research.

On the Antarctic seafloor, cumulative impacts on benthic habitats necessitate advanced techniques for identification and monitoring of key species. Hyperspectral imaging provides valuable insights into the physico-structural and photo-physiological traits of habitat-forming organisms which increase biodiversity and ecosystem processes. When combined with Structure from Motion (SfM) or acoustic mapping techniques these surveys demonstrate their integral value to understand how sea ice influences ecosystems and how changes in sea ice will influence ecosystem baselines. This presentation will illustrate the results of a 2023 Cape Evans Antarctic field campaign which was a world first hyperspectral survey of the seafloor in Antarctica.

Hyperspectral imaging is emerging as a robust tool for scientific mapping of both benthic and under-ice habitats. This advanced technology contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of critical ecosystems in Antarctica, providing a scientific basis for effective conservation and management strategies. The application of hyperspectral imaging offers a rigorous and multidimensional approach to study the interconnected dynamics of sea ice and seafloor habitats in Antarctica.

Drivers shaping the deep-sea benthic community composition of the Norwegian and Barents Sea

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Understanding the environmental and biotic conditions that drive the distribution of species and communities is fundamental for identifying vulnerable areas and developing protection plans, but this is especially challenging in the deep-sea benthos. This is because many deep-sea benthic species are rare or sparsely distributed, and data collection is costly. Therefore, modelling techniques that aim to maximize the amount of information extracted from the available data have high potential moving forward. We used Hierarchical Modelling of Species Communities (HMSC), a Bayesian joint species distribution modelling approach which simultaneously uses information on environmental variables, species traits and study design, while also considering spatial dependency and latent (i.e. unknown) variables, to estimate environmental niches, species associations and community assembly processes. By considering community level patterns in addition, information is shared across species, which has been shown to be beneficial when modelling data-poor species.

We were able to explain on average 37% of the spatial variation in the 293 species we modelled, and we were also able to link 10% of this variation to the species traits we included. Temperature was the predictor variable that accounted for the largest proportion of variation, a strong indication that climate change will affect many deep-sea benthic species. Also, we detected three spatially structured latent variables which together accounted for around 33% of the explained variation. Based on their distribution, the latent variables could be related to variation in topography or fishing intensity, variables for which obtaining accurate data tends to be challenging. Our results provide a comprehensive understanding of the deep-sea benthic community of the region, which is essential to develop ecosystem-based management.

Habitat and biotope mapping in the Southern Baltic Sea: The German approach

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In close cooperation with the geological and biological department, we were able to produce full-coverage maps of broad and other benthic habitat types (BHT and OHT according to the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive) as well as biotope types according to the HELCOM underwater biotope and habitat classification (HUB) for the entire German Baltic Sea. Using hydroacoustic recordings and benthological surveys (bottom grabs, underwater towing camera systems and diver sampling), maps with a high spatial resolution of 1 x 1 km were produced, in selected areas even up to 50 x 50 m. A total of over 7000 data points (stations and transect sections) were generated and acquired for the period 2010 - 2021 and incorporated into predictive biotope modelling. Combining the national guidelines, which enable a standardised delineation of habitats, with benthic community modelling allowed us to create maps with a level of spatial detail that was previously unavailable for the Baltic Sea. The maps serve as a basis for future monitoring, status assessments, and protection and management measures. The presentation will illustrate the process of habitat and biotope mapping in German marine waters and present the latest results.

Sediments and bedforms mapping of the Lower Saxony Wadden Sea and North Sea (Germany)

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The implementation of HD 1992/43/EEC, WFD 2000/60/EC and MSFD 2008/56/EC Directives makes governmental agencies start seabed-mapping programs and strongly encourages research institutes looking for new technologies, tools and mapping methods. Within this context, the Coastal Research Station of NLWKN is carrying out a long-term program to map subtidal areas of the Lower Saxony coastal and marine waters, adopting a methodological approach aimed to increase objectivity and repeatability of results.

Even though existing maps provide a good broad-scaled representation of sediments distribution, they were interpolated from grab-samples data, so lacking of resolution and tending to under-represent the hard-substrates. The ongoing mapping program provides full-coverage detailed maps of sediments and bedforms, by means of swath-bathymetrical systems, subbottom profiler and validation samples. The methodological approach integrates bathymetric, backscatter and stratigraphic information to characterize bedforms and substrates.

Resulting maps outline common sedimentological and geomorphological feature across all the observed Wadden Sea tidal inlets, which are made of fine sandy sediments and narrow outcrops of peat layers on the main tidal channels slopes. Both erosive and depositional geomorphological processes are present, represented by several orders of scarps, mainly connected to alternations of hard-substrates and unconsolidated sands, and medium to very large sand-waves. In the North Sea area, new detailed data about hard-substrates outcrops have been collected and mapped. Shore-connected very large structures and different orders of sand-waves reveal intense active geomorphological processes, triggered by a complex combination of waves and tidal currents, resulting in huge sediment mobilization.

In conclusion, the mapping programs provides new detailed geological-geomorphological information of a very dynamic coastal area, using repeatable and objective methods. The combination of different datasets and tools allows the quantitative analyse of the complex subtidal morphology, the correlation of bedforms and substrates, the characterization of abiotic features. Resulting products will be further developed for habitat mapping purposes and morphological and hydro-dynamical modelling.

Improved benthic geologic mapping combining acoustic backscatter and visual observations with object-based and machine-learning techniques

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In the absence of any direct observations, benthic geomorphology serves as a direct indicator of benthic geologic processes. High-resolution acoustic mapping can reveal fine-scale geomorphological details, however quantitative, objective, and repeatable methods are essential to translate large amounts of acoustic data into usable information. We present a geologic mapping study on the Upper Columbia River, a large, dynamic river in the northwestern USA, which combines multibeam sonar data with photographic observations of the riverbed to produce high-resolution geologic maps illustrating fine-scale benthic geologic characteristics including sediment grain size, texture, and geomorphology. The multibeam sonar data set included a centimeter-scale bathymetry digital terrain model and a normalized acoustic backscatter mosaic for nearly 65 kilometers of the river. Within the coverage area of the multibeam data, approximately 700 underwater photographs were acquired. The bathymetry and backscatter were spectrally enhanced to highlight variations in riverbed geometry, roughness, and texture, and then digitally partitioned into homogenous segments using object-based image analysis (OBIA) techniques. OBIA techniques were also used to quantitatively analyze the underwater photographs and determine the sediment composition (mud, sand, gravel, cobble, boulder, bedrock) of the area shown in each photograph. A machine-learning algorithm was used to correlate acoustic signatures with sediment compositions and then extrapolate the resulting relationships to produce benthic geologic maps. The resulting maps depict the complete spatial distribution and abundance of sediment compositions for approximately 65 kilometers of the river with a minimum mapping unit of 1 meter. Accuracy assessments with independent testing data indicate an overall map accuracy of approximately 81%. To our knowledge, this the first study of its kind to map sediment composition in a large, dynamic riverine setting with a relatively high degree of accuracy. The methods described here are immediately applicable to other studies for which detailed benthic geologic and/or habitat characterization is required.

EMODNET SEABED HABITATS – DELIVERING A HABITAT MAP FOR THE CASPIAN BASIN

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The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) is a network of organisations supported by the EU's integrated maritime policy. These organisations work together to observe the sea, process the data according to international standards and make that information freely available as interoperable data layers and data products with the overarching aim of facilitating blue growth.

Phase 4 of EMODnet Seabed Habitats (ESH) concluded in September 2023. The geographical scope of this phase was expanded to include complete coverage of jurisdictional waters of EU Member States in the Caribbean Sea, and the Caspian Sea. Deliverables from this phase included a broad-scale seabed habitat map for Europe, the Caribbean and the Caspian Sea (EUSeaMap 2023), which was released in early October 2023.

EUSeaMap provides full coverage of the broad benthic habitat types for the first time in the Caspian Sea. This required collation and aggregation of existing environmental layers, and development of new ones where necessary. Benthic data were identified, collated and used to establish threshold values for classifying the environmental layers into ecologically relevant classes for the determination of habitat types. The seabed substrate layer for the Caspian from EMODnet Geology, combined with the GEBCO DTM (500m resolution) and other environmental layers, informed the broad-scale seabed habitat map in this region.

EUSeaMap describes habitats according to European classifications (EUNIS and MSFD broad habitat types) and regional classifications. No existing classification was identified in literature for the Caspian Sea, requiring the definition of a specific habitat list. The broad habitat types classification developed includes infralittoral, circalittoral, offshore circalittoral, bathyal and abyssal biological zones. Seabed substrate types include rock, sand, mud, coarse substrate and mixed sediment. Two mussel species were identified as biogenic substrate builders: *Mytilaster lineatus*, (infralittoral), and *Dreissena grimmi*, (circalittoral). A seabed PAR threshold was used for the separation between infralittoral and circalittoral zones. The boundaries between the circalittoral/bathyal and the bathyal/abyssal, defined by changes in slope, were delineated using a semi-automatic approach. The circalittoral and the offshore circalittoral were separated using a depth threshold. EUSeaMap will facilitate policy makers and researchers, and can be used to inform effect monitoring of climate change on the ecosystem and biodiversity of the Caspian Sea.

All deliverables are freely available via the EMODnet Central Portal which provides a standardised, centralised and free access point for all spatial information on seabed habitats in Europe: <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en>.

Exploring multispectral backscatter datasets on reefs

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Reefs are conspicuous seafloor features that are relatively easy to identify from their morphology using multibeam bathymetric survey methods. In contrast to using bathymetry, there has been limited investigation of how multibeam backscatter can be used to characterize reef habitat, and whether biological attributes of reef systems (e.g. density and cover of epibiota) can be measured based on their backscattering records as a function of survey frequency. Our study employed multibeam multispectral backscatter (170, 280 and 400 kHz, using an R2 Sonic 2024) data collected in different regions of the Abrolhos shelf (Brazil). Backscatter angular response curves were extract over reef features to investigate the acoustic response according to the frequency.

The lower frequencies (170 and 280 kHz) showed similar curves in shape and values, with a great decrease in backscatter strength at 20° near nadir region, and increased backscatter values at the outer regions of the swath. For the highest frequency (400 kHz), the values near nadir were lower when compared to the other frequencies, and the shape of the curve was closer to that of models indicating gravel or sand – unlike the increasing values observed at the outer regions for the lower frequencies. Further investigations are ongoing (including the integrated analysis of RGB mosaics and multispectral geomorphometry), but potential reasons for the observed differences could include the influence of reef morphology on the acoustic response, the algal cover over the reefs, and even the difficulty of plotting the curve accurately positioned over the reef feature - which may end up influencing result due to the inter reef sediment.

The results from this investigation highlight the variability and complexities in backscatter response by frequency across different benthic environments and lend support for a global repository (e.g. an electronic catalogue or backscatter signature dictionary) of backscatter examples across different benthic environments to aid seafloor classification. Such an initiative has been discussed by the GeoHab Backscatter Working Group (BSWG). The table built with the results presented in this abstract includes a brief description of the bottom type/feature, angular response curves, mosaic, and metadata (such as equipment, software, calibration, local, depth). This novel multispectral data on reefs can be useful to describe these features, as well as provide information to compare reef data and establish acoustic properties at different frequencies. We use the examples from our study to demonstrate how an E-catalogue could be compiled through a future international collaborative initiative.

Habitat mapping as a management tool for the projected exploitation activities in the IOM's license area in the Clarion-Clipperton Zone, the Pacific Ocean

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Interoceanmetal Joint Organization (IOM) is an international organization holding an exploration license granted by the International Seabed Authority (ISA). IOM is one of 16 contractors conducting environmental baseline studies in the Clarion-Clipperton Zone (CCZ). Data collected by individual contractors and independent research institutes has made it possible to describe the regional features of CCZ.

Regional models of nodule abundance and habitat distribution across CCZ form a basis for the Environmental Management Plan for CCZ. CCZ is divided into two main domains: (1) license areas where exploration activities are taking place, and (2) areas of particular environmental interest (APEIs), which are no-mining zones free from any impact that may arise from exploitation activities. This regional level of environmental management is supplemented by contract zone-specific area-based management tools, namely Preservation Reference Zones (PRZs) and Impact Reference Zones (IRZs), which are to be delineated in each license zone in order to monitor the effects of exploitation activities on ecosystems. A PRZ is an area where no mining and no effects of mining may occur, while a IRZ is to be designated within the seabed area actually mined; both zones have to be “as ecologically similar as possible”.

ISA is currently working on a set of regulations which will define design criteria for PRZs and IRZs. The most recent version stipulates that ‘[t]o designate representative IRZs/PRZs requires characterisation of the pelagic and benthic environment including all sub-habitats that may be impacted by mining operations, and determination of regional distributions and patterns of connectivity of communities.’ In practice, all the habitats which are to be impacted by mining activities (direct and indirect) in the license area must be adequately (also in terms of their size) represented within a PRZ and must allow connectivity between identified communities (forming ecological corridors and/or stepping stones). The first criterion (representativity of habitats) is to be met within the claim area, whereas the latter one seems to require cooperation between neighbouring contractors in order to ensure connectivity between communities across the areas where they occur.

IOM's PRZ was delineated in 2017 taking into account the guidelines applicable at that time. Its location must now be reassessed against the recently defined criteria. This will involve the habitat mapping exercise using detailed bathymetry, Particulate Organic Carbon (POC) and nitrogen fluxes, nodule abundance, and (key) species and communities distribution in areas where respective data is available.

BenthicNet: A global dataset of benthic habitat imagery to support development of large image recognition models

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Our ability to collect benthic habitat imagery has surpassed our capacity to analyze it. Images of seafloor geology and biology are the most common form of ground truth data used to produce benthic habitat maps, yet analysing these images is the most labour-intensive component of many habitat mapping workflows. Technologies that enable partial automation of benthic image processing tasks are becoming increasingly necessary to scale benthic habitat mapping efforts to regional or global extents. Image recognition models – particularly deep learning approaches – are the current tools of choice for achieving such automation, yet development of these models is made difficult by the lack of large and consistent benthic image datasets on which they may be trained.

Here we present BenthicNet: a compiled dataset of benthic habitat imagery curated to support the training and evaluation of large image recognition models. Over 11 million benthic images were collected from sources around the world to represent a diversity of global habitats from the tropics to the poles. Nearly 200,000 of these images were accompanied by a total of 2.6 million labels, which were translated to the CATAMI classification scheme. The remaining unlabelled images were sub-sampled spatially to yield a subset of 1.1 million images that adequately represent the global diversity of benthic environments sampled at a manageable data volume. The datasets and labels are made openly available to foster the development of benthic habitat image recognition models.

Preliminary trials have suggested the utility of this dataset for training large deep learning models that may be utilized for a variety of specific image processing tasks. A large self-supervised model was trained using the full (1.3M) image dataset, which may be repurposed for benthic image classification via transfer learning. Transfer learning trials suggested that this model performs comparably to other large publicly accessible models for tasks where large numbers of labelled images are available for transfer learning (e.g., >70k). Where only smaller labelled datasets are available (e.g., on the order of 1k images), our trials suggest that the BenthicNet model may greatly outperform other established models for transfer learning applications. Along with the datasets, this model is made openly available to the benthic habitat mapping community through established repositories and free image processing software packages.

Reducing uncertainty in seafloor fluid vent localization

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Modern water-column-imaging multibeam sonars have been shown to be effective tools for a variety of ocean mapping applications but generate immense amounts of raw data when recording acoustic backscatter over the entire water column. High data acquisition rates can pose logistic, economic, and technical challenges for rapid processing, analysis, and archiving of these data. These limitations in multibeam water column imaging often provide unique challenges in commercial marine seep hunting surveys that routinely acquire large basin-scale high-resolution multibeam datasets that require rapid processing and interpretation required for selection of coring targets for geochemical sampling of seep sediments. Interpreting the seafloor position of gas emissions in multibeam water column data using common commercial software packages is hindered by slow processing due to these large file sizes, a manual “by eye” qualitative assessment of each sonar ping searching for acoustic anomalies, skill and experience of the interpreter, fatigue of the interpreter during field operations, and environmental or acquisition artifacts that can mask the location of gas emission on the seafloor. These restrictions over regional basin-scale surveys create a qualitative data set with varying inherent positional errors that can lead to missed or incorrect observations about seep-related seafloor features and processes. By vertically integrating midwater multibeam amplitude samples over a desired range of depths, a 2D integrated midwater backscatter raster can be generated and draped over bathymetric data, providing a quantitative synoptic overview of the spatial distribution of gas plume emission sites for enhanced seafloor interpretation. We reprocess a multibeam midwater data set from NOAA Cruise EX1402L2 in the northwestern Gulf of Mexico using a vertical amplitude stacking technique. Constructed midwater backscatter surfaces are compared with digitized plume positions interpreted during EX1402L2 for a comparison into assessing uncertainty in mapping approaches. Our results show that the accuracy of manually digitizing gas emission sites varies considerably when compared with the midwater backscatter amplitude maps. This quantitative plume mapping technique offers multiple advantages over traditional geopicking from cost effectiveness, offshore efficiency, mapping repeatability, and ultimately improving the detectability of gas plume emission on the seafloor. This study shows datasets generated from this method can reliably be used as a geophysical proxy for locating chemosynthetic and related benthic habitats.

Enhancing the dynamic representation of uncertainty in seabed habitats on the temperate Australian continental shelf using a Bayesian Multinomial GLM and Seamap Australia

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The temperate ecosystems of southern Australia's continental shelf, cover more than 7 million hectares and contribute significant social and economic benefits to the Australian community. These waters support important fisheries, and expansive marine conservation areas, and share the seascape with offshore oil and gas activities, and the growing renewable energy sectors. Users of this marine space need to understand the distribution of habitats, species and associated ecological communities throughout these ecosystems and the processes that support their connectivity, productivity and function.

Historically, attempts to map these ecosystems have primarily focused on nearshore environments within coastal waters (< 3 nm from the coastline). In line with global practices, these mapping efforts have relied on ground-truthed classification models based on marine imagery and multibeam sonar or remote sensing imagery. Attempts to communicate the accuracy of these maps have largely relied on the use of error matrices. Although such approaches offer insights into the accuracy of the overall map, they require modellers to apply thresholds (be that automatically or based on a user-chosen value) to the prediction to convert probability values into delineated individual habitat classes. However, these thresholds impose limitations on the versatility of the produced products, as users may seek to be either more or less certain when considering predicted habitats. Moreover, this traditional method of accuracy assessment cannot quantify the spatial variability in the uncertainty associated with these predictions.

Through a collaboration between Traditional Owners from the Karri Karrak Aboriginal Corporation and Undalup Association on Wadandi Country and researchers from the Australian Government through the National Environmental Science Programs' Marine and Coastal Hub we set out to create a dynamic and intuitive map of seabed habitats. Here, we introduce a novel approach to communicate the uncertainty in predicted seabed habitats on the temperate Australian continental shelf using Bayesian multinomial Generalised Linear Models. Additionally, we demonstrate through Seamap Australia (<https://seamapaustralia.org/>), a national platform, how the maps change if end users adjust their tolerance for prediction certainty to meet the needs of specific use cases. By removing the requirement of thresholds in the maps, our approach empowers end users to make informed decisions, enhancing the flexibility and applicability of the generated maps. This innovative method provides a valuable tool for management, marine planners and park managers, contributing to more informed decision-making in the management of Sea Country.

Metrology of the seafloor acoustic response: recommendations on how to derive backscatter curves

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Seafloor acoustic response has become the key parameter for many if not most marine surveying communities. Its measurements have been widely extended in hydrography using predominantly bathymetric echosounders, and it is used in diverse applications such as habitat mapping, seabed characterisation or classification. Numerous theoretical models have also been developed in the last decades to study its link with physical or heuristic bottom parameters. While analysing how these three domains deal with the seafloor acoustic response, it appeared that the nature itself of the seafloor acoustic response is equivocal. The work presented here proposes a relationship between the three uses of the seafloor acoustic response. A metrological method is established, connecting seafloor response measurements, applications and theory. In particular, the deterministic backscatter parameters derived theoretically are usefully linked to the stochastic nature of backscatter measurements observed in practice.

This result yields a method to accurately derive backscatter values from bathymetric echosounder data: the best choice of backscatter estimator is justified based on analytical calculations, and ways to represent its uncertainties are proposed. Hypotheses and limits of the method are discussed. Finally, some recommendations are given on how to exploit these results in practice.

Seafloor macrolitter mapping and removal by an innovative robotic solution in the Venice Coastal Area

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Plastic pollution in the aquatic environment is now recognized as a problem of critical concern, involving the whole world and affecting both marine and freshwater ecosystems. It is expected that most of ML are localized in the seafloor. Therefore, it is crucial to prevent and reduce the quantity of litter that reaches the sea, at the same time there is an urgent need of cutting-edge solutions to monitor and remove marine litter already in the environment. Within the EU co-founded H2020 Smart technology for Marine Litter SusTainable RemOval and Management (MAELSTROM) project, an innovative robotic system, i.e. a floating platform combined with an underwater cable-driven robot was developed to remove macrolitter items from the seafloor in a selective and eco-sustainable way. The target of the robotic solution was an abandoned mussel farm in the Venice coastal area. Although the mussel farm was decommissioned some years ago, all the materials used for mussel harvesting in the sea were left in the environment by the owner. To investigate the level of pollution of the area, repeated multibeam surveys associated with video inspections for ground truthing were carried out to map the presence of macro litter on the seabed and in the water column.

In June 2023, the robotic seabed cleaning platform was successfully tested for the first time in the removal of fishing and farming derived litter. During test, the robotic solution, using a gripping device, using the high resolution multibeam seafloor and water column maps as reference, removed 260 kg of ropes made of polyamide 6 (nylon 6) material and floating buoys in an efficient and selective way.

In this research, we demonstrate the efficacy of high-resolution mapping and classification in optimizing the functionality of a cutting-edge robotic system designed for removing litter from the marine seafloor. Additionally, we present initial findings from cleaning operations, utilizing data comparisons before and after cleanup to assess the effectiveness of the removal technology.

Benthic ecological mapping of scallop buffer zones marine refuges in the southern Gulf of St. Lawrence

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Implementing effective marine conservation and developing marine monitoring strategies as part of the ongoing management of existing conservation areas requires a good spatial understanding of marine ecosystems. However, there are still major gaps remaining in our understanding of the multi-dimensional spatial patterns and processes in the ocean, especially in benthic ecosystems. This study adopts a seascape ecological approach to collect data sets to facilitate mapping scallop buffer zone marine refuges and other coastal areas within the southern Gulf of St Lawrence to address some of these knowledge gaps. These areas have been designated to protect potential juvenile lobster habitat from the impacts of scallop dredging in the region, and this research aims to generate detailed habitat maps of these protected areas for the first time.

Bathymetric and backscatter multibeam survey data, collected over a 30 year period, were compiled and merged to cover the extent of the survey area at a 10m resolution. Ground truthing was conducted using a 4k drop camera system, collecting 8 minutes of video at 51 ground truthing locations. The video data was reviewed to identify and georeference the locations of species of interest, included lobster (*Homarus americanus*), scallop (*Placopecten magellanicus*) and rock crab (*Cancer irroratus*). Bathymetric and backscatter derivatives were used as random forest model inputs to create a benthoscape map for the study site. Habitat suitability maps for lobster, scallop and crab were generated using a maximum entropy modelling approach.

This research supports ongoing management and monitoring of these conservation areas, providing input into the regional conservation planning process through provision of ecological information related to benthic ecosystems and habitats. This study improves our understanding of these conservation sites by establishing baselines, and ultimately facilitating effective management of these sites that feed into broader marine spatial planning objectives in the region.

Integrating the Seascape into the process of offshore wind planning in Brazil

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The intensification of global climate change has led to a growing incentive for the energy transition, stimulating the expansion of renewable energy. Brazil has one of the greatest potential to explore offshore wind due to significant capacity factors along more than 8.000 km of coastline. However, all this renewable energy potential overlaps with one of the largest carbonate dominated continental shelves in the world, where important marine ecosystems made up of limestone algae banks, sandstone reefs, coral reefs and seagrass meadows comprises a great habitat heterogeneity.

With the aim of making the implementation of offshore wind farms (OWF) compatible with the conservation of marine ecosystems, PETROBRAS is carrying out research studies to develop innovations in the process of characterization of marine environments able to foster the spatial planning of OWF from an integrated seascape perspective. Three R&D projects are being developed with the general scope of discriminating marine geohabitats using appropriate methodologies for the different characteristics of the Brazilian coast.

In the Southeastern region, the *SeascapeWind* project will apply techniques for scanning the seafloor with multispectral sonar (170, 240, 400 kHz) and develop an Angular Range Analysis modeling to increase the spatial resolution of the backscatter response. In the Northeastern region, the lower water turbidity allows the use of Satellite Derived Bathymetry (SDB) for discrimination of the seafloor, including canyons and paleochannels. Other complementary techniques will be used to increase spatial resolution, such as overflights with UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) and USVs (Unmanned Surface Vessels) to acquire more detailed aerial images and subsequent hydrographic survey of some selected areas. Complementary surveys and data acquisition using research vessels will provide the “groundtruthing” where the previously described methodologies are not applicable. In the Southeastern region, the survey of geohabitats will have a greater emphasis on paleostratigraphic reconstruction of the Quaternary, aiming to identify regions with a greater probability of occurrence of ancient shorelines whose marine cementation gave rise to large lineaments of sandstone reefs (parcels), an important structuring element of local biodiversity. The Local Ecological Knowledge (CEL) of artisanal fishermen and recreational diving operators will also be used within geohabitat mapping methodologies, associated with fishing acoustic techniques to evaluate the ecosystem services provided by the parcels.

The seascape perspective of geohabitats will be given geological and shallow geophysical surveys, evaluation of benthic biota as well as genomic and geochemical analyzes to determine the environmental quality of the region, from past to present.

Mapping the distribution of non-vent-obligate megafauna at active hydrothermal vent fields in the Indian Ocean

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There has been increasing interest in mining polymetallic sulfide deposits formed at deep-sea hydrothermal vents for minerals that are required for the transition to clean energy technologies. Because inactive deposits near active hydrothermal vents no longer discharge hot, corrosive fluid, they may be targeted for mining. Although we know that inactive areas host animals found throughout the deep sea and not exclusively on inactive deposits, these animal communities have not been well characterized. Large variation in the abundance of animals on inactive deposits has led to the speculation that environmental factors, such as proximity to active vents, may affect community composition. This research aims to understand patterns in the distribution and abundance of animals occupying inactive substrates surrounding active hydrothermal vents, and to determine factors that may be regulating their occurrence.

As part of the Indian Ocean Exploration (INDEX) project, annual expeditions survey the German contract area, which encapsulates the Rodriguez Triple Junction and portions of the Central Indian Ridge (CIR) and Southeast Indian Ridge. Video collected by the Canadian remotely operated vehicle ROPOS was used to generate a faunal distribution map of an active vent field on the southern CIR. Selected segments (30-70 m length) of the seafloor at varying distances from known active vent sites were reconstructed in Pix4D. All megafauna (visible in imagery, > 3 cm in size) were annotated along these segments and correlated to environmental factors such as nearest distance to an active vent site, substrate type, and bathymetric derivatives. We will present the results of this analysis and highlight ongoing research to identify patterns in community structure on other hydrothermal systems.

This research works to address the significant knowledge gap regarding biological communities inhabiting inactive sulfide deposits. Baseline descriptions of inactive vent and peripheral communities are crucial to understand hydrothermal vent ecosystems and, ultimately, the impact of disturbance.

Organic carbon stocks and vulnerability in marine sediments in New Zealand

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Marine sediments play a vital role in regulating climate change by burying organic carbon (OC) on timescales of thousands to millions of years. Following seafloor disturbance, this vast, largely unquantified amount of OC is at risk of being remineralised into CO₂, thereby offsetting the absorption efficiency of the oceans for taking up atmospheric CO₂. Knowledge of the amount of OC stored in marine sediments provides the basis for evaluating the risk to the marine environment and climate and the need for possible mitigation action.

We have derived the first inventory of marine OC in sediments in the Aotearoa New Zealand Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) based on methods developed for the United Kingdom. We focus on the top 10 cm of sediment, where the organic matter is likely to be the most vulnerable to natural or anthropogenic disturbances. From these first-order estimates, marine sedimentary OC stocks in the Aotearoa New Zealand's EEZ are $\sim 2240 \pm 290$ Mt OC, i.e. ca. 1% of the estimated global stocks. These stocks are distributed unevenly across shallow coastal and continental shelf environments ($\sim 7\%$), continental slope ($\sim 26\%$) and areas deeper than 1500 m ($\sim 66\%$), with fjords alone accounting for 8% of the national stocks.

From this, we have generated the first vulnerability index for OC to bottom trawling at water depths less than 1500 m by combining our results with sediment type lability, particle sinking speeds and OC degradation rates. This emphasizes the potential impact of trawling on vulnerable OC stocks in continental shelf and slope environments, particularly off south Westland, central northern Chatham Rise and along the east coast from Kaikōura to Hawkes Bay.

Our investigation also highlights the need to measure and monitor environments that have not as yet been impacted by human activities, particularly deep-water habitats that remain the greatest repository of OC on Earth.

Uncrewed surface vehicles to support uncrewed aerial vehicle shallow-water habitat mapping: Practical examples from Norwegian coastal waters

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Effective management of coastal ecosystems hinges on understanding the status and spatio-temporal variations of shallow-water marine habitats. Traditional methods of mapping and monitoring these habitats involve labour-intensive and potentially risky activities such as wading, diving, and small boat operations.

The Norwegian SeaBee infrastructure project aims to improve this process by employing uncrewed aerial (UAV), surface (USV), and underwater vehicles, coupled with advanced cameras, an efficient data pipeline, and trained neural networks. This approach enhances the speed, continuity, resolution, precision, and accuracy of habitat mapping, while simultaneously reducing cost, labour, and risk to personnel.

SeaBee uses a Maritime Robotics Otter USV as both a stand-alone tool for habitat mapping and as platform for collecting ground-truth data used to annotate UAV images for machine-learning. The USV's sensor payload currently comprises a single-beam 200kHz habitat-mapping echo sounder, a downward-facing underwater RGB camera and two surface layer instruments: a fluorometer (chlorophyll a , coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM) and turbidity) and a conductivity-temperature sensor. The vehicle has a weight of about 70 kg, is 2 m long, battery powered and uses dual differential thruster propulsion. It is typically operated at 1-3 m/s and has 15–20 hours endurance with the current payload.

The talk will focus on acquisition, management, post-processing and georeferencing of the payload data, exploring how the different types of data complement each other and contribute to the SeaBee annotation effort. It will also discuss some operational aspects and lessons learned from using the USV in the Norwegian coastal zone, such as mission planning, communication, positioning, vehicle handling and maintenance.

Progress in mapping geogenic reef habitats using Artificial Intelligence.

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Geogenic reefs are highly diverse habitats and of particular ecosystem importance. All relevant directives and conventions throughout Europe include sublittoral hard substrate habitats in some way. The mapping of geogenic reefs in the German North Sea and the Baltic Sea follows a standardised procedure. The product is a grid of 50x50 m cells, each of which is categorised according to the number of boulders detected in sidescan sonar backscatter data. This analysis is currently carried out manually by human experts, using only three classes: None, 1-5, and more than 5 boulders. The practical background to this is that a person can recognise about four to five objects simultaneously without the need for counting. Beyond that, the workload increases with counting each object one-by-one. However, the number of boulders in reef areas is significantly higher than five objects per 50x50 m cell. To make the evaluation more effective, we have automated the evaluation of the hydroacoustic data using artificial intelligence and developed an operational usable software that provides the geographic position of each detected object. We demonstrate the success of the machine learning routines and the benefits for geogenic reef mapping using an example from the nature conservation area “Pomeranian Bay – Western Rönnebank” in the German Baltic Sea. The software detected more than five boulders in 65% of the grid cells, with up to 102 boulders. Visualising the distribution of automatically detected boulders in heat maps provides a much more detailed picture of the reef structure than the raster cell approach.

Research on Visualization Techniques for Managing Large Marine Ecosystem Variability

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The increasing demand for marine spatial utilization, spurred by developments in ocean energy and marine resources, has intensified conflicts between utilization and conservation, leading to societal issues linked to preemptive marine use. As the usage and development of marine areas expand, concerns over environmental pollution, damage to Large Marine Ecosystems (LMEs), and conflicts with existing marine stakeholders have grown.

Accordingly, this research aimed to gather and standardize characteristics of LMEs, create an integrated database, and devise visualization techniques to observe and analyze changes in LMEs resulting from marine development pressures.

An effective management system for LME variability requires the ability to monitor and analyze changes over time. Therefore, this research included an in-depth analysis of domestic and international visualization techniques such as monitoring technology, simulation technology, and digital twins, which are informed by AI-based assessment models. The research facilitated a transition from traditional planar 2D visualization methods to more sophisticated WebGL technology-based 3D visualization simulation techniques. This was achieved through case studies of the Ecological Marine Units Map (EMUs Map), Borehole Geophysical Database (BGD), and Marine Radioactivity Information System (MARIS). The adoption of these advanced visualization techniques enables more effective recognition and interpretation of predictive results concerning the variability of marine ecosystems.

This research integrated several databases, including those for prediction, diagnosis, marine usage pressure, influencing factors, gap filling, and raw data, to establish a comprehensive coastal spatial characteristics database. This database supports a smart spatial information system that manages LME changes, utilizing a data lake framework. The system's primary features include integrated assessment and predictive models for significant marine pressures—like tidal power generation, gravel extraction, and harbor landfill—plus 3D spatiotemporal simulation, analysis, and reporting functions. The system provides AI-based predictions, 4D visualizations, and simulations tuned to large-scale marine pressures, enhancing policy decision-making and the management of LME variability.

This research is poised to significantly influence the prediction and management of LME changes, contributing to future marine management and conservation strategy formulation. This research was supported by the "Development of AI-based marine ecosystem diagnosis and prediction technology for response and management of Large Marine Ecosystem fluctuation factors" project of the Korea Institute of Marine Science & Technology Promotion (KIMST), funded by the Ministry of Oceans and Fisheries (KIMST-2023-187).

Distribution modelling of adult and juvenile grey triggerfish along the coastline of Brazil

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The grey triggerfish (*Balistes capriscus*) (family *Balistidae*) is widely distributed across North and South America, the west coast of Northern and central Africa and some parts of Europe. Adult grey triggerfish can be found between 10 and 100 m depths, whilst juvenile fish can be more often found in pelagic habitats and often with floating *Sargassum*. Although grey triggerfish are not currently on the IUCN endangered list their stock needs to be monitored carefully, due to increased overfishing, growing human population, and destruction or disturbance of habitat. As a result, understanding where essential fish habitats are located is vital to support effective habitat protection and healthy fish populations, as well as predicting how habitats and resultant effects on fish populations may change. While the commercial importance of grey triggerfish in Brazil is known, the footprint of essential fish habitats to help protect the species is not.

A Random Forest algorithm was used to model the spatial distribution of adult grey triggerfish along the northeastern and southeastern coastlines of Brazil. These results were then overlain with the distribution of floating *Sargassum* which was mapped using satellite imagery and compiled using Google Earth Engine. Juvenile populations were modeled using a rule-based classification system. The results of which can be used as a useful proxy to map areas that can be potentially attractive to juvenile grey triggerfish. The modeled outputs also highlight the link between juvenile distribution to floating *Sargassum*, a part of the Great Atlantic Sargassum Belt, previously noted in the literature. Once there is a better understanding of the distribution of spawning adults, linking this to valuable juvenile habitats becomes easier. Based on these distribution maps a few areas have been highlighted that could be of interest for stock enhancement work based on the spatial extent of the adult and juvenile populations as well the prevailing offshore current, and fishing activity occurring along the Brazilian coast. This work aims to better understand the distribution of triggerfish, by creating an essential fish habitat map, and provide a stepping stone for further stock enhancement work, for one of Brazil's most important food sources.

Benthic ecosystem mapping for improved understanding of fisheries stock dynamics on Georges Bank, offshore Nova Scotia

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Atlantic Canada's commercial fishery is valued at over \$3.7 billion in 2019. Globally, commercial fishing and other ocean sector industries, place a variety of contrasting pressures on benthic ecosystems. Incorporating spatial information into the assessment and management of fish populations has the potential to quantify the impacts of these pressures. For many demersal species, due to strong associations with substrate type, distributions can be relatively well represented by seafloor habitat maps. These maps, combined with geospatial fishery data, have tremendous potential to improve our understanding of the spatial patterns and complexities of benthic populations. This research addresses key knowledge gaps around environmental information associated with major fish stocks on Georges Bank, offshore Nova Scotia (sea scallop, *Placopecten magellanicus*, and monkfish, *Lophius americanus*), for improved understanding of ecosystem processes.

The study site, the Canadian side of Georges Bank, has full coverage multibeam echosounder (MBES) data collected from 1999-2000 with a spatial resolution of 20m. A suite of environmental data layers were derived from the MBES, including bathymetry, derived seafloor morphology, and backscatter. These environmental data layers were used to model and map substrate type, based on sediment data derived from a seafloor photographic data set for the study area. Additionally, spatial oceanographic variables (including temperature, salinity, velocity, and shear stress) were created using the outputs from a Finite Volume Community Ocean Model (FVCOM) developed for the area at a high spatial resolution (150m horizontal and 1m vertical). These oceanographic and MBES derived variables were used to develop species distribution models (SDMs) for scallop and monkfish using training data from stock assessment surveys conducted by Fisheries and Oceans Canada (1999-2022). Habitat suitability and species abundance were modelled through Maximum entropy modelling and random forests respectively. All model inputs were checked for correlation and, if correlated, were removed using the random forests variable importance metric.

The core habitat regions for scallops that were identified by random forests and maxent were similar. Abundance predictions for scallops performed better than monkfish based on AUC and pseudo R^2 values. Bathymetry, temperature, and velocity inputs were important in determining scallop distributions across Georges Bank. Curvature and slope inputs were most important for predicting monkfish distributions. The knowledge gained from this study can directly improve fisheries science advice for these commercially harvested species.

Quantifying remotely-sensed habitat characteristics from artificial reefs in southern California

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In southern California, artificial reefs (ARs) were historically constructed to increase recreational fishing opportunities. More recently, ARs are being constructed for reef habitat restoration and compensatory mitigation. With the introduction of artificial hard substrate, ARs can change the distribution and abundance of local marine habitats and species. The Bolsa Chica Artificial Reef complex was built over a 13-year time period (1986-2001) on soft-sediment seafloor, at a depth of 26-30 m, in federal waters four miles offshore of Orange County California. The AR modules vary greatly in construction material type (e.g., quarry rock, concrete pier pilings, rubble, barges), size, and habitat complexity. We have quantified the physical attributes of each AR module by analyzing geophysical sonar data (acoustic backscatter and bathymetry) collected by the Vantuna Research Group at Occidental College with a Multi-Phase Echo Sounder. The data collected were analyzed in ArcGIS Pro and in R with functions from the MultiscaleDTM package. The extent of AR modules were determined through a multiband raster classification composed of acoustic backscatter and bathymetric derivatives (terrain ruggedness and slope) with object-based image analysis done in ArcGIS Pro and then exported as a polygon shapefiles. Reef habitat metrics were then quantified for each module using functions from the MultiscaleDTM package. For each AR module we have quantified size and location metrics (e.g., location, depth, reef extent), and relief and complexity metrics (e.g., slope, rugosity, terrain roughness, bathymetric position index, heterogeneity). Determining these physical habitat characteristics is the first step in a larger study to inform U.S. Federal and California State resource management agencies of the best practices for the design and evaluation of future compensatory mitigation, habitat restoration or infrastructure projects (e.g., offshore energy development, harbor breakwaters, structures to protect coastlines from sea level rise).

Impact of pleasure craft boating on benthic habitats along the Italian waters

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The continuous growth of international trade and the number of ships, the pressure on marine life is increasing, especially maritime traffic, is likely to have profound and widespread impacts on benthic habitats.

This study explores the distribution of pleasure craft marine traffic and the infralittoral seabed habitats in the Italian waters through the application of spatial analysis.

Since 2009, EMODnet (European Marine Observation and Data Network) seabed habitats has been producing and collating a big amount of data and information layers. For this reason, EuSeaMap and the other spatial products make available via the EMODnet central portal (formerly seabed habitats portal) is considered relevant and was used for many applications. EuSeaMap classifies the habitats according to the EUNIS (European Nature Information System) classification, which provides a common European reference set of habitat types. In this study the sixth iteration of EuSeaMap was used.

Data on maritime traffic are provided by EMODnet Human Activity. The shipping density maps (6 annual average density layers), with a resolution of 1x1 km, cover all the EU waters from 2017 to 2022. Each grid cell provides the “density” of vessel traffic expressed as hours per square kilometres per year. The ship types considered in this study are restricted to pleasure craft as one of the most impacting aspects on the seabed habitats is the anchorage in the infralittoral biozone. Vessel density data were analysed to individuate different classes of potential impact on the seabed (low, medium, high).

The seabed habitats layer and the pleasure craft raster layer were intersected to extract information regarding the average maritime traffic density by habitat type and the percentage of surface habitat affected by vessel traffic. The highest vessel density values were registered over "A5.23: Infralittoral fine sands" and the "A5.33: Infralittoral sandy mud". When rating per total surface of habitats type affected by maritime traffic, the "A5.535: Posidonia beds" and "A5.5353: Facies of dead "mattes" of Posidonia oceanica" are the most affected, followed by "A3: Infralittoral rock and other hard substrata".

The presented results, highlighting the impact of pleasure craft boating on specific seabed habitats, could be useful to support the implementation of specific conservation measures and the evaluation of ecosystem services.

Remote Sensing and Spatial Analytics in Marine Habitat Mapping

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The end of 2023 marked the publication of the official national map of coastal and benthic marine habitats of the coastal sea of the Republic of Croatia and benthic marine habitats in the Croatian Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). This map, one of the largest and most complex products of this type in Europe, was created over a period of 25 months and contains information about the spatial distribution of marine habitats for 51% of the Adriatic Sea under Croatian jurisdiction, covering the area of approximately 30.278 km². The map is created in three scales (1:25.000, 1:10.000, 1:5.000) which vary among different marine areas based on the level of protection and other criteria.

Major methodologies applied for the creation of this map involved the utilization of Remote Sensing technologies, specifically Satellite-based Earth Observation and Aerial Photogrammetry, coupled with advanced spatial analytics through Geographic Information System (GIS) tools. Remote Sensing served as the primary method for mapping habitats down to depths of 20 meters, integrated with data derived from more than 4.000 ground truth transects acquired through in-situ methods. Concurrently, acoustic methods were used for the mapping of deeper areas.

To achieve project outcomes, which required high spatial resolution of habitat delineation and high level of content detail (mapping up to the 5th level of the National Classification of Marine Habitats), the fusion of the most advanced methodologies in Remote Sensing data processing was used: the Pixel-Based Image Analysis (PBIA) and Object-Based Image Analysis (OBIA). OBIA was used for image segmentation of Ortho maps created through aerial photogrammetry with the resolution of 0,5 m, to achieve fine detail in habitat delineation. PBIA was used on 110 seasonal images from the multispectral Sentinel-2 satellite constellation. This enabled the analysis of seasonality patterns and subsequent classification of different species of seagrass, primarily *Cymodocea nodosa* and *Posidonia oceanica*.

The fusion of the two datasets was done using advanced GIS tools and spatial statistics. The final product, which contains information about the spatial distribution of up to three habitat types per spatial feature was created using a custom-developed cartographic generalisation algorithm. This assured spatial, topological, and content accuracy of the map while providing high spatial resolution and an extensive database which will be a key tool for future Natura 2000 site and protected areas management, ecological network suitability analysis, marine resource management, and spatial planning.

Mapping of deep-water coral habitats using underwater vehicles multibeam data

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Mapping benthic habitats is an essential step for characterization, monitoring and protecting vulnerable marine ecosystems. Cold-Water Coral (CWC) reefs have been identified in canyons of the Bay of Biscay. They are characterized by a high spatial heterogeneity at both the regional and canyon scales, mainly due to the complex geomorphology of the canyons. However, knowledge of their distribution is limited to the footprint of images acquired by towed cameras or ROVs. The development of semi-automatic mapping methods using high-resolution acoustic data would be a very useful tool for the understanding and monitoring of these habitats and deep-sea habitats in general. Such a study will help to improve our knowledge of the distribution of coral habitats and their conservation status at the canyon scale, information that is currently only available along towed camera/ROV dive paths. It will provide a better understanding of the factors (geomorphology, substrate) that influence the distribution of coral habitats within a canyon, provide data for predictive models and contribute to the development of methodological guidelines for mapping and monitoring coral habitats.

During the ChEReef 2021 cruise, in the framework of the European MARHA project, a complete multibeam echosounder mapping of a Natura 2000 canyon was obtained at a metric resolution with Ifremer IdefX AUV, as well as optical and multibeam echosounder survey with the Ifremer Ariane HROV on smaller areas. The AUV was equipped with an EM2040 Multibeam system to collect high-resolution bathymetric and backscatter data at 70 m altitude and 300 kHz. The HROV Ariane, equipped with a tilted camera and an EM2040 multibeam mounted at a 45° angle, was used to explore some transects and to map some canyon cliffs at different distances.

The processing methodology at different scales with the two platforms will be presented and the detection capabilities of cold-water coral reefs using multibeam data will be discussed and compared with ground-thrusted data using optical imagery.

Benthic animal mapping: Ultra-high-resolution mapping of cold-water coral environments using laser scanning technology

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Shipboard multibeam echosounders often provide a smoothed representation of rough deep-water topography that cannot adequately characterize the vertical dimension of complex 3D seafloor structures of ecologically important habitats such as cold-water corals. These steep environments harbor rich and diverse filter-feeding communities and provide a natural protection for vulnerable species against trawling activities, but require specialised tools for ultra-high resolution mapping. In September 2023, a Schmidt Ocean Institute-funded expedition onboard the research vessel Falkor(too) focused on the exploration of vertical cold-water coral (CWC) cliff ecosystems in the Galápagos Archipelago using a Voyis MicroInsight laser scanner and a Norbit WMBS multibeam echosounder front-mounted on a work-class remotely operated vehicle. The primary objectives were to create ultra-high-resolution maps to precisely identify and delineate biological underwater features, and explore the potential of combining ultra-high resolution laser-scanning and traditional hydrographic survey methods such as MBES. This equipment was employed to map three sections of coral reefs discovered at ~350m in depth. A range of exposure times were tested, and data acquisition and georeferencing took place in Voyis' ViewLS software. We acquired 2.9 Terabytes of data, with estimated point cloud densities varying between 192,500 – 220,000 points per square meter. Preliminary visualisation of 3D point cloud in ArcGIS Pro and CloudCompare packages showed that the laser data allowed distinction of individual coral polyps as well as genus-level identification of mapped crabs. Initial observations also indicate that different biological taxa showed differences in reflexivity, with sponges showing higher intensity. This work will allow us to measure habitat complexity and start assessing the reliability of this approach to monitor habitat quality overtime.

Implications of the temperature dependence of backscatter for cross-calibration and seafloor monitoring

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Backscatter strength (BS) calibration is essential to achieve consistent BS measurements from different multibeam echosounders (MBES). Cross calibration on reference areas can provide a pragmatic solution to this need. The Kwinte reference area (KRA) near Oostende Harbor in the Belgian part of the North Sea (BPNS) is used to assess the repeatability of BS measurements and the hydrographic quality of bathymetric data. The KRA is included as a protected area in the Marine Spatial Plan 2020–2026. In order to use as well the KRA for MBES backscatter cross-calibration, multi-frequency (50–440 kHz) angular backscatter measurements were performed with a calibrated EK80 steered at various tilt angles. The resulting angular response curves are made public so that they can be used as reference levels for cross-calibrating any MBES used in the BPNS and neighbouring countries.

However, BS time series acquired over the KRA with the Kongsberg Discovery (KD) EM2040 MBES installed on the RV Belgica demonstrate a strong dependence of BS levels on seawater temperature: variations of up to 4 dB are observed for changes of 10 °C. Independent repetitive measurements carried out in the Bay of Brest (France) with another KD EM2040 MBES, show comparable variations. KD also observed this dependency on EM2040 measurements in their test-tank facilities. This dependency appears to be complex, varying with frequency and steering angle. Variations in transducer sensitivity and fluctuations in the acoustical properties of the antennas coating have been mentioned as possible explanations.

This dependence of BS on temperature is a major source of measurement variability that has not previously been considered for MBES. However, the fact that corrections based on a calibration performed at a given temperature are not applicable to data acquired under different conditions constitutes a critical issue. This dependence also makes it difficult to compare BS data acquired in different seasons as part of year-round monitoring programs, using BS as an indicator of changes in the nature and properties of the seafloor.

For surveys in the BPNS, a protocol is proposed for BS cross-calibration using systematic measurements on the KRA when starting a survey cruise. The resulting corrections are then integrated into a modified version of the MBES acquisition system SIS 5, making calibrated bottom and water column BS data available in real time. Furthermore, it is expected that a better understanding of this temperature dependency will allow systematic correction inside the MBES sensor.

Deep Thoughts from Mareano – a New Systematic Mapping Strategy for the Deep Norwegian Sea Mining Region and Beyond

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MAREANO is Norway's national offshore seabed mapping programme. Since 2005, MAREANO has focussed its efforts on the continental shelf and slope, in line with management needs and interests. In 2019, MAREANO started the process of mapping the deep Norwegian Sea in response to management requests to fill in the huge knowledge gaps in the region. However, in 2020 the next phase of mapping was delayed. This was due to a change in national management priorities, but allowed time to explore how MAREANO's survey methods could be adapted and optimised for these much deeper and steeper areas.

Given Norway's decision to open up for deep-sea mining exploration in January 2024, there is now renewed interest in performing systematic mapping of the deep Norwegian Sea to provide the baseline data for knowledge-based management of the proposed mining region. Consequently, MAREANO has stepped up its deep-sea methods development and planning, with a view to balancing scientific needs, management needs, monitoring standards, new technologies, consistency of products, and responsible use of public funds.

A lot of work has gone into MAREANO methods development over the years. Here we present the status of this work and the current plan for mapping the deep. The hope is that the GeoHab community can help act as a first pass peer review, to ensure that MAREANO is offering a robust and cost-effective strategy.

Developing of the eastern Gulf of Finland marine landscapes under anthropogenic stress

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The eastern Gulf of Finland – shallow (natural depths vary from 2–5 m in the Neva Bay to 80 m near the Gogland Island), brackish (water salinity is from 0,07 to 3–6 ‰) water area – is one of the most highly anthropogenic impacted part of the Baltic Sea. Multidisciplinary study of marine landscapes carried out by Karpinsky Institute and ABIORAS within several key-areas acquired during field cruises in 2017-2023 provide new information on hydrophysical and hydrochemical parameters, geology (bottom relief, substrates, and morpho- and lithodynamics) and macrozoobenthos characteristics (taxonomical content and quantitative development, habitat number and distribution). Analyses of high-resolution multibeam and sub-bottom profiling data enabled the detailed mapping of Quaternary deposits, and revealed diverse submerged glacial, postglacial and Holocene landforms, e.g. streamlined moraine ridges, large retreat moraine ridges, De Geer moraines, and kettle holes, linear, and curved V-shaped furrows of several kilometers long and up to five meters deep, and pockmarks. All study areas are situated below photic zone in mesohaline conditions, at approximately similar distance from shores, but characterize by local peculiarities: structure of bottom sediments and their heterogeneity; prevalence of accumulation and transit of sediments; specific geological structures (moraine, Pleistocene clays, runnels and craters); physical and chemical processes (gas (methane) production and ferromanganese concretions formation). It was found that the most favorable conditions for benthic invertebrates are a mixed sediment substrate (especially areas of Fe-Mn concretions formation). Low energy circalittoral totally anoxic mud bottom was previously attributed as azoic in sense of life is represented there by bacterial mats only. Expanding of hypoxic/anoxic near-bottom conditions caused by climate change and anthropogenic nutrient load factors is a significant environmental problem in the Gulf of Finland. Recently an opportunistic alien non-indigenous habitat-engineering spionid polychaete *Marenzelleria arctica* is established along the whole eastern Gulf of Finland and herein it demonstrates dominant position in macrozoobenthos including anoxic habitats due to its mode of life and capacity to anaerobic metabolism. *Marenzelleria arctica* mitigates the negative effects of oxygen depletion on benthic communities as a result of bio-irrigation and bioturbation of bottom sediments, as well as the drastic increases in the nitrogen/phosphorus ratio of the near bottom waters. Physical impact on the sea bottom (dredging, dumping, sand and gravel extraction, etc.) has a strong negative effect on benthic communities. Field work of 2023 was carried out with a support of the state assignment of IO RAS (Theme No. FMWE-2024-0025).

Holocene sedimentation processes and marine landscapes of the nearshore areas of the East Siberian Sea

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The coastal areas of the East Siberian Sea are among the most poorly studied regions from geological point of view. In 2018-2020, in frame of geological mapping program at a 1M scale, VSEGEI conducted geological and geophysical studies of the East Siberian Sea bottom. 3400 km of sub-bottom profiling, 3200 km of side-scan sonar survey and multibeam echosounder, 191 surface sampling sites and 31 long cores were obtained. In 2020 research was carried out in the areas between the mouth of the Indigirka River and northern periphery of Novaya Sibir' Island. At 84 sampling sites, physical and chemical parameters of the bottom sediments and near-bottom water (temperature, pH, Eh) were measured, and samples for grain-size, geochemical and mineralogical, macrozoobenthos and pollen analysis were collected. Processing and interpretation of geophysical data and the multiproxy study of sediment cores, including layer-by-layer grain-size, geochemical, diatom, palynological, and microfossil analyses as well as radiocarbon dating, were used for reconstructing geological development of the region in accord with palaeoclimatic and palaeogeographic aspects of its environmental evolution in the Late Pleistocene and Holocene. Deposits of acoustic units characterize sedimentary cyclicity from the end of Middle Pleistocene. No glacial landforms were found of the seafloor. After LGM during the warming stage and the transgression onset (18-11 ka BP) the studied area remained exposed. Pre-Holocene bottom topography predetermined the east-west direction of the shallow shelf flooding, lagoons and bays forming within paleovalleys, and the islands separating. By 8.5 ka BP, the palaeocoastline in the eastern East Siberian Sea was close to the modern one, while New Siberian Islands remained connected with the mainland. Sedimentation rates varied from 51 cm/ka during the period 6.2–5.5 ka BP to 13 cm/ka in the last approximately 1.8 ka. Macrozoobenthos samples allowed establishing some patterns of benthic fauna distribution. Within silty-clayey mud at water depths 30-37 m, polychaete worms and bivalve mollusks predominate. Representatives of Isopods and Nemertean phylum dwell in deeper areas. At water depth 20–30 m, Amphipoda crustaceans and Nematoda roundworms were found. Shallow plain areas were characterized by dominating of Cumacea. A different taxonomic composition of macrozoobenthos is characteristic for slopes of varying steepness. In 36 samples of zoobenthos particles of microplastics and paints were found. Pollen spectra of surface deposits indicates that in remoted areas of archipelago pollen of trees is almost absent, but areas beneath continental coastline comprise pollen, transmitted by the rivers from taiga zone.

Survey of seabed geoenvironments in shallow coastal area in the Gulf of Bothnia, the Baltic Sea

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Less than 30% of Finnish marine areas have been formally mapped geologically and knowledge gaps are substantial, especially in the shallow water. Increasing construction of coastal infrastructure and other human activities close to rivers and their estuaries are causing pressure on dynamic and sensitive coastal environments. Mapping shallow coastal marine areas is thus essential for developing effective strategies for coastal zone management and mitigating the impact of anthropogenic activities. Geological knowledge provides a firm basis for the protection of valuable ecosystems and resources, and for safe navigation. Geological mapping also yields important information about the structure of the seabed, in order to guarantee sustainable construction in these areas.

This study investigates the seabed geoenvironments in three distinct areas situated in shallow coastal regions adjacent to river estuaries along the eastern coast of the Gulf of Bothnia, Finland. Investigations were conducted from shore up to 15-meter water depths. The aim is to interpret the seabed structure and explore erosion environments and identify the key factors affecting them. Data on seafloor characteristics and bathymetry was gathered employing acoustic-seismic derived shipborne methods, including multi-beam echo sounding, sediment echo sounding, side-scan sonar, and reflection seismic sounding. Additionally, sediment samples were collected using surface sediment samplers. ¹³⁷Cs activity in the sediment profiles will be used to estimate sedimentation rates in the estuaries.

Preliminary findings reveal variations among the study areas. In the northernmost region the data confirms that the geomorphological features, such as eskers, seen on land extend on to the seabed. However, the features are strongly eroded, and the uppermost seabed substrate predominantly consists of erosional secondary sand. Erosional features suggest dynamic environmental conditions, likely influenced by wave action and sea ice. In contrast, more sheltered areas exhibit softer sediments, including thick mud layers indicative of active sediment accumulation. These soft sediments, coupled with shallow depths and sheltered conditions, emerge as potential habitats for dense vegetation. One of the objectives of this study is also to test the effectiveness of sounding methods in identifying these areas covered in vegetation.

The study is part of a master's thesis conducted at the University of Helsinki and SeaMoreEco (Seamless monitoring, restoration and conservation in the northern Gulf of Bothnia) project. SeaMoreEco is an Interreg Aurora project co-funded by Lapin Liitto and Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management. The study utilizes FINMARI research infrastructure such as Geomari and Gridi research vessels from Geological Survey of Finland.

Marine geological inventories around the Åland, the Baltic Sea, as part of Biodiversea LIFE IP project

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Biodiversea LIFE IP (2021-2029) is the largest collaborative project to date to safeguard the biodiversity of the Baltic Sea in Finland. The main objective of the project is to enhance the protection of marine nature and promote the sustainable use of natural resources in the marine and coastal areas of Finland. The project activities include inventories in the Åland offshore areas among others. Here the primary aim is to produce science-based information for selecting and establishing new marine protected areas (MPAs) in locations that have high nature values.

In relation to this, the Geological Survey of Finland (GTK) has focused on the geological mapping of the seabed around the Åland Islands. The marine geological surveys provide essential information on the seabed geodiversity, distribution of the sediments and background information for habitat modelling. The comprehensive mapping data supports and guides the planning and coordination of different uses of marine areas. The research areas have been selected in collaboration with other project partners to identify potential biodiversity hotspots and areas with nature values.

GTK has carried out marine geological surveys in an offshore area south of Åland in 2023 using different seismo-acoustic methods i.e., sub-bottom profilers such as Chirp sonars and seismic reflection profiler along with side scan sonar and multibeam echo sounder onboard R/V Geomari. Based on the preliminary results the research area is topographically heterogenic with bathymetry varying mainly from 10-70 m. The seafloor is dominated by underwater bedrock outcrops that may reach to depths of 10-20 m. Most of the bedrock depressions are filled with glacial and postglacial clays which are covered with 5-10 m of brackish-water and modern sediments. Thickness of these clay basins varies from approximately 5-40 m depending on the depth of the basin. Thin sand layers cover the clay basins especially in the northern part of the research area which complicates the interpretation of the deepest sediment structures. The mapped data is used to make seabed substrate map of the research area which will be used in further investigations such as the selection of potential sampling sites.

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Coastal and Marine Ecosystems Mapping in the Group on Earth Observations (GEO) Global Ecosystems Atlas Initiative

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The Group on Earth Observations (GEO) is leading a multi-collaborative effort to map the ecosystems of the planet using the IUCN's Global Ecosystems Typology (GET), a classification of Earth's terrestrial, freshwater, and coastal and marine ecosystems. The GEO Global Ecosystems Atlas (the Atlas) effort was launched at a Convening Meeting at the GEO Secretariat in Geneva, Switzerland in May of 2023, and since that time a number of ecosystem classification and mapping experts have worked with GEO Secretariat staff to characterize the scope, approach, and scientific framework which will guide the development of the Atlas. The Atlas is intended to provide current and accurate information on ecosystem extent, which can be used for both ecosystem status reporting (as per the Convention on Biological Diversity's Global Biodiversity Framework) and ecosystem accounting (as per the UN System for Environmental and Economic Accounting). To the extent that coastal and marine ecosystems are included in the IUCN's GET classification, they will be included in the ecosystem map layers that will form the content and backbone of the Atlas.

This presentation will include 1) a characterization of the Atlas concept and project to date, 2) a discussion of the importance of crosswalking of existing maps to the IUCN GET classification units, and 3) an exploration of the extent to which coastal and marine ecosystem maps might be accommodated in the Atlas. The relationship of global ecological marine units (EMUs), global ecological coastal units (ECUs), and the emerging global ecological benthic units (EBUs) to the Atlas will be addressed.

Quality of Multibeam Backscatter Data for Habitat Mapping at NGU

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Multibeam backscatter data is one of the most important sources of data for accurate habitat mapping, including geological interpretation of surficial sediments. However, its quality still often lags that of other relevant datasets such as bathymetry and its derivatives. To fulfil the potential of backscatter data for habitat mapping, it is thus imperative to continue working with sonar and software manufacturers, surveyors, and data analysts towards measuring and improving its quality. We present a few recent developments on the topic of multibeam backscatter data quality that the Geological Survey of Norway (NGU) has spearheaded for the MAREANO programme and coastal mapping activities.

First, we present the latest features of the *Iskaffe* software developed at NGU for assessing the quality of multibeam backscatter data, and originally introduced at GeoHab 2021. These include a small tool to rapidly parse all parameters in a set of raw data files and list if, and where, those changed during data collection. This tool allows rapidly detecting untimely or undesirable changes. We also introduce *bsmeta* – a user-friendly and versioned metadata template for backscatter mosaics. This template incorporates sections for the survey, the data, the data processing, the mosaic itself, and quality control. A scaled quality grade was developed for this last section.

Backscatter Working Group (BSWG): State of the Art.

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Multibeam echosounders (MBES) record backscatter data, which aid in mapping seafloor properties for seafloor habitat mapping. The Backscatter Working Group (BSWG), operating under the umbrella of GeoHab, aims to ensure consistency and usability of backscatter data for various applications. Emphasizing education, advice, and networking, the BSWG provides guidelines for acquisition and processing, standards for best practices, facilitates communication among stakeholders, and continues to address gaps in research. The BSWG functions on a voluntary basis, organized into thematic branches. Each branch focuses on specific subtopics and reports to the BSWG head, fostering connectivity among the community of backscatter users. Led by coordinators, each BSWG branch undertakes various tasks such as organizing meetings, defining projects, curating project lists, and reporting progress. Current branches include: 1) calibration/manufacturers, 2) acquisition, 3) processing, 4) analysis and interpretation, 5) environmental effects on backscatter, 6) water-column data, 7) multispectral, and 8) communication & dissemination. The BSWG organizational structure allows flexibility for branches to evolve based on community input and interest, aiming to enhance collaboration and advance backscatter data research.

Since 2022, several initiatives have been undertaken in line with the BSWG objectives. For a better communication, the BSWG unveiled a new logo and has its own LinkedIn page. The 2015 “Guidelines and Recommendations” report was given a permanent DOI for future reference, and a study was initiated on the need and feasibility to update this report. Another study is being carried out to identify the research priorities of the backscatter community. In scientific and technical subjects, significant advances have been made in the knowledge of environmental effects on backscatter levels and the development of user methods for backscatter calibration. Open-source software are being developed for backscatter quality control, and water-column data manipulation and analysis. The BSWG has started collaboration with the International Hydrographic Organization to assist them in incorporating backscatter considerations in the future iterations of their standards and guidelines documents. Finally, a cross-disciplinary project was initiated to create a backscatter e-catalogue of a variety of habitats, involving the scientific community at large. The short talk and the associated poster highlight these ongoing initiatives, and encourage future activities aimed at advancing the objectives of the BSWG for a consistent and useful backscatter data for seabed mapping. BSWG needs you!

Don't let the mud fool you – ambiguous multibeam seafloor bathymetry and backscatter measurements using a broad frequency range

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Acoustic echosounder systems have become the standard tool for determining seafloor depth. Paradoxically, there is no clear definition of where the seafloor begins acoustically, it is usually taken as the first prominent echo. In soft sediments, the acoustic determination of seafloor depth can become ambiguous, with consequences for both bathymetry and backscatter. Reasons for this behaviour are geo-acoustic properties of muddy sediments with low density contrast to seawater, low attenuation and sometimes reduced sound velocity, rendering them a slow reflector. Here we present examples from muddy seabeds in shallow water between 0 and 100 m, recorded over a wide multibeam echosounder systems (MBES) frequency range between 12 and 400 kHz. Some of the areas we observed are charged with gas. Some of them were found to have acoustic velocities lower than the overlying seawater, and others contain suspended sediments and mobile fluid mud layered on top of a stationary seafloor. The latter setting is critical for hydrographic authorities concerned with safe navigation, where the question arises as to which acoustic depth seabeds are navigable for cargo ships and where further dredging is required.

We have collected MBES data over the last decades with different systems (KONGSBERG, ELAC, NORBIT) including 12, 50, 80, 95, 180, 300 and 400 kHz frequencies. Along with the multibeam surveys, synchronized parametric sub-bottom profiles were acquired to determine the first acoustic 'seafloor' echoes and to identify differences between the two depths. The largest of these occurred in mud when surveyed with 12 kHz MBES, resulting in a depth difference of 12 m below the so-called nautical depth. This data set virtually draws a palaeo-bathymetric map of the subsurface. In the same sediment, 50 kHz MBES showed penetration and false bottom detection down to 2 m, forming strange looking ring shapes on the seabed. Even at 300 kHz, a very pronounced penetration of 30 cm could be observed, forming eyed pockmarks in the resulting backscatter map.

The vast majority of the seafloor is covered by sediments. In the deep sea, and particularly in coastal inlets and harbours, soft mud with low acoustic attenuation is among the most common sediments and penetration effects are ubiquitous. Although the contribution of volume scatterers from within the sediments is a well-described phenomenon, we suggest more data is needed to gain a better understanding of which geogenic or biogenic settings give rise to which pattern. This could lead to a better understanding and interpretation of multispectral backscatter imaging.

Pits on the seafloor in sandeel and harbour porpoise habitats

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Pockmarks are among the most prominent morphological features in the oceans and interpreted as surface manifestations of hydrocarbon fluids venting from sediments. In the North Sea, >50,000 enigmatic depressions with an average depth of 0.11 m have been documented, however, in a shallow, none-methanogenic setting. We proposed an alternative hypothesis for their formation, in which vertebrates erosively feed on the seafloor forming pits, which get subsequently scoured. We combined multibeam mapping, species distribution modelling, physical oceanography, and satellite remote sensing to evaluate where pits might occur. Spatial analyses showed all pits occur within a 10 nm radius to known sandeel (*Ammodytes marinus*) habitats and within harbor porpoise feeding grounds. We therefore suggest that porpoises feeding on buried sandeels are responsible for the initial pits.

Follow-up research including high-resolution multibeam, subbottom profiling, and video is presented here. Based on the hypothesis, we found new pits in the German Bight and offshore the Irish west coast (southwest of the Aran islands). After identification, e.g. next to the islands of Sylt and Heligoland, we lowered a drop camera and found a featureless, fine to medium grained sandy seafloor. By hitting the seafloor with the dropcam frame, we were able to frighten buried sandeel which escaped as a school with dozens of individuals. Sandeels in the water column were observed in parallel using a parametric acoustic subbottom profiler. We extended our area of interest and found more of these enigmatic depressions in Irish waters. Here, multibeam data were investigated and pits identified in 2014, which were absent in 2023. They morphologically resemble the ones in the German Bight to a very high degree. Review on the local substrate is ongoing to check if they again occur in a sandy seafloor underpinning a linkage between pits and sandeels. We currently prepare for a multifrequency experiment spanning 12-400 kHz with the goal to map out sandeels buried in the seafloor with single- and multibeam echosounders. Other areas with known extensive occurrence of marine vertebrates that feed on the ground are under consideration regarding pits.

The number of marine megafauna feeding and breeding on or near the seabed is enormous. The sediment erosion potential of biological agents - also in combination with scouring - deserves more attention from the marine geoscience research community. Seafloor morphology modulated by vertebrate macro-bioturbation and subsequent scouring may in fact represent a distinct geological facies, previously misinterpreted as pockmarks.

Revealing the evolution of trawling activity in the Fehmarn Belt. A four-year long-term monitoring using multibeam echosounder data and pioneering a qualitative assessment framework.

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Examining the interaction between trawling activity and ecosystem responses is a challenging undertaking. To comprehensively investigate this complex relationship, an interdisciplinary approach was pursued within the framework of the MGF-OSTSEE project, which is part of the DAM pilot mission with the overall aim to investigate how ecosystems of the Natura 2000 areas in the German part of the Baltic Sea will develop after the exclusion of mobile ground-touching fisheries (MGF).

A key objective in assessing the impact of mobile bottom fishing activities on the seafloor surface was the development of a suitable trawling index. This index was crucial to link the findings between different disciplines and to be able to quantify the change before and after the exclusion. Utilizing VMS data to determine trawling intensity proved insufficient due to observed small-scale heterogeneity in the trawl mark pattern using hydroacoustic imaging and the predominant use of smaller fishing boats in the investigation area, which the VMS may not cover.

Building on the ongoing project results, the focus is on demonstrating the application of the developed semi-automatic approach to image and qualitatively assess small-scale changes in trawling intensity within a sandy-silty sediment environment, monitored annually over four years. Monitoring is based on R2Sonic multibeam-echosounder data with 0.25 m gridding resolution collected during May and June, each with the same measurement setup.

The impact of ship anchoring on muddy sediments in Eckernförde Bay (Baltic Sea)

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Seafloor habitats in shallow waters are affected by increasing anthropogenic pressure, including anchoring of ships and boats. Anchoring threatens seafloor integrity in different ways such as the disturbance of benthic habitats or the redistribution of nutrients, CO₂, and contaminants. However, the scale and the consequences of these processes are poorly constrained. To assess the morphologic impact of anchoring on a muddy seabed, we collected dual-frequency bathymetric and backscatter data within Eckernförde Bay (Southwestern Baltic Sea) in two consecutive years. We document hundreds of anchoring tracks within a survey area spanning less than one square kilometer, and quantify the degeneration of the furrows and mounds over time using slope and backscatter maps. A relative chronological order of all tracks within the same network is derived from the intersections between the tracks with the help of a topological sorting algorithm. The lengths of most tracks ranged from several meters to a hundred meters, while some extended for several hundred meters. A relatively fresh anchoring track can reach a depth of up to half a meter. Notably, a one-year-old anchoring track remained among the most pronounced features within the survey area, exhibiting undulations in the decimeter range. Conversely, presumably much older anchoring tracks show no discernible bathymetric evidence but were identifiable in backscatter maps, suggesting long-term alteration of the seafloor beyond any obvious morphological changes. As seaborne trade is expected to increase over the coming decades, this study emphasizes the need to include the process of ship anchoring, when assessing the enduring impacts of anthropogenic activities on already stressed shallow marine ecosystems.

Accessing Intensity:

Making the Canadian Hydrographic Service's intensity inventory available

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In 2016 the Canadian Hydrographic Service (CHS) created the Hydrographic Data Access Centre of Expertise (HDACoE) to explore methods of providing access to the CHS's data archives. The initial focus of the HDACoE was to release gridded bathymetric datasets for non-navigational use. The result was the CHS NONNA Data Portal launched in 2020. To date, more than 5 million bathymetric datasets have been downloaded free of charge.

The success of the CHS NONNA Data Portal has led the HDACoE to further identify, recover and to facilitate access to other forms CHS data that may be of use to our clients. The CHS has been collecting multibeam echo sounder (MBES) and Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) data for bathymetric purposes for decades. The concurrent collection of backscatter information from hydrographic surveys has been identified as a valuable product for publication as an additional layer through the CHS NONNA Data Portal.

While the CHS' primary focus remains safety of navigation, it is clear that intensity data is of great importance for environmental management/knowledge and of value to the Blue Economy. The interest in intensity data continues to grow in the scientific, commercial, environmental and Indigenous communities. Increased access to intensity data would be a benefit to seafloor modelling and mapping.

CHS is embarking on a pilot project to make our intensity data accessible with four main objectives: Immediate release of existing intensity products, Feedback form to better understand community interest and need, User metrics (Dashboard) to respond to client feedback and the Production/Collection of metadata to accompany the published data.

These products will be accessible to view within a new layer within the CHS NONNA Data Portal, and available to download in GeoTiff and/or ASCII format with metadata.

The Hydrographic Data Access Centre of Expertise (HDACoE) has encountered many challenges to make the Canadian Hydrographic Service's intensity inventory free and available for public interest. This presentation will showcase the new release of the NONNA intensity layer to highlight the HDACoE's efforts to make this data accessible.

Planning multi-deployment surveys for habitat mapping by optimising coverage in bathymetric feature space.

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Benthic imaging surveys collect georeferenced, in-situ observations of the seafloor, which can be used to derive habitat classifications. These habitat classifications are then used to ground-truth habitat models that predict the benthic habitat from available remotely-sensed data. However, optical sensing has a limited range underwater resulting in a small sensor footprint. Given limited ship time and bottom time, only a tiny fraction of the survey area can be visually sampled in-situ. This motivates the problem of how to utilise available remotely-sensed data to plan in-situ sampling, such that the collective utility of the in-situ observations is maximised. We propose that to learn a representative habitat model for a given area, the feature space of the remotely sensed data should be comprehensively sampled with in-situ observations. The feature space refers to the set of environmental covariates that are related to the benthic habitat, which in this research focuses on the bathymetric terrain and its derivatives. Planning in-situ sampling for feature space coverage is a known problem with established solutions. However, these existing planning methods do not readily account for the operational constraints of collecting the in-situ samples, which is important for Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) surveys and towed camera systems, where it is more efficient to collect samples in long transects. Our research investigates planning techniques that optimise sampling trajectories over feature space metrics and operational constraints to maximise feature coverage. We demonstrate that the proposed planning methods improve feature space coverage compared to both random sampling and established feature space coverage methods. Our methods are demonstrated using bathymetric terrain descriptors, but they extend naturally to other large-scale auxiliary oceanographic data modalities. This research is a valuable tool for planning AUV sampling campaigns, as it increases the utility of each survey mission leading to more efficient use of ship time. We present field trials of this sampling technique from a recent AUV campaign in Apollo Marine Park, Australia.

A Framework for The Application of Remote Sensing Technologies for Benthic Mapping and Spatial-Temporal Monitoring in Southern Australia

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Rapid advancements in remote-sensing geophysical and biological technologies in recent decades have been made possible by fierce manufacturer competition and parallel advancements in digital signal processing procedures. Our technological capabilities have progressed in tandem with the growing recognition of the need for spatial products to aid in sustainable development, management, and conservation goals. This progress has culminated in the imaging of benthoscapes worldwide; thus, allowing for the construction of detailed maps depicting benthic habitats. The ever-blossoming field of benthic mapping has produced a diversity of approaches, data types, technologies, and models that are used to decipher and map distributions of biological patterns of the benthos.

Amongst the chaos of the rapidly growing field, the research outlined here aims to develop and present a data acquisition and modelling framework for predicting South-Eastern Australia's coastal and near-coastal benthic habitats. To build this framework, I harmonised two multibeam survey areas that covered a combined area of 324km² and had a small overlap of 0.8km² on the boundary of Apollo Marine Park in South-Western Victoria. The older data were collected in 2008 using a Reson 8101 while the more recent dataset was collected in 2021/2022 using a Kongsberg EM2040C. I implemented a bulk shift procedure on the two backscatter datasets to accord their dB values, and mosaiced the bathymetry datasets, producing two complete georeferenced datasets. Derivatives from the newly mosaiced bathymetry dataset were then computed at various scales of the neighbourhood to provide information on the seafloor state. A Supercell object-based image analysis was also employed at various scales to provide segmentation by grouping pixels into vector objects. Finally, three sources of sea truth data were sourced to provide insight into the biotopes of Apollo Marine Park and the Cape Otway coastline. These were collected using baited remote underwater video stations, towed videos, and an autonomous underwater vehicle, respectively. The datasets focused on different areas that were dominated by different habitat types from macroalgae biotopes in the near-shore areas to sponge-dominated soft sediment habitats in the deeper waters. The datasets, and therefore the technologies they used, spanned across almost two decades and used different annotation schemes that needed to be translated to the Combined Biotope Classification Scheme (CBiCS) before modelling could begin.

Four machine learning approaches; a Random Forest, a Generalised Additive Model, a Boosted Regression Tree, and a Convolution Neural Network, are being compared across an assortment of the data available over a range of scales. The best method, determined based on training speed, prediction speed, and accuracy for benthic habitat classifications, will be used to create habitat classifications across the site. This study can then be used as a reference guide for researchers before carrying out benthic habitat classifications using combined datasets.

Mapping shallow-water maerl beds with UAV hyperspectral imaging

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Maerl beds are habitats formed by several species of free-living coralline red algae. The beds are typically composed of a pink layer of live maerl on top of white and dead corallines. Maerl beds provide a complex habitat supporting a high diversity of marine species and a multitude of ecosystem services, including building up large and long-term carbon stocks.

In some regions, maerl is extracted for commercial purposes, leading to a direct loss of habitat complexity and of associated biodiversity. The regrowth of maerl is slow, and reestablishment of exploited maerl habitats can take several decades. Maerl beds are also threatened by pollution, oil and gas exploitation, fishing activities, coastal darkening, ocean warming and ocean acidification. OSPAR lists the status of maerl beds in arctic waters as “unknown”. Due to lack of studies, there is a significant gap in our understanding of their distribution, ecological structure and ecosystem functioning.

The MASSIMAL project aims to develop tools for mapping shallow-water benthic habitats, including maerl beds, through hyperspectral imaging from unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). Hyperspectral cameras have higher spectral resolution than regular RGB cameras, and are thus able to capture more detailed measurements of the benthic reflectance. As part of the project’s research campaigns, maerl beds close to the island of Søla (65.68°N, 11.71°E) were imaged. “Ground truth” observations of maerl beds were collected using underwater imaging, performed using ROVs, an autonomous boat, and snorkelling.

When viewed at close range, maerl has a distinctly pink color. However, due to the high absorption of red light in water, maerl appears as gray or green in aerial photos. We show examples of the remote sensing reflectance spectra for maerl, and how this changes as a function of water depth.

In order to map maerl beds, maerl has to be separated from nearby habitats. For the dataset presented here, these habitats mainly consist of sand, rock, and brown macroalgae. We show that live maerl beds generally have higher remote sensing reflectance than macroalgae, and lower reflectance than sand and rock, across the whole visible spectrum.

We present results from machine learning models trained to classify sand, maerl, rock and brown algae. The results show that the depth-dependent light absorption of the water layer combined with a lack of distinct spectral features makes classification across a large range of water depths challenging. However, within a limited depth range, i.e. 1-4 meters, maerl can be classified with relatively high accuracy.

Benthoscape maps as conservation management tools in the Gulf of St. Lawrence, Canada

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Significant gaps persist in our understanding of spatial patterns and processes in the ocean, especially in benthic ecosystems. Effective marine conservation management and monitoring strategies require that these knowledge gaps be addressed. Benthoscape maps, which delineate the seafloor based on broad biophysical characteristics, can act as a baseline for monitoring changes in the benthos over time. However, many benthic conservation sites lack these mapping products. In addition, conservation management tends to focus on information pertaining to species presence and abundance, but the health of an ecosystem depends on how many niches are filled and what functions are provided by the local species. Here we generate benthoscape maps for three sponge conservation sites surrounding Anticosti Island in the Gulf of St. Lawrence, Canada, as designated by Fisheries and Oceans Canada (DFO). These sites cover a combined area of 1574 km², with depths ranging from 57 m to 424 m. We conducted multibeam echosounder (MBES) surveys to collect bathymetry and backscatter data. We also conducted 99 transects with a 4K drop camera as ground validation and to record and quantify the benthic community patterns and composition. We found that sponge abundance at these sites was lower than expected, and the substrate composition was often not suitable for their growth. Trends in functional traits, defined as measurable phenotypes of a species that impact its life history, fitness, or performance, in relation to benthoscape classes were also recorded to compare both species and function diversity spatially across these conservation sites. Results from these surveys and analyses will be presented to highlight how this approach is providing new insights for conservation management and Marine Protected Area (MPA) design in Canada. The outputs from this will also provide monitoring tools for currently designated MPAs.

Geohabitats mapping at 1°N latitude of the Mid-Atlantic ridge

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Studies on the characterization of geohabitats are important contributions to support the understanding of marine regions. The main objective of this research was the mapping of marine geohabitats through multibeam bathymetry at 1°N Latitude of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge.

The use of hydroacoustic methods for geohabitat mapping has been widely employed in the last two decades, as these systems are used to infer the physical, geological, and biological properties of the seafloor. Data were collected aboard the Hydrographic and Oceanographic Research Ship (NpqHOc) Vital de Oliveira, within the scope of the QWHALES, SeabedMap and INCT Atlantico projects. An EM-122 multibeam echosounder was used, in the 12 kHz frequency range, with an opening of 60° and at a speed of 7 knots. The sub-bottom profiler equipment, SBP-120 from Kongsberg, was also utilized. Raw data processing was performed with Caris HIPS & SIPS version 11.4.24 software. The generation of subproducts, interpretation, and measurement of features were performed in the GIS environment.

Until this study, the selected study area had not been mapped, meaning that mapping a previously unexplored region of the ocean floor represents a crucial advancement, emphasizing the importance of understanding the complexity of the marine environment. Through bathymetric and acoustic backscatter data, different maps were generated. The interpretation of these data revealed the presence of various important geological features on the seafloor, including the discovery of seamounts. In the seamount region, an elevation profile was traced, identifying an approximate height of 156 meters and a diameter of around 1 km, suggesting a prominent formation on the seafloor; there is a strong indication of marine life development, both associated with geohabitat development related to geomorphology and the possibility of active hydrothermal activities in the region.

Seabed mapping for marine spatial planning: Canadian Pacific shelf

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The Geological Survey of Canada (GSC), a branch of the Canadian Department of Natural Resources (NRCan) has undertaken a seabed mapping program to provide geoscience to support the safe, effective and sustainable use of the seabed. It contributes to Fisheries and Oceans Canada's national marine spatial planning process, federal impact assessment processes, marine renewable energy, and national marine conservation targets.

A series of maps of seabed characteristics are being produced and will identify surficial geology, geological hazards and important morphological features of interest among other things. Extensive ship-based field work was conducted onboard Canadian Coast Guard science vessels. In collaboration with the Canadian Hydrographic Service, new multibeam bathymetry data was acquired totalling > 17,000 km². Targeted sampling was conducted to constrain geological map units and follow up on features of interest that were identified during the mapping process. Primary map products at a coast-wide scale include: regional digital elevation model bathymetry dataset gridded at 10 m; grainsize database compilation using >15,000 samples and over 50 years of grain size data; surficial geology and geomorphology. Targeted features of interest include: geomorphology of Chatham Sound showing glacial landforms and glass sponge reefs; sediment dynamics on Dogfish Bank, an area of interest for offshore wind energy; deglacial volcanism in Milbanke Sound where a submerged cinder cone is emplaced on a drowned recessional moraine; surficial geology and glacial features in Queen Charlotte Strait; assessment of gas venting and prospective cold seep prevalence using multibeam bathymetry water column data in the north coast region and Swiftsure Bank; and cumulative impacts of commercial anchorages in the Salish Sea. A semi-automated seabed classification model using Esri ArcMap was produced to assist with mapping work. As part of the Canadian 'Open Science' initiative, all data and products will be made publicly available.

Mapping the German EEZ of the North and Baltic Sea - an update on project status and remaining challenges

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Detailed knowledge of the seabed is essential for a wide range of decisions, including marine nature conservation and marine spatial planning. According to EU directives implementation, accurate information on the seabed sediment types is a prerequisite for the identification, monitoring and protection of marine benthic biotopes in European marine waters. The Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (BSH) of Germany started a sediment mapping program of the German Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) of the North and Baltic Sea in cooperation with the Federal Agency for Nature Conservation (BfN) as well as Research and Development partners in 2012. By acquiring new hydroacoustic data and reprocessing old available data, about 68% of the German EEZ has been mapped until now – and the surveying is still ongoing.

Based on backscatter mosaics, geological sampling and underwater videos, full-coverage and highly detailed sediment distribution maps, comprising three classification levels, are generated by using a standardized procedure. Additionally, quantitative information on the spatial variability of boulder occurrences at the seafloor is provided as a boulder distribution grid map. For this aim, a specific method was developed, which allows fast and practicable manual boulder detection based on the area-wide backscatter mosaics, whereby overlaid grid cells are manually categorized into three classes (0, 1-5 and >5 boulders). Combining the information of the sediment and boulder distribution maps enables the identification of important marine benthic habitats of the North and Baltic Sea such as geogenic hard substrates.

Nevertheless, even though standardized and reproducible mapping approaches are used and boulders are principally detectable in backscatter data, practical experience reveals difficulties and limitations. In particular, the frequency and quality of the hydroacoustic data and furthermore the heterogeneity of the sediments are of major importance for an objective and clear identification and delineation. Starting with an updated overview of the mapping project, we will present and discuss the challenges and limitations of sediment mapping and manual boulder detection using hydroacoustic data.

Quantifying blue carbon storage in eelgrass beds: Combining sediment analyses with geospatial mapping on the Nova Scotian coast.

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In a world where carbon is being produced at a rate much higher than the sequestration capabilities of the natural environment, researchers have been investigating ways to increase the proficiencies of existing carbon stocks. In recent years, seagrass ecosystems have been recognized as a potential avenue for elevated carbon sequestration. Despite comprising only 0.2% of the seafloor, seagrass meadows are responsible for burying 10% of total carbon in the ocean and have twice the carbon storage capacity as compared to terrestrial forests. Specifically in the North Atlantic Ocean, eelgrass have been known as the most productive of the seagrass species for the storage of blue carbon in their underlying sediments. To date, there have been many studies testing eelgrass storage capacity across the world, but a significant knowledge gap exists in investigating how far away from the eelgrass beds that carbon storage is elevated. This study seeks to measure blue carbon storage in several known eelgrass meadows along the Nova Scotia coastline, and test how far away from the meadows blue carbon is elevated in the sediments.

To measure this, a high-resolution multi-beam echosounder (MBES) will collect spatial data in and around various eelgrass meadows to approximate organic carbon percentage in surface sediments, which will be used to create a benthic habitat map. This data will be collected in combination with push core samples taken both within and at various distances from the edges of the eelgrass beds to determine a depth profile and quantify how much of the carbon is stored in aboveground versus belowground biomass. A combination of spatial mapping and sediment analysis will be conducted to both determine the spatial distribution of blue carbon and test the depth and distance at which it is elevated within the eelgrass meadows and their surrounding areas. The results of this study will contribute to the body of existing knowledge of the carbon sequestration capabilities of eelgrass in the North Atlantic and hopefully aid in the decision-making regarding the protection and restoration zones of eelgrass.

Mapping kelp using bathymetric Lidar?

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Maps of submerged aquatic vegetation (SAV) such as seagrass, seaweed and kelp are important in coastal management. Current methodology ranges from underwater video-based methods, acoustics, and remotely sensed RGB, multi-spectral or hyperspectral imagery. Which to choose depends on the inherent trade-offs between costs, spatial accuracy and classification ability. All methods were tested near Stavanger, Norway, as part of the method development within the ‘Marine Base Maps for the Coastal Zone’ project. In addition, shallow water bathymetry was collected using both Multibeam Echosounder (MBES) and bathymetric Lidar.

In this study we explore the potential use of bathymetric Lidar for mapping SAV with emphasis on larger kelp. The primary feature of interest in bathymetric mapping is the seabed itself. However, just as acoustic signals may be reflected by dense materials, objects on the seabed will reflect the laser emitted from the Lidar. Thus their elevation above seabed can be measured. While Lidar is inherently challenged in classifying objects as it only emits a single wavelength (622 nm), a combination of logical deduction, derived properties and support from other biotic and abiotic models or data can aid. Kelp in Norway can form dense ‘forests’ more than 2 meters tall and live to depth of 30 meters. Few other vegetation on hard substrate in shallow waters can obtain similar height and density.

Following initial classification of points to seabed, water surface, noise and vegetation, the height of points above seabed can be determined. Using this, initial results quickly allowed identification of dense and tall kelp forests whose upper canopy layer showed distinct separation from seabed below. But challenges occur when kelp density or height is low or decline towards edges. As laser is attenuated by water and constituents, a high-powered system is needed to reach three times the Secchi depth. But point density is greatly reduced at such depth and limits kelp detection and classification at depth below 15m. And in the shallows, dense kelp may even block the Lidar from detecting any seabed points.

The perspectives for mapping dense occurrences, as well as monitoring exploitation such as kelp harvesting, are promising. Further challenges and potential solutions are discussed. Improved point classification using waveform data, and multi-modal AI classification incorporating environmental layers, may extend the usefulness. While costs of Lidar for the sole purpose of kelp is prohibitive, data may e.g. derive from otherwise existing or planned bathymetric mapping.

Marine research and habitat mapping programmes in Norway

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Norway has a very long tradition of harvesting resources from the oceans and coastal waters, dating back to the early immigrants following the retreating ice cap in the Stone age nearly 12 000 years ago. Marine research in Norway started in the 19th century, with pioneers like Georg Ossian Sars studying cod and herring.

The EEZ (exclusive economic zone) of Norway is 2.385.178 km², which is around seven times larger than the onshore area. Fish and petroleum resources in the offshore area are very important, along with aquaculture in the coastal zone. Renewable energy and deep sea mineral resources are now emerging as possible important activities in the future. All of these human activities have been the driving force for large research and habitat mapping programmes. The effects of climate change are also an important question. This talk will provide an overview of the long lines in Norwegian history, and current research and marine mapping addressing the need for knowledge for ecosystem-based management of Norway's EEZ.

AUV Synthetic Aperture Sonar imagery and bathymetry for sedimentary processes and detection of trawling disturbance

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Autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) are being used more and more as platforms for various acoustic sensors, such as multibeam echosounders (MBES) and sidescan sonar (SSS), with multibeam echosounders providing bathymetry and backscatter, and sidescan sonars providing detailed imagery. Synthetic aperture sonars (SAS) like HiSAS2040 provide range-independent sonar images, typically with a resolution of 5 cm over a 240 m swath, minus a nadir zone of c. 60 m. Recent development of processing routines also allows the bathymetry to be extracted from the SAS signals, and bathymetric grids with a resolution of 25 cm have been produced. This gives new possibilities for characterizing sediments and identifying sedimentary processes. It is also very useful for documenting and quantifying environmental disturbance of the seabed caused by trawling.

We will provide examples from two areas in the North Sea – one in the southern part, and one from Skagerrak in the northeastern part.

In the southern part, the water depth ranges from c. 45 to 150 m. Nature types are diverse – from moraines with iceberg ploughmarks to large sand banks with spectacular sand waves, moraine ridges, and sandy flats showing impressive current-induced structures. The combination of vessel-based MBES data, and AUV-based MBES and SAS data allows identification of several scales of sedimentary structures. Ripples, mega-ripples and sand waves are observed, often in intricate patterns indicating complex bottom current distributions, with a superimposition of tidal currents, oceanographic currents and currents linked to wave energy. Sand erosion areas where the subcropping moraine is exposed are also clearly imaged, with coarse material like gravel, cobbles and blocks up to several metres in diameter can be recognised. Video and photos show that these hard bottom habitats have a fauna strikingly different from the sand areas.

Trawling has been suggested to be an important source of carbon release to the overlying water masses and eventually the atmosphere. We have therefore started investigating both areas of intense trawling, and areas of hardly any trawling. The results so far indicate that the combination of SAS imagery and SAS bathymetry provides a powerful combination for documenting and quantifying the physical disturbance of the seabed.

Seabed mapping for ecosystem based management in Polar environments

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The Arctic is warming three times as fast as the global average. Within 2050, the temperatures on Svalbard may increase 3° to 8° C. The sea ice melts, and within a few decades we may have a transition from a White Polar Ocean to a Blue Polar Ocean. Warming may influence bottom water formation, and the benthic ecosystems. Climate effects are simultaneous with other influences such as pollution, fishing, changes in land use, population increases, and changes in culture and economy.

About two-thirds of the Norwegian ocean territories are north of the Polar Circle, and includes the northern parts of the Norwegian Sea, the Barents Sea and the Polar Ocean. Nature types range from shallow waters influenced by wave action or strong currents, to deep-sea environments with abyssal plains and the Mid-Atlantic Ridge with mineral occurrences. In addition, large shelf areas, extensively sculpted by the ice sheets during the last glaciations and contemporary glacimarine fjord environments.

In the Mareano programme, we have mapped the nature types and benthic habitats since 2006. We have partly mapped large, continuous areas, and partly used a transect approach with c. 1100 km² boxes. The motivation has been to give a general documentation of the nature types and habitats, to provide a baseline for documenting future changes, and to document the environmental state of the seabed before e.g. extensive trawling, in areas that are becoming more accessible due to the melting sea ice.

Working in Polar environments gives certain challenges. Heavy storms can occur even during summer time, and during winter time freezing of equipment may pose serious problems. Even if the Arctic is warming, sea ice is still a challenge when mapping in these waters and vessels capable of working during ice conditions like the RV Kronprins Haakon are the preferred choice.

We will provide examples of the wide range of habitats and nature types, and describe how we adapt to the harsh environment. We will also share some thoughts on the future Arctic seas.

Benthic habitat of the Gulf of Maine: The legacy of Mesozoic to Cenozoic geological history

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A series of vignettes illustrate and describe a suite of benthic habitats in the Gulf of Maine. Present-day benthic habitats are the legacy of the Mesozoic Era (252 to 66 million years ago) to Cenozoic Era (66 million years ago to present) geological history of the region. The shallow continental margin platform hosting the Gulf of Maine was formed during the opening of the North Atlantic Ocean by rifting of the North American and African plates at a spreading centre during the Mesozoic Era. Both non-marine and marine sedimentary rocks were deposited on the new continental margin. During the Cenozoic Era, a series of sea-level transgressions and regressions, associated with multiple advances and retreats of North American continental ice sheets, were accompanied by deposition and erosion of sediments and underlying bedrock. Some of these erosional events were profound and are reflected in today's broad-scale geomorphology of the region.

During the Last Glacial Maximum (c. 24 to 20 ¹⁴C thousand years ago) of the Pleistocene Epoch (2.58 million to 11.7 thousand years ago), the southeastern margin of the Laurentide Ice Sheet (LIS) occupied the Gulf of Maine. Mapping of submarine geomorphology provides evidence that a fast-flowing marine ice stream occupied the gulf. The LIS retreated to the north in a step-wise fashion. Surficial sediments were deposited in the gulf during and following glaciation. Plan-view glacial geomorphology is interpreted from high-resolution multibeam sonar bathymetry set within regional-scale bathymetric data. Interpretation of seismic reflection profiles provides the cross-sectional structure of the glacial features and sedimentation patterns in the Gulf of Maine. Basins in the gulf display thick (tens of metres) deposits of fine-grained glacial and post-glacial sediments. Ridges separating the basins are dominated by coarse-grained deposits (till) and these ridges constitute a series of major recessional moraines.

During the Holocene Epoch (11.7 thousand years ago to present), the interplay of sea-level rise with post-glacial crustal rebound resulted in subaerial exposure, for a time, of Georges and Browns banks, thus restricting the Gulf of Maine from the Atlantic Ocean. Interpretation of multibeam sonar bathymetry provides evidence of fluvial erosion on the banks during this time. Later inundation was accompanied by the development of extensive sand wave fields formed under the modern current regime.

Integrating bathymetric data into species distribution models for local fisheries management in Aotearoa New Zealand

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Understanding spatial distribution patterns of culturally and economically valuable species is key to effective local marine management initiatives in Aotearoa New Zealand. This study utilises bathymetric and fisheries data collected as part of the Iongairo project, a collaboration between government agencies, indigenous communities, and the University of Otago to better understand key habitats for Taonga (treasured) species in Te Pātaka o Rākaihautu/Banks Peninsula. Multibeam echosounder imagery, collected initially for navigational purposes, was integrated with fisheries data collected using baited remote underwater videos (BRUVs) to create models explaining distribution of key fisheries species. BRUV surveys, which provide relative abundance estimates of carnivorous fish and mobile invertebrates, were conducted across a range of marine management regimes, including marine reserves, commercial and recreational fishing zones, and customary protection areas (coastal ecosystems managed by indigenous communities). Bathymetric habitat and broad scale environmental data was integrated into various models to predict distribution patterns and identify key drivers controlling species presence. This study demonstrates the versatility of bathymetric datasets for use in ecological modelling, with implications for marine management initiatives.

Improving Multibeam Backscatter Results in the Field: Updates to NOAA's Calibration & Quality Evaluation Processes

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NOAA acquires multibeam data with over 26 platforms, operating a variety of systems across a diverse seafloor range, from deep sea to nearshore. Multibeam backscatter is now a routine data deliverable, and NOAA has worked closely with field units and data stakeholders to implement meaningful improvements to our calibration and quality control workflow. We have outlined a generalized, flexible, and stackable calibration framework that enables operators to build a relative calibration scheme that is appropriate for their system. Depending on the specifics of the field unit, a complete calibration may independently address residual biases associated with pulse characteristics, the sonar's angular beam pattern, and other vessels on project. Additionally, we are implementing quality metrics for both the presence of artifacts in backscatter data and the general perceived quality of the processed mosaic. These metrics are preliminarily based on two independent but complementary processes: identifying incoherent pings and soundings and computing a no reference image quality assessment, respectively. By establishing initial thresholds for these metrics, field units are able to sort their backscatter into one of three categories-- good, fair, or poor-- in an unbiased and consistent manner.

These updates to NOAA's calibration and quality evaluation processes represent the operationalization of on-going multibeam backscatter research. By seeking to implement operational, open-source tools at a fleet scale, we hope to track and ultimately improve the quality of the backscatter product that we provide to a growing and diverse set of users.

***Themachinethatgoesping*: A new perspective on multibeam water column data**

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Multibeam water column image (WCI) data can provide valuable information for understanding marine environments. For example, it has been used to investigate underwater gas seepage, macro algae, fish, shipwrecks and suspended particulate matter. However, the usage of this technology still trails behind its potential. One reason is the lack of purpose-built software packages which inhibits the creation and adoption of new, improved scientific methods using WCI data.

Themachinethatgoesping (short: *Ping*) is a new open-source python library (implemented in c++) for processing multi- and singlebeam echosounder data that is currently developed within the TURBEAMS project. *Ping* aims at simplifying the development and application of novel processing methods by providing a performant python interface to the acoustic raw data, together with commonly needed processing routines. Examples include implementing and testing water column calibration routines, extracting quantitative meaningful backscatter data and gridding acoustic samples in 2D and 3D. This base functionality allows for creating custom processing routines as sharable python scripts that are powerful enough to handle large amounts of data and transparent enough to understand the specific equations applied to the acoustic raw data.

In this contribution, we will demonstrate the application of *Ping* in the TURBEAMS project for extracting calibrated WCI data. The objective is to investigate suspended particulate matter in the Belgian part of the North Sea. *Ping* is actively developed, and its progress can be followed on Github (<https://github.com/themachinethatgoesping>).

Mapping indirect habitat loss: about awareness, implementation realities and prevention

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Marine ecosystems are affected by many drivers and pressures, both natural and anthropogenic. Pressures are classified as sealing (i.e., placement of structures), abrasion (e.g., scraping by demersal trawling), removal (e.g., aggregate extraction, navigational dredging), and deposition (e.g., dredged material disposal). Assessment of direct physical disturbance and loss is based typically on spatial data of human activities. However, the full extent of the pressures, and particularly indirect habitat losses in the near and far field are much more difficult to assess. It relates to the intensity, frequency and persistence of an activity that may lead to irreversible habitat loss. Assessing habitat loss is a mandatory criterium of seafloor integrity, an important descriptor of Good Environmental Status as defined by the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD; 2008/56/EC). New thresholds are now proposed, e.g., restricting loss to a maximum of 2 % per broad habitat type (BHT). Hitherto, this is related mostly to sealed loss; for indirect loss there are yet no commonly agreed approaches.

For the MSFD implementation, Belgium put forward an indicator on the areal extent of EUNIS level 2 habitats and gravel beds. In view of applying thresholds of habitat change substantial improvements are needed on the knowledge of the main substrate types in the Belgian part of the North Sea (BPNS) (mud, sand, and coarse sediments per biological zone). For the BPNS, this categorization complies with the definition of the BHTs *sensu* the Commission Decision EU 2017/848. Dedicated seabed mapping and monitoring is set-up at high spatial and temporal resolution, underpinned by information on geology and sediment dynamics. A new reference seabed substrate map has been developed building on high-resolution acoustic data over the entire BPNS and is further valorised via EMODnet Geology and Seabed Habitats. Pilot change assessments are made from a risk perspective with focus on (1) 'sandification' (mud to sand; gravel to sand), with relevance to the burial of sensitive receptors; and (2) 'muddification' (e.g., sand to mud), with relevance to changes in biogeochemistry.

Steps are taken to assess the cumulative impact of activities and how this may lead to indirect loss. However, the dynamical nature of shelf environments, fragmented knowledge on substrate variability (geology-related), but also the process of map making, and chosen scale, complicates applying thresholds of change. Notwithstanding the environmental and operational constraints, most important is to prevent irreversible loss, requiring systematic integration of data and knowledge.

Discovering new underwater ‘worlds’ – Mapping the depths of Australia’s remote Indian Ocean Territories (IOT)

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Australia’s westernmost tropical islands mark the summits of some of the largest seamounts in the remote Indian Ocean Territories (IOT). These include Christmas and Cocos (Keeling) Islands that lie ~1500 km to ~2100 km off the western Australian mainland, and form Australia’s newest Marine Parks. These new marine parks, which were established in March 2022, encompass a vast area of 744,070 km² and include marine habitats that extend to depths of ~6000 m.

Much of the deep seafloor of this remote tropical region remained largely unmapped until recently. In 2021 & 2022, CSIRO, and its Marine National Facility (MNF) supported a Museums Victoria-led research voyage aboard RV *Investigator*, to map and unravel the biodiversity mysteries of Australia’s Indian Ocean Territories.

Here we present on the extensive seafloor mapping efforts that were undertaken by RV *Investigator* in the IOT. We reveal, in high resolution, newly discovered deep-sea habitats across the region’s seamounts, which are home to some strange and amazing creatures. These mapping efforts contribute significantly to deep-sea research and future resource sustainability of this remote Australian region.

SEABEDMAP Project. Results 2023: Geomorphic features on the easternmost Brazilian Equatorial Margin

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More than 6.000 km² have been surveyed on the continental slope, of the easternmost point of the Brazilian Equatorial Margin, as part of the SeabedMap Project. The main aims were mapping the seabed and training human resources, with an emphasis on sustainable development objectives 4 - Quality Education, 5 – Gender Equality, 13 – Climate Action and 14 – Life below Water. This contribution represents the first multibeam mapping for the corner of Brazil, between 100 and 2000 m depth.

The data were acquired aboard the Brazilian Navy Hydrographic and Oceanographic Research Ship (NpqHOc) Vital de Oliveira. Multibeam bathymetry, sub-bottom profiles, and sound speed measurements along the water column were obtained. This area is important for the scope of SeabedMap Project in relation to the study of submarine canyons as a potential for lifting and transporting masses of cold water over the shelf and edge of the continental shelf.

Geomorphic features such as submarine canyons and submarine plateaus were identified; further erosive features such as landslides and gullies also were present. The morphology was also influenced by tectonics. These results obtained add to recent studies that have shown how submarine canyons generate the ideal flow-topography environment, inducing the process of seasonal uplift of colder and saline water masses from the deepest to the shallowest areas, resulting in the formation of vortices, ecological differentiations, as well as the seasonal fertilization of the waters of the Northeast coast of Brazil, breaking the paradigm of an exclusively oligotrophic zone.

Marine Remote Sensing in Sweden, large spatiotemporal analysis of the Swedish shallow water habitats

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Marine vegetation communities constitute valuable habitats and generate significant ecosystem services. Knowledge of these habitats' areal distribution and change over time is therefore of great interest from several perspectives, including environmental monitoring and management.

During 2023, the Västerbotten County Board was tasked by the Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management to produce nationally comprehensive data from satellite imagery showing the presence of underwater vegetation. National maps were created for the years 2018-2022 in the platform "SAV Sweden". Through this, the seabed has been classified within 4300 km² per year along the coast of Sweden.

Nationally, approx. 1930 km² of the bottom was classified as covered by vegetation (average value 2018-2022), which corresponds to 46% of the analysed area. However, this differed markedly between different sea basins, where the Baltic Sea Proper had a corresponding value of approx. 55%, while the Gulf of Bothnia and the Skagerack-Kattegatt area approx. 35%. The spread was very small between years in absolute vegetation cover.

Total accuracy was estimated for the years 2021 and 2022 using drone imagery or drone imagery analysis. The accuracy was about 70% for both 2021 and 2022 with minor differences between years and sea basins.

As a result of seascape-level trend analysis (in the size range of 50-100 hectares), a total of 354 seascapes were identified with a statistical linear trend. They correspond to an area of 629 km² or 15% of a total of 4300 km² analysed. Nationally, the trend was marginally positive, with an increase in vegetation cover of about 40 km², corresponding to about 2% of the national subaquatic vegetation area. At seascape level, a total of 197 seascapes had a positive significant trend and 157 seascapes a significant negative trend in the period 2018-2022.

The analysis and data constitute a new valuable geographical layer for Sweden. The first deliverable covers ca 70 % of the national shallow sea area (0 to 3 m depth), generally characterized by high productivity and high ecological values. It will be an invaluable help in the implementation of the upcoming EU-wide restoration regulation (entry into force estimated in Q2/2024) and enable improved mapping and monitoring potential for the Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC) and the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (2008/56/EC). The underlying Copernicus data as well as the new maps is open access and usable by anyone. A continuation is under review with a decision pending early in 2024.

Measuring the impacts of ship anchoring

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Routine vessel anchoring impacts the seabed with direct and indirect implications the health of the shallow marine environment. Even still, anchoring practices remain largely unmeasured, undocumented, and most importantly, unregulated. Remarkably, anchoring is absent from any national and international policies designed to reduce human impacts on the marine environment.

Our pioneering field experiments measured the real-time impacts of anchoring in a multi-vessel campaign. We used two vessels: RV Ikatere, a 14 m catamaran used for data collection before, during and after the anchoring event; and RV Tangaroa, a 73 m blue water research vessel, which was at anchor for 24 hours in the Wellington Harbour anchorage, Aotearoa/New Zealand. In March 2024, fieldwork started by surveying and seafloor sediment sampling in the anchorage area before anchoring, as well as in a control site nearby. Then, RV Tangaroa was put on anchor, and equipped with a range of sensors measuring the immediate impacts in the water column. Simultaneously, RV Ikatere was also recording and sampling the anchoring impacts in the adjacent area (e.g., resuspended sediment plume sampling). Finally, after the anchoring event, the study region was resurveyed again to gain comparative datasets. For the entire duration of the fieldwork campaign (i.e., 3 days), moorings were deployed in strategic locations near the experiment area to measure variations in ambient environmental conditions that can be attributed to ship anchoring. The datasets collected during this field campaign will delineate a complete environmental signature during anchoring practices, including physical, chemical, biological, ecological changes. Collectively they will help constrain the spatial extent and severity of anchoring impacts, and provide real-time observations (e.g., sediment plume, noise pollution) and longer-term (e.g., seabed structure and composition modification) impacts of anchoring. This campaign aims to measure, for the first time globally, the range of real-time impacts of commonplace vessel anchoring practices. To achieve more sustainable and lower-impact shipping corridors, the hidden costs of ship anchoring must be incorporated into future global trade strategies and environmental management. Our new approaches are timely and will have global relevance, and as such could be presented to the Marine Environmental Protection Committee at the IMO.

Marine inventories to support conservation planning and the expansion of the MPA network in the Åland Islands

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The Baltic Sea is increasingly exploited by society, which generally harms the underwater environment. Comprehensive and high-quality data on marine environments is essential to manage and maintain ecosystems and ecosystem services effectively. This data is obtained by mapping species and habitat distributions.

The Åland Islands is an autonomous region off the southwestern coast of Finland, consisting of over 6700 islands and 11,700 km² of sea area. The surrounding Baltic Sea is an important element for the 30,000 people in Åland, with many gaining their livelihoods from activities related to the sea, such as maritime transport, tourism, and coastal fisheries. Establishing marine protected areas (MPAs) has been challenging due to the lack of knowledge on underwater marine nature, the private ownership of marine areas, and the active use of the sea. Thus, Åland is lagging behind the international goals for marine conservation, with only about 3% of the marine areas protected.

With a marine field station in Åland, Åbo Akademi University has systematically mapped the diverse underwater nature of Åland's coastal waters since 2017. These surveys and collated data amounted to 14,395 data points in 2023. In 2021, an adequate level of data was reached to produce reliable species distribution models. Altogether, 37 data layers on nature values and 16 on human activity data were used for a site-selection analysis using the Marxan decision support tool to aid marine conservation planning. The most suitable areas for protection were identified in different scenarios, considering predetermined protection goals based on national and international assessments. To survey previously unmapped offshore areas with potentially high nature values, additional mapping was started in 2023.

The results of the marine inventories are the basis for the ongoing expansion of the MPA network in Åland. Some areas have already been selected and redeemed by the Government of Åland and will reach protection status in the near future. Further, results are actively used to support ecosystem-based management, e.g., to improve the monitoring program for macrophytes and for environmental permissions and impact assessments in the marine environment.

To gain wider acceptance, the local stakeholders and broader community have been engaged in the process through presentations, social media, and by opening the used data for comments and input. Through close cooperation between scientists, officials at the Government of Åland, and the local community, major steps have been taken towards an improved, science-based, and coherent MPA network in the area.

Summit environment of the ferromanganese crust hosting Tropic Seamount (offshore Western Sahara)

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Tropic Seamount offshore Western Sahara (970 m water depth; 20°N) is the southernmost of the Canary Seamounts and a guyot that submerged below sea-level at least 70 mya ago (based on basal ferromanganese crust ages). Since then, the summit environment has received limited sedimentation and hosts hardgrounds and thick ferromanganese crusts containing an estimated €192 billion worth of tellurium (February 2024 prices). Several previous surveys have enacted multibeam echosounder seabed mapping, hydrodynamic modelling, ROV surveying and sampling to revealed a tidally dominated, heterogenous seabed environment and associated fauna.

The EU TRIDENT project is tasked with creating new technological tools for deep-sea impact assessment to supervise and monitor deep-sea activities. Tropic Seamount is the demonstration site for developed real-time monitoring technologies and protocols. In April 2024, the RV Mário Ruivo will collect additional survey and monitoring data to establish an environmental baseline against which small-scale impact simulations can be monitored demonstrating the “traffic light system” to avoid adverse impacts.

Results from the RV Mário Ruivo environmental baseline survey, and historical data, will be presented revealing habitats and geomorphologies of a ferromanganese crust-rich seamount summit area covering 120 km² and the EU TRIDENT concept explained.

High Resolution Ocean Modelling for Benthic Habitat Mapping on the Georges Bank

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In benthic habitat mapping, comprehensive data fields are valuable to properly characterize a region and conduct subsequent inferences on species habitats; however, many aspects of a region's oceanography, in particular water column data, are only sparsely available due to time and budget constraints of field operations and the practicality of data collection on a regional scale. The result is field campaigns which must compromise between spatial or temporal resolution and duration. Oceanographic simulation, validated by field observations, can augment field data, filling in gaps and offering additional opportunities for species habitat insights.

This study uses the Finite Volume Community Ocean Model (FVCOM) to calculate water column temperature, salinity and velocity, as well as bed shear stress throughout the Gulf of Maine with particular interest in the northeast Canadian section of Georges Bank, which has supported a large sea scallop (*Placopecten magellanicus*) fishery since the 1950s. The model is driven by coarser publicly available regional models; 1) the Gulf of Maine Operational Forecast System (GoMOFS) provides temperature and salinity at the boundaries as well as initialization fields; 2) the North American Regional Reanalysis (NARR) provides surface values for wind and the calculation of heat fluxes. Tidal forcing is calculated using the local Scotia-Fundy-Maine WebTide model. Our model is validated against public and private US NOAA and Canadian CHS tidal harmonic constituents from stations in the gulf and CTD casts from World Ocean Database on the Georges Bank.

Model resolution in the area of interest reaches 150 m in the horizontal and 1.0 m in the vertical, providing granularity not available in public models of the region and commensurate with the resolution of other habitat data for the area. Temporally, model outputs are produced at one-hour increments over a full year, allowing the calculation of fine-grained seasonal and monthly geo-located maps of the spatially varying statistics. These maps serve as inputs, among other data, to a random forest model of scallop habitats undertaken by project collaborators as part of a larger study allowing highly local water column variation to be analysed as a factor in these benthic habitats. This work discusses the processes involved in the setup, processing and validation of localized high-resolution simulations and the subsequent generation of geo-located maps with the objective of providing an overview to other benthic habitat studies where simulation derived data could provide valuable insight.

Quantifying the spatial extent and ecological function of artificial reef habitats offshore California, USA

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Marine infrastructure from offshore energy development can change the distribution and abundance of local marine habitats and species via the introduction of artificial hard substrate. This “artificial reef” effect potentially modifies a variety of local and regional processes, including those that drive the ecological dynamics of managed, sensitive, or non-native species. Artificial reefs may also enhance certain human activities such as fishing or diving. Decision makers must therefore understand how offshore projects that add significant amounts of hard substrate into the marine environment may be evaluated, managed, and potentially incorporated into an artificial reef program. On the west coast of the United States, these habitat issues are of particular importance due to: 1) the imminent decommissioning of oil and gas platforms and their associated subsea structures such as pipelines, power cables and wellheads, which may remove important habitat for managed fish species; and 2) the introduction of new marine infrastructure from offshore renewable energy facilities (i.e., the development of offshore wind) which can affect local biodiversity and food web structure. However, it remains unclear to what extent planned and de-facto artificial reef structures contribute to regional-scale ecological dynamics, particularly in proportion to natural reefs.

This project builds upon a previously synthesized reef habitat map of the Southern California Bight. Bathymetry and side scan sonar data is being collected to confirm location and determine the physical state of known artificial structures. Biological characteristics are assessed using visual surveys via SCUBA (for depths < 30m) or stereo-ROV (> 30m). Similar data on nearby natural habitats is also being collected to provide a basis for comparison. The goal is to determine what physical, biological, or geographical features are important for productivity of planned and de-facto artificial reef structures and what criteria should be used to evaluate future artificial reef proposals and projects at a regional scale to maximize environmental benefits and ecosystem services.

Building an artificial reef to withstand oceanographic, urban, and geological impacts

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Palos Verdes Reef (PVR) is an artificial reef that was designed to restore rocky-reef habitat that has been impacted by scour, sedimentation, and burial in the shallow subtidal portion of the Palos Verdes Peninsula in Los Angeles County, California, USA. The reef was designed to be resilient to ongoing sedimentation and turbidity challenges on the peninsula, and this project was a unique endeavour as restoring lost habitat in situ had not been attempted in a temperate rocky reef and kelp forest community. PVR was built in 2020 as 18 discrete modules using 52,729 tons of quarry rock placed approximately 8–80 m from existing, unburied rocky-reef habitat.

Bathymetric and side scan surveys were performed once prior to construction and annually thereafter. Using the mapping data, we identified prime locations for reef module placement: areas that are buried in a thin (< 1 m) layer of sediment and adjacent to existing, unburied rocky-reef habitat. Modules were positioned in a formation that followed the natural orientation of existing hard substrate to allow sediment to pass through without settling and were designed to mimic a nearby natural high-relief seafloor feature that has proven to be resistant to burial and sedimentation while also featuring the highest fish biomass of any rocky reef in the region. Rocky-reef associated taxa rapidly recruited to the restoration site, with visible changes occurring within just a few months post-construction. This rapid addition of understory and canopy-forming kelps to the newly added substrate poses a challenge for collecting and processing both bathymetry and side scan data. However, the data showed that there was no significant accumulation or scouring of sediment due to the placement of the reef and the quarry rocks have not moved, subsided, or been re-buried even in the face of strong storms, earthquakes, and tsunamis.

Application of single-beam sonar in detecting eelgrass *Zostera marina* L. distribution characteristics in China

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Seagrass meadows are declining at alarming rates globally due to both anthropogenic activities and natural threats. Seagrasses play key ecological roles in coastal ecosystems as primary producers and providers of habitat and environmental structure. Therefore, mapping seagrass beds is indispensable for the effective monitoring and management of coastal vegetated habitats.

In this poster, we summarize the advantages and disadvantages of various methods for detecting seagrass bed distribution characteristics. We explain in detail the steps involved in detecting eelgrass seagrass bed distribution characteristics with single-beam sonar, including instrument introduction, data acquisition, and data analysis. We also cite a few examples of studies that have utilized single-beam sonar detection technology to uncover the distribution characteristics of seagrass beds, such as using it to reveal the distribution of the eelgrass *Zostera marina* L. and threats from the green tide algae *Chaetomorpha linum* K. in Swan-Lake Lagoon (China). For instance, the largest eelgrass seagrass beds (29.17 km²) in China were discovered in the coastal waters of Tangshan using sonar detection technology. Finally, we propose that sonar should be combined with various detection techniques, such as field surveys and remote sensing techniques, to comprehensively assess the distribution characteristics of eelgrass seagrass beds. This integrated approach will provide detailed data for the effective management, protection, and restoration of seagrass beds.

Assessment of the impacts of protection on southern rock lobster across a network of marine protected areas off Victoria, Australia

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Southern rock lobster (*Jasus edwardsii*) is an ecologically and economically important species found across the southern portion of Australia and extending to New Zealand. They are both commercially and recreationally fished across their range. Within the coastal waters of Victoria, Australia, this fishery has seen declines in allowable catch due to decreasing stocks both through fishing pressure and environmental change. Marine protected areas (MPAs) offer a method for protecting a residual biomass of *J. edwardsii* from fishing pressure, but this species has shown variable responses to spatial protection. In this study, we use a dataset of *J. edwardsii* populations collected using a standardised fishing assessment trapping method where samples were collected inside and outside six MPAs distributed across the state of Victoria to determine the effectiveness of protection. From these datasets, we derived abundance (total, male, female), size (total, male, female), and reproductive condition (female only). We also collected information on the habitat and environments inside and outside the MPAs, including seafloor structure, temperature, hydrodynamics, and fishing pressure. This information was then combined in a multi-scale generalised additive mixed effects models (GAMMs) to assess the impact of MPA protection while accounting for any differences in habitat, environment, or fishing pressure. These relationships were also used to develop species distribution models to assess habitat suitability in relation to MPAs. The GAMMs showed that *J. edwardsii* have a strong relationship with habitat type, including a preference for more complex seafloor, lower temperatures, and decreased wave energy. There were also regional differences in the perceived importance of MPAs. In the eastern and central areas of the state (Cape Howe, Wilsons Promontory, Port Phillip Head) no significant differences were found when comparing populations of *J. edwardsii* inside and outside MPAs. However, the populations in the western region (Pt Addis, Merri, Discovery Bay) showed a strong and significant relationship with protection status where abundance was up to four times greater inside the MPA and the abundance of legal sized individuals increased to as much as five times within the MPA boundaries. Overall, these results show that the impact of MPAs has spatially variable effects on *J. edwardsii* populations across Victoria, with variation in environmental conditions, fishing effort, and habitat availability contributing to these differences. Additionally, the information provided by the distribution models has the potential to contribute to more effective management of this species through spatial representation of their habitat preferences.

National scale mapping of the invasive marine alga *Caulerpa cylindracea* in Croatian waters

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Green alga *Caulerpa cylindracea* is one of the most invasive non-native species in the Mediterranean Sea. After its first record within the Croatian waters in 2000, its spatial distribution was followed through different scientific expeditions and monitoring programs, mainly by using scuba divers and through local ecological knowledge. That resulted in more than 100 spatially different reports over 20 y period. In 2022 and 2023 we took the opportunity to map this species as a part of the national marine habitat mapping project in Croatian waters (AdriHab). Within AdriHab we recorded benthic video transects using a hand-held drop-down camera with no surface monitoring option but therefore with minimal dragging effect. The camera was installed within the stainless steel frame for protection, equipped with two fins, two lights for deeper waters, and a digital scuba depth meter placed within the camera's field of view. The camera was usually deployed and towed using 3,70 m inflatable boat with 18 hp engine, equipped with an onboard GPS logger. Most of the video transect covered the bottom from 2 to 40 m deep, while some extended down to a max 130 m within the protected areas. Obtained videos were analysed using a dedicated online spatial database that was developed for the AdriHab. It allowed us to spatially delineate recorded benthic habitats, geotag benthic species of interest, and export data in GIS format.

The simplicity of our towed camera together with an efficient online spatial database, resulted in record and analyses of more than 3700 video transects within less than 2 y period.

Caulerpa cylindracea, as one of the target species was documented in 565 transects, from 1 down to maximum 72 m depth. Collected data significantly surpasses a previous 20-year-long dataset. Obtained distribution is presented using Pan-European grids of 10 x 10 km for which an extensive number of transects provides sufficient data coverage and will be used for reporting according to the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive, descriptor D2.

In the case of *Caulerpa cylindracea*, we demonstrate how our unexpansive and highly efficient video recording system together with the database, can be used for the spatially extensive monitoring of the sessile macroscopic species of interest such as not-native organisms.

Mapping of the marine coastal and benthic habitats in Croatia (Adriatic Sea)

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Croatian marine waters cover a large part of the Adriatic Sea and include 5,835 km of coastline, 1,246 islands, islets, and reefs, within approximately 31,000 km² of territorial waters, and 23,870 km² of Croatian Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ). By the end of 2023, in period of 25 months, we completed benthic and coastal habitat mapping for 51% of Croatian marine waters. In total, 30,278 km² were mapped, with approximately 6,600 km² of this area involving direct mapping using acoustic methods (multibeam and side-scan sonar) for marine areas deeper than 15 m, as well as remote sensing (Sentinel-2 satellite imagery and digital ortho-photo images) for coastal and benthic habitats down to 15 m deep. An artificial neural network-based model using historical and newly obtained sediment and habitat type data was employed to map the remaining area of 23,617 km². In situ field validation was applied at more than 4,200 sites using ground truthing methods such as scuba diving and the use of ROVs, towed drop-down cameras, coastal observations, UAVs, and corers for granulometry.

A direct mapping was applied on the entire seabed down to 40 m, the entire seabed within MPAs, as well as Natura 2000 sites and selected areas of particular interest. We also mapped two selected areas within the EEZ. The final map was created at a scale of 1:5,000 for the MPAs, 1:10,000 for the Natura 2000 areas and selected areas of interest, 1:25,000 for other directly mapped areas, and 1:50,000 for the two selected areas in EEZ. Additionally, the area mapped using models was presented at a scale of 1:83,333. Benthic habitats were classified according to the National Classification of Marine Habitats in Croatia, which was revised as part of the habitat mapping project and amended to include newly described habitat types. At a minimum, habitats were mapped at the 3rd classification level, while priority, endangered, and rare habitat types were mapped at the 4th and 5th levels when possible. After generalization, the map became publicly available through the Nature protection information system web portal (www.bioportal.hr). Mapping was done within the framework of the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development project “Mapping of coastal and seabed habitats in waters under national jurisdiction”, cofunded by the EU from the European Structural and Investments Fund as part of the Operational Programme Competitiveness and Cohesion 2014 – 2020, and implemented by the group of science institutes and expert institutions.

